

Formation of Substellar Bodies in Cold Conditions

Gravitational Stability of Fluids in a Phase Transition

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Title image:
Simulation B75 with
 $\gamma_J = 0.5$ at $t = 18 \tau$
(Table 12.1)

RÉSUMÉ

INTRODUCTION Cette thèse traite de l'étude de la formation de corps solides froids de taille substellaire, par la fragmentation d'un fluide gravitationnellement instable et en transition de phase. L'intérêt principal est la formation potentielle de corps d' H_2 rocheux dans un mélange d' H_2 -He, à l'image de nuages moléculaires. Par ailleurs, la combinaison entre une transition de phase et la gravité pourrait être pertinente dans une grande gamme de situations astrophysiques, comme des disques proto-planétaires.

MOTIVATIONS La nucléosynthèse primordiale prédit une quantité de matière baryonique beaucoup plus grande qu'observé dans l'univers proche. Les corps solides froids d' H_2 formeraient un candidat idéal pour les baryons manquants dans les galaxies car ils sont quasiment indétectables. Dans des régions de gaz très froides, la formation de tels corps est possible car l' H_2 pourrait être en transition de phase. La formation peut aussi avoir lieu pendant l'effondrement gravitationnel de la formation d'étoiles ou dans des structures substellaires froides comme les globules cométaires. Les comètes observées dans les systèmes solaires pourraient être des résidus de corps d' H_2 beaucoup plus grands, car l' H_2 est très volatile et serait vaporisé avant d'être assez proche du soleil pour être détectable.

CONTEXTE Les nuages moléculaires consistent en $3/4$ d' H_2 et $1/4$ d'He. L'observation de glaces différentes et l'existence des comètes suggèrent que des transitions de phase se passent dans certaines régions froides. L' H_2 peut être en transition de phase en dessous de sa température critique (33 K) avec une densité suffisamment haute. Les conditions pour une condensation d' H_2 peuvent être atteintes pendant un effondrement gravitationnel en plan parallèle. Cet effondrement est la géométrie la plus rapide ayant pour conséquence une augmentation de la température d'un facteur 2 seulement. Une transition de phase peut donc être atteinte dans toutes les régions avec une température initiale de ≤ 15 K.

PHYSIQUES La stabilité gravitationnelle de fluides à une ou plusieurs composantes est étudiée en utilisant une analyse linéaire en se concentrant particulièrement sur les fluides en transition de phase. Le critère de Jeans pour un gaz idéal prédit une échelle minimum à partir de laquelle un fluide est instable. Pourtant, un fluide en transition de phase est instable gravitationnellement à toutes les échelles, car une compression n'augmente plus la pression mais elle augmente la fraction de corps condensés. Utilisant le potentiel intermoléculaire de Lennard-Jones, une étude de l'équilibre viriel montre que des corps d' H_2 peuvent se former de façon arbitraire, même à des températures relativement hautes jusqu'à 400 – 600 K. Il existe un domaine hors-équilibre viriel dans lequel les corps d' H_2 se forment de manière quasiment instantanée.

SIMULATIONS La dynamique non linéaire de fluides à une ou deux composantes en transition de phase ou pas est étudiée au moyen du code numérique de dynamique moléculaires LAMMPS. Les super-molécules sont utilisées pour combiner le potentiel de Lennard-Jones ainsi que le potentiel gravitationnel. Des simulations de test affirment l'indépendance du nombre de super-molécules, ainsi que la reproduction d'un effondrement gravitationnel d'un gaz idéal selon le critère de Jeans. Les simulations confirment que des fluides en transition de phase sont instables gravitationnellement, indépendamment de la force du potentiel gravitationnel. Les instabilités produisent un vaste éventail de masses de corps solides : petits grumeaux, comètes, planétoïdes. Une instabilité dans un mélange d' H_2 -He mène soit à la formation d'un planétoïde gazeux d'He si l'instabilité est en-dessus du critère de Jeans, soit à la formation d'un planétoïde rocheux d' H_2 si l'instabilité est en-dessous du critère de Jeans avec de l' H_2 en transition de phase.

CONCLUSION Cette thèse montre que la physique des fluides froids et auto-gravitant (e.g. les nuages moléculaires sombres), est beaucoup plus riche que ce qui est généralement supposé. Le processus de ségrégation de petits grumeaux dans un champs gravitationnel ne peut pas être simulé avec des codes numériques hydrodynamiques traditionnels, mais bien avec une approche de super-molécules. Les observations, l'analyse linéaire et viriel ainsi que les simulations par ordinateurs suggèrent que la formation de corps solides d' H_2 de taille substellaire est possible dans des régions froides grâce à la combinaison de la transition de phase et de la gravité. En effet, un fluide en transition de phase est instable gravitationnellement, indépendamment de la force du potentiel gravitationnel. Une transition de phase d' H_2 est facilement atteinte pendant un effondrement gravitationnel plane parallèle si la température initiale est ≤ 15 K.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

EINFÜHRUNG Die vorliegende Doktorarbeit dokumentiert das Studium der Bildung von kalten, substellaren Körpern durch die Fragmentierung eines Fluids im Phasenübergang bei einer Gravitationsinstabilität. Das Hauptinteresse liegt in der potentiellen Entstehung von festen, substellaren H_2 -Körpern in kalten H_2 -He Gemischen, wie zum Beispiel Molekülwolken. Die Kombination von Phasenübergängen und Gravitation ist auch in vielen anderen astrophysikalischen Gebieten relevant, wie zum Beispiel bei protoplanetaren Scheiben.

MOTIVATION Die primordiale Nukleosynthese prognostiziert eine grössere Menge an Baryonischer Materie als im nahen Universum beobachtet wird. Kalte H_2 -Körper wären ein idealer Kandidat für die fehlenden Baryonen in Galaxien, da sie nur schwer zu entdecken sind. In sehr kalten Gas-Regionen können solche Körper entstehen, da ein H_2 Phasenübergang möglich ist. Die Bildung solcher Körper könnte ebenfalls während des Gas-Kollapses bei der Entstehung eines Sterns oder in substellaren Strukturen wie Knoten von planetarischen Nebeln erfolgen.

KONTEXT Molekülwolken bestehen aus $3/4 \text{ H}_2$ und $1/4 \text{ He}$. Beobachtungen von interstellarem Eis und das Vorhandensein von Kometen deuten an, dass Phasenübergänge in kalten Regionen erfolgen. H_2 kann in einem Phasenübergang sein, wenn seine Temperatur unter dem kritischen Punkt liegt (33 K) und er eine genügend hohe Dichte hat. H_2 Kondensationsbedingungen können während einer planparallelen Kontrahierung erreicht werden. Dies ist die schnellste Kollapsgeometrie bei welcher die Temperatur nur um den Faktor 2 steigt. Von daher kann ein H_2 Phasenübergang immer erreicht werden, solange die Anfangstemperatur unter 15 K liegt.

PHYSIK Die Gravitationsstabilität von Fluiden, welche aus einer oder mehreren Komponenten bestehen, wird mit linearer Analyse — mit Betonung auf Phasenübergänge — untersucht. Das Jeans-Kriterium besagt, dass eine Mindestmasse benötigt wird, damit ein ideales Gas gravitationsinstabil ist. Im Falle eines Phasenübergangs ist ein Fluid, unabhängig seiner Masse, immer gravitationsinstabil, weil eine Komprimierung nicht mehr den Druck sondern den Anteil fester Körper erhöht. Die Virial-Gleichgewichts-Analyse mit Hilfe des Lennard-Jones zwischenmolekularen Potentials zeigt, dass kleine H_2 -Körper sogar bei sehr hohen Temperaturen bis 400 – 600 K willkürlich entstehen können. Es gibt einen Bereich, bei dem kein Virial-Gleichgewicht möglich ist und in welchem feste H_2 -Körper beinahe augenblicklich entstehen.

SIMULATIONEN Die nichtlineare Dynamik von Fluiden, bestehend aus einer oder zwei Komponenten, wird mit dem numerischen Moleküldynamik-Programm LAMMPS in und ausserhalb eines Phasenübergangs simuliert. Super-Moleküle werden benutzt, um das Lennard-Jones Potential mit dem Gravitationspotential zu kombinieren. Test-Simulationen bestätigen die Unabhängigkeit von der Anzahl der Super-Moleküle und bilden den Gravitationskollaps eines idealen Gases nach. Die Simulationen bestätigen, dass ein Fluid, unabhängig von der Stärke des Gravitationsfeldes, im Phasenübergang gravitationsinstabil ist. Während der Instabilität entstehen Körper von kleinen Oligomeren über Kometen bis zu Planetoiden in einem grossen Massenspektrum. Eine Gravitationsinstabilität in einem H_2 -He Fluid führt zur Bildung eines He-Gasplanetoiden, falls die Instabilität oberhalb des Jeans-Kriterium liegt und zur Bildung eines H_2 -Gesteinsplanetoiden, falls die Instabilität unterhalb des Jeans-Kriterium liegt und H_2 im Phasenübergang ist.

SCHLUSSFOLGERUNG Die vorliegende Doktorarbeit weist darauf hin, dass die Physik von kalten Fluiden mit Eigengravitation, wie zum Beispiel Molekülwolken, viel reichhaltiger ist als normalerweise angenommen wird. Die Segregation von kleinen H_2 Klumpen und die Akkumulation zu grösseren Körpern in einem Gravitationsfeld kann mit herkömmlichen hydrodynamischen Programmen nicht simuliert werden, ist aber mit Hilfe von Super-Molekülen möglich. Beobachtungen, lineare Analyse, Virial-Gleichgewichts-Untersuchungen sowie Computer Simulationen weisen darauf hin, dass die Entstehung von substellaren H_2 -Körpern in kalten Regionen dank der Kombination von Phasenübergängen und Gravitation möglich ist. Fluide im Phasenübergang sind unabhängig von der Stärke des Gravitationsfeldes gravitationsinstabil. Ein H_2 Phasenübergang kann während einer planparallelen Kontraktion leicht erreicht werden, solange die Anfangstemperatur unter 15 K liegt.

ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION The present thesis undertakes a study of the formation of cold, substellar sized bodies due to the fragmentation of gravitationally unstable fluids in a phase transition. The main interest is the potential formation of rocky, substellar H_2 bodies in cold H_2 -He fluids such as molecular clouds, but the combination of phase transition and gravity may be relevant for a wider range of astrophysical situations, such as proto-planetary disks.

MOTIVATION The Big Bang nucleosynthesis predicts a much larger amount of baryonic matter than observed in the low- z universe. Cold H_2 bodies would be an ideal candidate for the missing baryons in galaxies as they are hardly detectable. In very cold dark gas regions such bodies can form as H_2 may be in a phase transition. The formation can also happen during the collapsing phase of star formation or in cold, substellar structures such as cometary knots. The comets observed in our solar system may be remnants of much larger H_2 bodies, as the volatile H_2 would vaporize before being close enough to the sun for detection.

CONTEXT Molecular clouds consist of $3/4$ H_2 and $1/4$ He. Observations of various ices and the existence of comets suggest that phase transition processes are happening in cold regions. H_2 can be in a phase transition below its critical temperature (33 K) if the density is high enough. H_2 condensation conditions can be reached during plane-parallel contraction, which is the fastest collapsing geometry and where the temperature rise is only of a factor 2. A H_2 phase transition can therefore be reached in all regions with an initial temperature ≤ 15 K.

PHYSICS The gravitational stability of single- and multi-component fluids is studied using linear analysis, with special emphasis on phase transitions. The Jeans criterion for ideal gas fluids predicts a minimum scale at which a fluid is unstable, while fluids in a phase transition are gravitationally unstable at any scale, because compression does not increase pressure, but the condensed phase fraction. Using the inter-molecular Lennard-Jones potential, the virial equilibrium study shows that small H_2 clumps may form arbitrarily even at relatively high temperatures of up to 400 – 600 K. There is an unvirializable density domain where ice clumps form almost instantly.

SIMULATIONS The non-linear dynamics of single-component and binary fluids in and out of a phase transition are studied using the molecular dynamics code LAMMPS. Super-molecules are used to combine the Lennard-Jones and gravitational potential. Test-simulations affirm the independence of the number of super-molecules and correctly reproduce ideal gas collapses in accordance with the Jeans criterion. The simulations confirm that fluids

presenting a phase transition are gravitationally unstable, independent of the strength of the gravitational potential. The instabilities produce a wide spectrum of ice clumps, from small multimers, to comets, to gravitationally bound planetoids. Instabilities in H₂-He fluids lead to the formation of gaseous He-planetoids if above the ideal gas Jeans criterion, or to the formation of rocky H₂-planetoids if below the Jeans criterion and if H₂ is in a phase transition.

CONCLUSIONS This thesis shows that the physics of cold self-gravitation fluids such as dark molecular clouds is much richer than usually assumed. The segregation in a gravitational field of small grains towards larger bodies such as comets and planetoids cannot be simulated with traditional hydrodynamical codes, but is possible with a super-molecular approach. Observations, linear and virial analysis as well as computer simulations suggest the possibility of the formation of substellar H₂ bodies due to the combination of phase transition and gravity in cold regions, as fluids in a phase transition are gravitationally unstable, independent of the strength of the gravitational potential. H₂ phase transition is reached easily during plane-parallel collapses if the initial temperature is ≤ 15 K.

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CONTENTS

List of Figures	xvi
List of Tables	xx
i CONTEXT	1
1 INTRODUCTION	2
1.1 Motivation	2
1.2 Thesis structure	4
2 INTERSTELLAR MEDIUM	5
2.1 Phases	5
2.2 Turbulences	8
3 MOLECULAR CLOUDS	9
3.1 Physical properties of molecular hydrogen and helium . . .	9
3.1.1 Hydrogen Helium mixture	11
3.2 Detection	11
3.2.1 CO emission	12
3.2.2 Other H ₂ detection methods	12
3.3 Dark clouds	14
3.4 Cometary knots	15
3.5 Interstellar ice	15
3.6 Dark gas	18
3.7 Star formation	18
4 DARK BARYONS	21
4.1 Dynamic evidence for missing matter	21
4.2 Baryons	22
4.3 Big Bang nucleosynthesis	22
4.4 Dark Baryons candidates	24
4.4.1 Warm-hot intergalactic medium	25
4.4.2 Dark H ₂ disk	26
4.4.3 Substellar bodies	27
4.4.4 Massive compact halo object	28
ii PHYSICS	29
5 EQUATION OF STATE OF A FLUID	30
5.1 Ideal gas fluid	30
5.2 van der Waals fluid	30
5.2.1 Density derivative	33
5.3 Fluid mixture	33
6 PLANE-PARALLEL COLLAPSE	34
6.1 Energy and radiation transfer during contraction	34
6.1.1 Gravitational energy	34
6.1.2 Radiative cooling	36
6.2 Interstellar Conditions	39

7	GRAVITATIONAL STABILITY	41
7.1	Gravitational stability of a single component fluid	41
7.1.1	Gaseous phase	42
7.1.2	Phase transition	42
7.2	Gravitational stability of a fluid mixture	43
7.2.1	Binary fluid	44
7.2.2	Multi-component fluid	45
7.2.3	Gaseous phase	45
7.2.4	Phase transition	46
8	LENNARD-JONES INTER-MOLECULAR POTENTIAL	47
8.1	Lennard-Jones mixtures	48
8.1.1	Binary mixture	48
8.2	Virial theorem	51
8.2.1	Lagrange-Jacobi identity	51
8.2.2	Homogeneous density	51
8.2.3	Homogeneous sphere	54
8.2.4	Condensed bodies	55
8.3	Dynamical friction	57
iii	SIMULATIONS	59
9	METHOD	60
9.1	Molecular dynamics	60
9.1.1	Potential solver	60
9.1.2	Time integration	61
9.1.3	Super-molecules	63
9.1.4	Ice clump detection	64
9.2	Units	65
9.3	Plane perturbation	66
9.4	Visualization	66
10	TEST SIMULATIONS	68
10.1	Gravitational solver	68
10.1.1	Kepler orbit	68
10.1.2	Direct, Fourier space and multilevel summation comparison	69
10.2	Super-molecule concept tests	71
10.2.1	Potential energy	71
10.2.2	Cluster percentage	73
10.2.3	Precipitation in an external field	74
11	SINGLE COMPONENT SIMULATIONS	75
11.1	One-phase fluid	75
11.1.1	Time evolution	75
11.1.2	Comet size distribution	77
11.1.3	Scaling	81
11.1.4	Extrapolation to physical scale	83
11.2	Phase transition	85
11.2.1	Fluid without gravity	87

11.2.2	Self-gravitating fluid above Jeans criterion	87
11.2.3	Self-gravitating fluid below Jeans criterion	92
11.3	Planetoid densities	96
12	BINARY FLUID MIXTURE SIMULATIONS	97
12.1	Above critical temperatures	97
12.2	Between critical temperatures	102
12.3	Below critical temperatures	107
12.4	Virial theorem	109
12.5	Influence of β -molecules on α -molecules below ideal gas Jeans criterion	112
12.6	Physical systems	113
iv	CONCLUSIONS	117
13	FLOW CHART	118
14	CONCLUSIONS	121
14.1	Analytic results	121
14.2	Simulations	122
14.2.1	Single component fluid simulations	122
14.2.2	Binary fluid simulations	124
14.3	Instability in H ₂ -He fluid	125
14.4	Wrapping up	125
15	PERSPECTIVES	128
15.1	Physical models	128
15.2	Technical challenges	129
15.2.1	Increase number of super-molecules	129
15.2.2	Low density	130
15.2.3	Isolated system	131
15.2.4	Radiative transfer	132
v	APPENDIX	133
A	LAMMPS USAGE	134
A.1	Pre-processing	134
A.2	Simulation run	134
A.3	Post-processing	135
B	LAMMPS RUN-SCRIPT	137
	Publications	143
	BIBLIOGRAPHY	145

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1	2014 Reprocessed Haslam 408 MHz Map.	6
Figure 2.2	LAB HI Survey.	6
Figure 2.3	Velocity Integrated CO Map.	6
Figure 3.1	H ₂ and He phase diagrams in cold and low pressure conditions.	10
Figure 3.2	3D H ₂ and He phase diagrams.	10
Figure 3.3	Thackeray’s Globules.	16
Figure 3.4	Cometary knots in the Helix nebula.	16
Figure 3.5	Critical points and triple points of common molecules in the ISM.	17
Figure 3.6	Stellar initial mass function.	19
Figure 4.1	Baryons with spin $J = 1/2$	23
Figure 4.2	The relative amounts of the different constituents of the Universe.	24
Figure 4.3	Baryon census.	25
Figure 4.4	Hubble sequence mass fraction.	26
Figure 5.1	van der Waals phase diagram for a fluid with $T_r = 0.9$	30
Figure 5.2	van der Waals phase diagram for a fluid with a temperature of $T_r = 0.2 - T_r = 1.2$	32
Figure 5.3	H ₂ and He laboratory data and van der Waals phase diagrams.	33
Figure 6.1	Collapsing geometries.	35
Figure 6.2	Absorption probability calculated by Monte Carlo	38
Figure 6.3	Adiabatic compression curves of an initial sphere to sheet-, filament- and point-like geometries.	40
Figure 7.1	van der Waals EOS, including the Maxwell construct.	43
Figure 8.1	Lennard-Jones potential.	47
Figure 8.2	Van der Waals phase diagram with Maxwell construct.	50
Figure 8.3	R/c_r and A/c_a values for H ₂ -He mixtures.	52
Figure 8.4	van der Waals phase transition (grey background, dotted lines) and unvirializable densities (within solid lines) of H ₂ -He mixtures with $x_\alpha = 1$ (blue), $x_\alpha = 0.75$ (cyan), $x_\alpha = 0.5$ (black), $x_\alpha = 0.25$ (yellow) and $x_\alpha = 0$ (red). Dots: T_{\max}	53
Figure 8.5	Minimum mass of isothermal equilibrium curves for H ₂ homogeneous spheres.	55
Figure 8.6	Virial equilibrium of gravitating Lennard-Jones homogeneous isothermal spheres.	56
Figure 9.1	MSM essential ideas.	62
Figure 9.2	Algorithmic steps for MSM.	62
Figure 9.3	Mean kinetic energy as a function of the maximum displacement in an ice clump.	65

Figure 9.4	2D density map of 3D space.	67
Figure 9.5	Color mapping of density map.	67
Figure 10.1	Kepler orbits for FFT solver.	68
Figure 10.2	Kepler orbits for MSM solver.	69
Figure 10.3	Periodic boundary conditions gravity solver test. . .	70
Figure 10.4	Isolated system gravity solver test.	71
Figure 10.5	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of the isolated system gravity solver test.	72
Figure 10.6	LJ potential energy as a function of the number of super-molecules.	73
Figure 10.7	Fraction of bound molecules as a function of the number of super-molecules.	74
Figure 10.8	z -Coordinate of the centre of mass of comets as a function of time of the SF simulation.	74
Figure 11.1	Temperature and fraction of bound molecules in comets of the one-phase fluid simulations.	76
Figure 11.2	Density and evolution of perturbation density of one- phase fluids.	77
Figure 11.3	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of the simulation OPGs.	78
Figure 11.4	3D-view of simulation OPGs.	79
Figure 11.5	Distribution of the y - and z -coordinates of planetoid centre of mass.	80
Figure 11.6	Temperature distribution of unbound molecules and comets.	80
Figure 11.7	Mean temperature over four one-phase fluid simu- lations OPGs with different random seeds.	81
Figure 11.8	Snapshot comet-size distribution sequence of all OPGs simulations.	82
Figure 11.9	Snapshot comet-size distribution summation sequence of OPGs simulations.	82
Figure 11.10	Time and size of the largest comet at the appearance of the turning point.	83
Figure 11.11	Extrapolation of the comet mass distribution for a real H_2 molecular fluid.	83
Figure 11.12	Position of the LJ simulations in a corresponding van der Waals phase diagram.	86
Figure 11.13	Temperature as a function of time of non-gravitating fluids.	87
Figure 11.14	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of simulation PT2-2 without gravity.	88
Figure 11.15	Close-up 3D-view of a medium sized comet.	89
Figure 11.16	Temperature distribution of unbound molecules and comets of PT2-2 without gravity.	90
Figure 11.17	Temperature as a function of time of sufficiently self- gravitating fluids.	90

Figure 11.18	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of sufficiently self-gravitating simulation PT1-3 . . .	91
Figure 11.19	Temperature as a function of time of weakly self-gravitating fluids.	92
Figure 11.20	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of weakly self-gravitating simulation PT2-2.	93
Figure 11.21	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of weakly self-gravitating simulation PT3-2.	94
Figure 11.22	Temperature distribution of unbound molecules and comets as a function of comet size of PT3-2.	95
Figure 11.23	Density of planetoid as a function of the radius. . .	96
Figure 12.1	Temperature and fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulations A10, A75, A50, A25 and A00.	99
Figure 12.2	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of the simulation A75 with $\gamma = 1.5$	100
Figure 12.3	Density of planetoid as a function of the radius of the simulations A75 and B75.	101
Figure 12.4	Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulation A75 _S	102
Figure 12.5	Fraction of bound β -molecules as a function of N_{tot} of simulation A75 _S	102
Figure 12.6	Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulations B10, B75, B50, B25 and B00 with $\gamma_J = 1.5$	103
Figure 12.7	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of the simulation B75 with $\gamma = 1.5$	104
Figure 12.8	Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulations B10, B75, B50, B25 and B00 with $\gamma_J = 0.5$	105
Figure 12.9	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of the simulation B75 with $\gamma = 0.5$	106
Figure 12.10	Fraction of bound β -molecules as a function of time of the simulations B75 _{γ}	107
Figure 12.11	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of the simulation B75 _{γ} with $\gamma = 0.8$	108
Figure 12.12	Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulations C10, C75, C50, C25 and C00 with $\gamma_J = 1.5$	109
Figure 12.13	Snapshot time-sequence and comet-size distribution of the simulation C75 with $\gamma = 1.5$	110
Figure 12.14	Fraction of bound molecules with $m_{\text{cl}} > m_{\text{He}}$ as a function of time of the simulations A75, A75 ₀₁ , B75 and B75 ₀₁ , with $\gamma_J = 1.5$	111

Figure 12.15	Density of planetoid at $t = 5\tau$ as a function of the radius of the simulations A75, A75 ₀₁ , B75 and B75 ₀₁ , with $\gamma_J = 1.5$	112
Figure 12.16	Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the normal simulations B75s, B75 where the β -molecules were removed B10 with $\gamma_J = 0.5$	112
Figure 12.17	γ_J of different total fluid masses with $T = 10$ K as a function of number density.	113
Figure 12.18	Snapshots and comet-size distributions of the simulations SSM01, SSM02 and SSE04.	115
Figure 13.1	Flow chart for plane-parallel perturbation.	119
Figure 14.1	126

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2.1	Mass distribution of hydrogen in the Milky Way ($R < 20$ kpc).	5
Table 3.1	Types of isolated ^a molecular clouds.	9
Table 3.2	Dark cloud substructure.	15
Table 4.1	Dark baryon candidates.	25
Table 8.1	Lattice constants.	52
Table 8.2	Condensed and uncondensed bodies in a Lennard-Jones fluid using the Lagrange-Jacobi identity.	55
Table 10.1	Parameters of the super-molecule test simulations.	73
Table 11.1	Parameters of the one-phase fluid simulations.	75
Table 11.2	Parameters of the phase transition simulations.	85
Table 12.1	Parameters of the binary mixture simulations.	98

Part I

CONTEXT

The following chapters present an introduction and situate this work in the scientific content. §1 states the main motivations for the present work. §3 gives an introduction to molecular clouds, with an emphasis on cold dark clouds. §4 recalls evidence for dark matter, summarizes the Big Bang nucleosynthesis and presents candidates for dark baryons.

*H₂ phase transition
+ gravity
=*
Substellar H₂ bodies

The present work is the study of the formation of cold, substellar sized bodies due to the fragmentation of gravitationally unstable fluids in a phase transition. The formed bodies can cover a wide range of size: A few molecules, called multimers, a few grams or kilograms, usually named snowflakes or snowballs, and even comets and planetoids. As their temperature is very low, they are difficult to detect. The investigated fluids can be interpreted as hydrogen-helium mixtures, omnipresent in the astrophysical context. The main targets are cold molecular clouds and cometary knots, leading to the formation of rocky, substellar H₂ bodies. Nevertheless, the study was made general enough to allow for a wide range of application, such as protoplanetary disks.

This work cannot be situated in one domain specifically, on the contrary it lies in-between several and tries, as much as possible, to combine them. This is already evident in the title of the present thesis, since a fluid in a phase transition is neither gaseous nor solid/liquid, but a little bit of both, and nonetheless ultimately different from each phase. The scientific content could be placed in astronomy, physics, chemistry, thermodynamics, and even computer science, and is best described as combining and linking all of them. One motivation of this work is to propose substellar H₂ bodies as possible candidates for the missing baryons. Being not totally invisible, but very difficult to detect, these bodies lie between dark and visible matter. The Jeans criterion usually is considered the threshold between molecular clouds and star formation regions. As will be shown throughout this work, this is only correct when considering the ideal gas assumption, which is not possible for fluids in a phase transition. Fluids in a phase transition are automatically Jeans critical, without forming stars though, and lie therefore between molecular clouds and star formation regions. It is only fitting, that in order to be able to perform computer simulations, techniques of both astrophysical codes and molecular dynamics codes had to be combined.

1.1 MOTIVATION

The investigation of a new topic is of course a motivation in itself, even if there may not be an immediate application related to it. In the present work, though, in addition to pure scientific curiosity, there are several reasons why the study of gravitational instabilities of fluids in a phase transition is of great interest for an wider range of domains:

- *Solid H₂ as dark baryons*

The debate whether dark matter is baryonic or non-baryonic has been going on for a long time: At present, the common understanding is that

most of the undetected matter is in fact non-baryonic (be it cold, warm, or hot). A small fraction has to be baryonic though, as the Big Bang nucleosynthesis predicts that we are still missing at least a factor 2 of the baryonic matter. Pfenninger et al. (1994) argue that a fraction of the dark matter in disk galaxies is in form of a very cold H_2 disk, undetectable in the near future due to a temperature very close to the CMB background. This dark gas would be fractal, the smallest structures being clumpuscules with mass of $\sim 10^{-3} M_\odot$ and size of 30 AU. Collisions between such clumpuscules prevents Jupiter-sized or larger H_2 bodies, but the presence of smaller bodies is possible, if their initial formation is possible. The possibility of solid H_2 as a candidate for baryonic dark matter is also discussed by other authors, as described in more details in the next chapters. The presence of solid H_2 , either within dark molecular clouds or outside thereof, would reduce the amount of missing baryonic matter in disk galaxies.

Big Bang
nucleosynthesis:
Missing baryons

Dark H_2 disk:
*May contain
solid H_2*

- *Formation of solid H_2 in clumpuscules*

When in a phase transition, H_2 is gravitationally unstable at any scale leading to the formation of solid H_2 . The above mentioned clumpuscules have a density of $\sim 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$. At this density, H_2 is in a phase transition below 3.2 K. As the clumpuscules have a temperature very close to the CMB (≥ 2.7 K), at least a fraction of them should have a H_2 phase transition. Therefore, H_2 bodies of any size would form in a very cold, fractal H_2 disk.

H_2 phase transition:
 $n \approx 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$
 $T \leq 3.2 \text{ K}$.

- *Formation of solid H_2 during star formation*

Star formation starts by the contraction of molecular clouds. Due to the fact that the collapsing geometries have different speeds, a contraction can be pictured in three steps. First, a plane-parallel collapse happens, as the sheet-like collapsing geometry is the fastest. This is followed by filament-like collapses and ultimately, dispersed throughout, point-like collapses occur, where stars can form. The sheet-like collapsing geometries are not only the fastest, but the temperature rises only by a factor ~ 2 and the opacity remains almost the same. Therefore, during a plane-parallel collapse, all molecular clouds below ~ 15 K can enter a H_2 phase transition at high enough density, and, if cooling is possible, even at higher initial temperatures ≤ 30 K. Any star-formation region with a low enough initial temperature to reach a H_2 phase transition is thus able to and should produce solid H_2 during the first step of a collapse.

H_2 phase transition:
*Plane-parallel
collapse with
 $T \leq 15 \text{ K}$*

- *Formation of solid H_2 in cometary knots*

Cometary knots, as observed in nearby planetary nebulae may have temperatures of ~ 10 K in their centre and their mass is estimated to a few $10^{-5} M_\odot$. Other than the clumpuscules, these cometary knots are not cold enough to be in a phase transition, but, similar to star formation regions, a H_2 phase transition is possible in the case of a sheet-like compression due to turbulences. If, H_2 bodies are forming in

H_2 phase transition:
Turbulences

cometary knots, there would be a large amount of potential birthplaces for solid H_2 , as these knots can be expected to exist in many places such as planetary nebulae, remnants of super novae and asymptotic giant branch winds.

- *Comets as remnants of solid H_2*

One arguments against the presence of solid H_2 bodies is of course that none has been observed thus far. This is to be expected for bodies far away from Earth, as they are very difficult to detect. But what about the Solar neighbourhood? One argument – although rather hypothetical at the moment – can be made that we are already observing these bodies without knowing: comets. These small bodies consist, at least when observed, mostly of H_2O ice, dust and more complex molecules. Since comets are only seen in proximity of the Sun, they could theoretically consist of huge masses of H_2 farther away. The H_2 part would be vaporize and outgassed due to solar radiation before being observable. If comets are in fact only the tip of the iceberg, that is, only the remnants of much larger H_2 -bodies, then there would be enough occurrences in the solar neighbourhood which would add up to a large amount of solid H_2 bodies.

Observed comets:
Remnants of larger
 H_2 bodies?

1.2 THESIS STRUCTURE

Nowadays, a typical thesis consists of a general introduction, followed by published and/or soon-to be published articles of the author. Those preceded by introductory texts and followed up by additional details. In my personal opinion, this “patch-work” is aesthetically not very pleasing, especially if the articles are included in their original formatting. For that reason, a different structure was chosen for the present thesis: The general introduction is given in Part i, but it is not followed by the inclusion of the two articles FP2015a (Füglister & Pfenniger 2015a) and FP2015b (Füglister & Pfenniger 2015b). Instead the content of the two articles is integrated in slightly different form in Part ii, covering the physics of fluids in a phase transition, Part iii, presenting the simulation method and results, and Part iv, summarizing the most important results and future challenges. It has to be emphasized that the presented material is the result of the collaboration with Daniel Pfenniger, co-author of both articles, and I would like to thank him for agreeing to publish our results in this format.

SYSTEM OF UNITS The usual system of units used in astronomy is the Centimetre-Gram-Second system of units (CGS). However, the International Astronomical Union (IAU) actually encourages the use of the International System of Units (SI)¹, which is why values in this work (as well as the published articles) are given in either this system or using astronomical units such as AU, pc, M_\odot and M_\oplus .

¹ https://www.iau.org/publications/proceedings_rules/units/

INTERSTELLAR MEDIUM

The interstellar medium covers, as the name indicates, all baryonic matter between stars. It consists primarily of hydrogen, either in ionized (HII, see Fig. 2.1), neutral (HI, see Fig. 2.2) or molecular form (H₂, see Fig. 2.3), helium and a small fraction of heavier atoms in similar abundance as the primordial one (see Table 2.1), even though thanks to star formation and subsequent stellar feedback, the metallicity has increased. Although there is a mass infall from the intergalactic medium and stellar input of $\sim 0.5 M_{\odot} \text{yrs}^{-1}$ each in the Milky Way, the mass of the interstellar medium is slowly decreasing as the star formation has a higher mass flow of $\sim 1.3 M_{\odot} \text{yrs}^{-1}$. In this chapter, the interstellar medium is briefly introduced, whereas the next chapter will go into more details on the densest regions of the interstellar medium, the molecular clouds. For a much more thorough study on the physics and observations of the interstellar medium, see Draine (2011).

Mass infall rate
 \wedge
 Star formation rate

Table 2.1.: Mass distribution of hydrogen in the Milky Way ($R < 20$ kpc).

<i>Phase</i>	$M / 10^9 M_{\odot}$	M / M_{H}	M / M_{gas}
HII	1.12	0.23	0.17
HI	2.9	0.60	0.43
H ₂	0.84	0.17	0.13
Total H	4.9	1	0.73
He	1.8		0.27
Total gas ^a	6.7		1
Molecular clouds	1.5		0.22

Notes: Values from Draine (2011).

^(a) H₂ is supposed to be almost uniquely in gaseous phase, although the present work shows that solid H₂ is a real possibility.

2.1 PHASES

The interstellar medium has a wide range of densities and temperature and can be observed at many wavelengths. It is usually divided into several phases. Historically, it was split into three phases: the cold dense phase (1), the warm intercloud phase (2) and the very hot gas (3). However, this leaves out many details, and especially cold neutral hydrogen and molecular hydrogen would be in the same phase. Draine (2011) proposes 7, more detailed phases:

Figure 2.1.: The reprocessed Haslam 408 MHz map of Remazeilles et al. (2015).
Credit: Legacy Archive for Microwave Background Data Analysis (LAMBDA), NASA.

Figure 2.2.: HEALPIX resampling of Leiden/Argentine/Bonn (LAB) Survey of Galactic HI (from Kalberla et al. 2005).
Credit: LAMBDA, NASA.

Figure 2.3.: The Dame et al. (2001) composite map of interstellar molecular clouds, as traced by the 115 GHz line of CO. The CO line intensity has been integrated over all observed velocities.
Credit: LAMBDA, NASA.

1. *Coronal gas*

This gas is shock-heated by supernova explosions. It has very low density $\sim 1000 \text{ m}^{-3}$ and high temperature ($> 10^5 \text{ K}$) and has a volume filling factor of ~ 0.5 . It is observed by UV, x-ray and radio synchrotron emission.

$$n \approx 1000 \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$T > 10^5 \text{ K}$$

2. *HII gas*

The ionized hydrogen is photoionized by ultraviolet radiation of hot stars and is also called warm ionized medium (WIM). Its density lies in the range of $10^5 - 10^{10} \text{ m}^{-3}$, its temperature is $\sim 10^4 \text{ K}$ and it fills ~ 0.1 of the volume. It is observed by optical line emission and the thermal radio continuum.

$$n = 10^5 - 10^{10} \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$T \approx 10^4 \text{ K}$$

3. *Warm HI*

This mostly atomic gas, also referred to as the warm neutral medium (WNM) is rather sparse ($n \approx 6 \cdot 10^5 \text{ m}^{-3}$), has a temperature of $\sim 5000 \text{ K}$ and a volume filling factor of ~ 0.4 . It is detected by HI 21 cm emission/absorption and in optical and UV absorption lines.

$$n \approx 10^5 \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$T \approx 5000 \text{ K}$$

4. *Cool HI*

This atomic gas, also known as the cold neutral medium (CNM) has densities of $\sim 3 \cdot 10^7 \text{ m}^{-3}$, a temperature of $\sim 100 \text{ K}$ and a small volume filling factor of ~ 0.01 . It is observed, as the warm HI, by HI 21 cm emission/absorption and in optical and UV absorption lines.

$$n \approx 10^7 \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$T \approx 100 \text{ K}$$

5. *Diffuse molecular gas*

This gas is dense enough ($n \approx 10^8 \text{ m}^{-3}$) for molecular hydrogen to form because of H_2 self-shielding. It has a temperature of $\sim 50 \text{ K}$ and a volume filling factor of $\sim 10^{-3}$ and is observed by HI 21 cm emission/absorption, CO 2.6 mm emission and in optical and UV absorption lines.

$$n \approx 10^8 \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$T \approx 50 \text{ K}$$

6. *Dense molecular gas*

Dense H_2 is found in gravitationally bound clouds (see §3 for more details) with densities in the range of $10^9 - 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-3}$, temperatures of $10 - 50 \text{ K}$ and a volume filling factor of 10^{-4} . It is usually detected by CO 2.6 mm emission (see §3.2 for H_2 detection methods).

$$n = 10^9 - 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$T = 10 - 50 \text{ K}$$

7. *Stellar outflow*

Evolved cool stars have important mass loss due to outflow, especially in the asymptotic giant branch (AGB). The gas has densities of $10^6 - 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-3}$, temperatures of $50 - 1000 \text{ K}$ (however, cometary knots within stellar outflow can have lower temperatures, see §3) and almost no filling factor. It is observed by a combination of the above mentioned emission lines and continuums.

$$n = 10^6 - 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-3}$$

$$T = 50 - 1000 \text{ K}$$

Of these 7 phases, the molecular gas phases are of interest for this work. The next chapter thus introduces molecular clouds and the related cometary globules in more details. It has to be noted that the above phases are useful to

characterize the interstellar medium, but in reality it cannot simply be split in some phases, as all in-between phases exist as well.

2.2 TURBULENCES

Energy injection

Self-gravity:
Importance \sim mass
Star formation

The interstellar medium is not smooth but very turbulent, with subsonic shocks constantly injecting energy. Elmegreen & Scalo (2004) provide a review on observations, theory and simulations of interstellar turbulences. The energy injecting shocks are due to many different circumstances, such as stellar explosions (supernovae and novae), stellar winds, disturbances and shear instabilities in spiral density waves, expanding HII regions, superbubbles and cosmic ray streams. Numerical estimates indicate that stellar explosions are the most important ones (Mac Low & Klessen 2004), but other energy sources are important as well (Biferale et al. 2004). The effect of self-gravity makes interstellar turbulence more complicated than turbulence on Earth. The importance of self-gravity increases with the cloud mass and dominates for masses $\gtrsim 10^4$. However, self-gravity is again important at much lower masses, especially in star forming molecular cloud clumps (see Table 3.2). The important question is whether the clouds, clumps or cores are gravitationally bound or not (Ossenkopf et al. 2001).

Simulations:
Fast star formation
Low SFR

Rather idealized
Restricted resolution

Computer simulations improved the understanding of interstellar turbulence a lot, and reproduced many observations and scaling relations. They show that supersonic turbulence decays quickly and magnetic fields cannot counter gravity (Ostriker et al. 2001), suggesting a fast star formation (see also §3.3 and §3.7). The simulations predict a density probability function, showing that only a small fraction of gas is dense enough to collapse gravitationally (Vázquez-Semadeni & García 2001), giving an explanation to the low star formation rate. However, the simulations are still rather idealized, not including realistic cooling, ionization, chemistry, radiative transfers, and often omitting self-gravity, and have a restricted resolution ~ 0.05 pc (Renaud et al. 2013). Future simulations still face many challenges, such as reproducing the stellar initial mass function, the binary star system fraction or the star-formation inefficiency.

MOLECULAR CLOUDS

Molecular clouds are the densest regions of the interstellar medium. They consist of 3/4 H₂, 1/4 He (see Table 2.1) and traces of more complex molecules as well as dust grains. They are usually detected by CO emission (see Fig. 2.3). Even though they contain up to 50% of the gas mass in galaxies (or even higher, see §3.6 and §4.4.2), they occupy only a small fraction $\leq 1\%$ of the volume. Molecular clouds can be split into different types, as summarized in Table 3.1. The main interest of this work lies in clouds with a temperature ≤ 15 K where a H₂ phase transition is possible during compression. Giant molecular clouds (GMCs) contain massive stars which heat up the surrounding environment to > 20 K and no H₂ condensation is to be expected, therefore the following sections concentrate on the cooler dark clouds. In addition to the traditional molecular clouds, the cometary knots will be discussed in §3.4, as their physical properties, despite being much smaller, is very similar.

Phase transition:
Possible in dark
clouds

Table 3.1.: Types of isolated^a molecular clouds.

<i>Type</i>	<i>Mass</i> [M_{\odot}]	<i>Size</i> [pc]	<i>Density</i> [m^{-3}]	<i>Temperature</i> [K]
Giant Molecular Clouds	$10^4 - 10^6$	10 – 100	$10^9 - 10^{10}$	20 – 100
Dark Clouds	$10^3 - 10^4$	2 – 15	$10^8 - 10^{10}$	~ 10
Bok Globules	10 – 100	≤ 1	10^9	~ 10
Cometary Knots ^b	$\sim 10^{-5}$	$\sim 10^{-4}$	$\sim 10^{10}$ ^c	~ 10

Notes: The exact values vary in the literature and have to be taken ± 1 order of magnitude. Values assembled from Clemens et al. (1991); Bergin & Tafalla (2007); McKee & Ostriker (2007); Draine (2011).

(^a) Not part of a larger cloud, but may be part of molecular cloud complexes.

(^b) Usually not considered a molecular cloud, but similar properties.

(^c) Approximated using mass and size.

3.1 PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF MOLECULAR HYDROGEN AND HELIUM

The individual condensation properties of H₂ and He in molecular cloud conditions are relevant in the industry and therefore well documented from laboratory data (e.g. Air Liquide 1976; Linstrom & Mallard 2005). The H₂ and He phase diagrams of Fig. 3.1 show the domain of pressure conventionally attributed to molecular clouds and temperatures below the critical point of H₂ (32.9 K). The H₂ critical and triple points are indicated as well as the H₂ liquid phase. Figure 3.2 shows the same data, this time including density as a third dimension but omitting the liquid form of H₂. H₂ and He are in a phase

Laboratory H₂ and
He phase diagrams

Figure 3.1.: H_2 (bold line) and He (dotted line) phase diagrams in cold and low pressure conditions.

Figure 3.2.: 3D H_2 (blue) and He (red) phase diagrams. For clarity, only a part of the upper, almost constant density condensed phases of both species, as well as the low density gas phase of He, are shown.

transition when on their respective condensation wall, linking the gaseous and solid/liquid phase.

From a chemical point of view, both H₂ and He present an outer electronic shell made of two electrons, however their chemical properties differ markedly. This is even more striking when comparing the hydrogen isotope deuterium D₂, which has the same mass as He, but is much more similar to H₂ (see Fig. 3.5). The differences are mainly because of quantum physics. He has a lower critical temperature than H₂ (5.2 K vs. 32.9 K) and a lower critical pressure (0.227 MPa vs. 1.286 MPa). He becomes a superfluid below 2.17 K, but does not have a triple point, since (super-)liquid He does not become solid at any temperature without additional pressure. Solid He is only possible at pressures ≥ 2.5 MPa and may be in supersolid form (Kim & Chan 2004). As the conditions of He superfluids and supersolids are very different from molecular cloud conditions, this interesting topic is not further discussed.

Quantum effects:
He *different from* H₂
and D₂

3.1.1 *Hydrogen Helium mixture*

The properties of H₂-He mixtures has been studied for industrial purposes mostly at high densities, for example for rocket fuels (Richardson 2015). In the astrophysical context, they were studied in details for temperatures above the critical point and at high densities (e.g. Streett 1973; Koci et al. 2007; Becker et al. 2014), and especially in conditions similar to giant gas planets (e.g. Vorberger et al. 2007; Saumon et al. 1995). However, the properties of H₂-He mixtures at low temperature remain largely untested in laboratory and only few theoretical studies haven been done so far. One example is the study by Safa & Pfenniger (2008), who calculate the thermodynamic properties of H₂-He mixtures below critical temperature based on the known intermolecular potentials. By taking into account quantum effects they obtain the critical point and stability of the mixture itself.

Usual interest in
mixtures:

Rocket fuel
Gas planets

When considering either H₂ or He at low pressure which gradually increases, as during a contraction, a H₂ phase transition would appear well before a He one. The conditions of phase transition of the mixture H₂-He may however differ from the conditions of each element when taken separately. In this work, the properties of H₂-He mixtures, with an emphasis on H₂ phase transition conditions, are investigated analytically (Part ii) and using computer simulations (Part iii).

3.2 DETECTION

Even though H₂ is the most abundant molecule in the Universe, it is very difficult to detect. This is due to the fact that it does not possess a permanent dipole moment and therefore does not radiate dipolar transitions. It does have a quadrupole transition, but emission starts only at temperature ≥ 512 K. It is possible to directly detect molecular clouds due to dust emission and extinction, but this is limited to nearby clouds and is only possible if there are

H₂ *almost invisible*

background stars. Both methods are mainly used to measure the CO-to-H₂ conversion factor.

3.2.1 CO emission

$T > 5 \text{ K}$: 2.6 mm

Molecular clouds do not consist uniquely of H₂ and He (which pose the same observability challenges), but also contain heavier elements, mostly C and O. In molecular condition, they combine to CO, which has a dipole moment. The rotational transition $J = 1 \rightarrow 0$ can be observed at 2.6 mm and happens already at 5.53 K which makes CO a good tracer even for cold molecular clouds. The usually deployed relationship between the CO emission and the molecular gas mass is the CO-to-H₂ conversion factor X_{CO} :

$$N(\text{H}_2) = X_{\text{CO}} W(\text{CO} : J = 1 \rightarrow 0), \quad (3.1)$$

where CO consists of the ¹²C and ⁶O isotopes.

Uncertainty $\geq 30\%$

Bolatto et al. (2013) provide a review on the determination of the CO-to-H₂ conversion factor, using both observations and simulations. They propose a constant value of $X_{\text{CO}} = 2 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2} (\text{K km s}^{-1})^{-1} \pm$ a factor 0.3 in the inner disk ($1 \text{ kpc} \lesssim R \lesssim 9 \text{ kpc}$) and a lower value of $X_{\text{CO}} = 0.5 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2} (\text{K km s}^{-1})^{-1} \pm$ a factor 2 in the centre ($R \lesssim 500 \text{ pc}$). This being said, the uncertainty is still rather high, especially in the centre. They discuss in detail the X_{CO} dependence on metallicity based on observation, although the simple fact that a low metallicity means a lower fraction of CO should imply that CO emissions in low-metallicity regions imply more H₂ mass.

3.2.2 Other H₂ detection methods

CO problems:
Freeze out
Low metallicity

The CO-to-H₂ conversion factor is a useful tool to detect molecular clouds, granted its temperature is high enough for CO not to freeze out (see §3.5). The critical and triple temperature of CO are 140.3 and 68.2 K respectively (see Fig. 3.5) and a strong, “catastrophic” freeze out can be expected at conditions with a temperature $\leq 20 \text{ K}$ and densities $\geq 10^{10} \text{ m}^{-3}$. An additional problem with CO-emission is the necessity of a high metallicity. Gas which has barely been enriched by stellar nucleosynthesis elements, (e.g. in the outer galactic disk), should essentially consist of the initial abundances (see §4.3), without high C or O abundances.

There are other methods to detect H₂ other than CO emission at low temperatures in the outer disk, as proposed by Combes & Pfenniger (1996, 1997):

- *Ultrafine structure*

0.55 km, 5.5 km

The ortho-H₂ has three levels of hyperfine splitting, $F = 0, 1$ and 2 , due to interaction of nuclear spin with magnetic dipole. There are two transitions, $F = 1 \rightarrow 0$ at 0.55 km and $F = 2 \rightarrow 1$ at 5.5 km which correspond to frequencies of 546.39 kHz and 54.85 kHz. As this structure is several orders of magnitude below hyperfine structures, it

is also called ultrafine structure. This cannot be observed on earth, as the ionosphere is filtering all frequencies $\lesssim 100$ MHz. In addition, the interstellar plasma scatters the waves so that high angular resolution of point sources is impossible and the galactic disk could be mapped. The best option to observe the ultrafine structure would be using a grid of cables on the surface of the Moon, but that is a project for the future.

*Only space
observation possible*

- *HD and LiH transitions*

Molecular hydrogen consisting of the isotopes protium (H) and deuterium (D), HD, has a weak electric dipole and can be observed at $112\ \mu\text{m}$ if above 130 K. This is thus only possible in heated regions, and the HD/H₂ abundance is very low $\sim 10^{-5}$. The LiH molecule can be observed at 0.67 mm above 21 K, but only from space. However, the LiH molecule is even more sparse (LiH/H₂ $\approx 10^{-10}$) and the temperature ≥ 20 K severely limits this method.

$T > 130$ K: $112\ \mu\text{m}$
 $T > 21$ K: $0.67\ \text{mm}$

- *H₂⁺ hyperfine transition*

The H₂⁺ has a very low abundance of $\leq 10^{-10}$, but it could be observed in the hyperfine structure. The strongest transition can be observed at 22.32 cm (corresponding to 1343 MHz) which happens at ≥ 110 K. Again, as with the HD transition, the high temperature limits the use of this method to observe very cold H₂ regions.

$T > 110$ K: $22\ \text{cm}$

- *UV H₂ absorption in front of quasars*

When observing gas with temperatures similar to the CMB, seeing any emission line is very difficult and absorption should be the preferred method. Absorption in the infrared is very weak, but electronic lines in the UV should be perceivable in absorption. H₂ has already been detected in absorption in front of quasars (e.g. Foltz et al. 1988; Ge & Bechtold 1997) at redshift $z \approx 2$, but to date no instrument is able to observe such absorption at $z = 0$. If a high density H₂ region, such as a clumpuscule (see §4.4.2) is in front of a quasar, it would mask parts of a quasar. If the clumpuscule is part of our galaxy, temporal variations are expected to happen with timescales of months.

Variation in months

- *Submillimeter continuum*

Observations in the submillimeter band show an additional cold component with $T = 4 - 7$ K (Reach et al. 1994). If the cold component is interpreted as dust, it would imply very dense clumps of gas. This cold component can also be explained by emission of small H₂ aggregates such as dimers. Those would have a continuum radiation for the free-bound and free-free transitions. As is shown by simulations in this work (see §11 and §12), multimers can form at temperatures close to the CMB.

*Cold dust or
H₂ dimers*

- *γ -ray distribution*

Diffuse γ -rays created from interaction of cosmic particles and nucleons in the ISM trace radially extended gas.

*Cosmic rays + ISM
→ γ -ray*

The last 2 methods have been successfully used to detect dark gas (see §3.6), whereas the implementation of the other methods still pose either technical problems or are not able to trace very cold gas.

3.3 DARK CLOUDS

$T \leq 15$ K
Filament structure

Dark clouds are somewhat smaller than giant molecular clouds, but the main distinction is the absence of massive stars and the consequent lower temperatures (Bergin & Tafalla 2007). Dark clouds have a temperature ≤ 15 K, the “magical temperature” below which plane-parallel collapses lead to the formation of solid H_2 (see §6). Dark clouds have irregular structures and contain several filaments. The presence of filaments suggests that dark clouds are born in a filamentary structure (e.g. Hartmann 2002). As the creation of filaments is usually preceded by sheet-like collapses (see §6), which are hard to detect face-on and look like filaments edge-on, a pancake-filament-point collapse of the interstellar medium can be expected during the formation of dark clouds.

Quasistatic view:
Virial equilibrium
Slow star formation

There is a still ongoing debate whether molecular clouds are quasistatic or highly dynamic. The quasistatic view supposes the clouds to be close to a virial equilibrium with several substructures, whereby the gravitational forces are balanced by a strong magnetic field. Star formation would take several cloud dynamical times. This view is backed by long live-time estimates of $\geq 10^7$ yrs (e.g. Mouschovias et al. 2006), the inefficiency of star formation (see §3.7) and the belief that clouds are believed to be gravitationally bound (e.g. Larson 1981). Lately, the quasistatic view has largely been discarded due to new observations and especially simulations of interstellar turbulences which show that magnetic fields cannot withstand gravity (see also §2.2).

Gravoturbulent view:
No equilibrium
Fast star formation

The newer dynamic view, also referred to as gravoturbulent fragmentation (e.g. Mac Low & Klessen 2004) suggests that clouds form, evolve and dissipate rapidly without reaching equilibrium, that molecular clouds have a low lifetime of $3\text{--}5 \cdot 10^6$ yrs and that stars form quickly within a dynamic cloud time. This view holds that magnetic fields, which are very difficult to measure, as well as the lifetime of molecular clouds may have been overestimated (Nakano 1998; Bergin et al. 2004). The low star formation rate is explained by a small fraction of gas mass dense enough for being gravitationally unstable (Elmegreen & Scalo 2004).

Fractal structure:
 $D \geq 2$

Observations show that dark clouds do not have a smooth density but have a hierarchical, self-similar, fractal structure. The exact value of the fractal dimension is still debated, but believed to be ≥ 2 (2.3 ± 0.3 in Elmegreen & Falgarone (1996) and 2.6 ± 0.1 in Sánchez et al. (2005)). Dark clouds consist of denser clumps, which again consist of dense cores (see Table 3.2). These cores are the smallest cloud-structure, where a single or binary star system can form. Young stellar objects haven been observed in some of them, and cores usually have been classified as being either starless or star-containing. However, this distinction depends very much on the detection possibility of an embedded young stellar object. Many starless cores might in fact contain

young stellar objects (Young et al. 2004). Bok globules (see Fig. 3.3) are not part of a dark cloud, but have otherwise similar properties as dark cloud cores. H_2 phase transition can be expected in cores or Bok globules.

Table 3.2.: Dark cloud substructure.

Type	Mass [M_\odot]	Size [pc]	Density [m^{-3}]	Temperature [K]
Dark Clouds	$10^3 - 10^4$	2 – 15	$10^8 - 10^{10}$	~ 10
Clumps	50 – 500	0.3 – 3	$10^9 - 10^{10}$	10 – 20
Cores	0.5 – 5	0.03 – 0.2	$10^{10} - 10^{12}$	8 – 12

Notes: Values from Bergin & Tafalla (2007).

3.4 COMETARY KNOTS

Cometary knots, as observed in the Helix nebulae (see Fig. 3.4), are usually not considered molecular clouds as they are too small to form stars: Their size is estimated to ≤ 200 AU and their mass to $\sim 10^{-5} M_\odot$ (Walsh & Meaburn 1993; O'dell & Handron 1996). Nonetheless, they have a lot in common with molecular clouds and especially dark cloud cores, given their physical resemblance. Thanks to their proximity (the helix nebula is at a distance of only ~ 215 pc), many details can be observed. An important fact is that the column density is increasing inwards, as long as the knot is optically thin or up to the limit of the optical resolution (Burkert & O'dell 1998). If this trend extends to the centre, one can expect high densities and low temperatures ~ 10 K in the central parts of the cometary knots. Even though star formation or Jeans collapses will not happen due to the absence of sufficient mass, contractions due to turbulence can still happen, leading to H_2 phase transition regions.

$$R \leq 200 \text{ AU}$$

$$M \approx 10^{-5} M_\odot$$

$$T \approx 10 \text{ K}$$

3.5 INTERSTELLAR ICE

The interstellar medium and especially molecular clouds not only consist of gas, but also contain ice. This is not surprising, as the critical and triple points of more complex molecules are at least half an order of magnitude higher than H_2 , as can be seen in Fig. 3.5. Boogert et al. (2015) provide an up to date review on the evolution model of ice formation and their observation.

$$\text{Complex molecules:}$$

$$T_c \gtrsim 100 \text{ K}$$

Interstellar ice forms on dust grains due to freeze out. This is in contrast to the proposed H_2 ice formation of this work, where H_2 ice grains form because of a phase transition. However, ice grains or heavier molecules may function as catalysts and speed up the grain formation (see §15). It is important to note that complex molecules, which do not easily form in their gaseous phase, are created during the freeze out process. First, at relatively high temperature and low density, polar ices, having high dipole moments and hence high critical

Freeze out

Figure 3.3.: Thackeray's Globules in the Running Chicken Nebula (IC 2944).
Credit: Astronomy Picture of the Day; Hubble Heritage Team, NASA.

Figure 3.4.: Cometary knots in the Helix nebula.
Credit: Astronomy Picture of the Day; C. R. O'Dell and K. Handron (Rice University), NASA.

Figure 3.5.: Critical points (•) and triple points (γ) of common molecules in the ISM. The sublimation curves cross interstellar pressure conditions very steeply in pressure a few K below their triple point.

temperatures, form. Then, at lower temperature and higher densities, a lot of CO is accreted, leading to the formation of CO₂. At even higher densities, there is a “catastrophic” CO freeze out, leading to the formation of complex molecules such as CH₃OH and H₂CO. Once the temperature increases to ≥ 20 K CO is sublimated, leading to the distillation of pure CO₂. More complex molecules are segregated at temperature ≥ 30 K. If the ice grains are subject to UV radiation and/or cosmic rays, complex molecules such as salts or organics could form.

Ice vibration wavelengths are well known from laboratory data. Interstellar ices are mostly detected by molecular vibrations in the near to far infrared from 3 – 16 μm . The signal below 3 μm is very weak, whereas intermolecular lattice vibrations could be detected in the far infrared ≥ 40 μm , but no instrumentation exists to date. H₂O could also be observed in the UV, but is unobserved due to UV extinction. The ices are transparent outside their vibrational modes, while the continuum opacity is increased by the presence of interstellar ice.

The most abundant ice is H₂O followed by CO, CO₂, NH₃, CH₃OH and CH₄. The ices are not pure but “dirty”, consisting of many different molecules. H₂O based ices occur in dense clouds with $n \geq 10^9 \text{ m}^{-3}$ and $T \leq 90$ K. They are mostly mixed with CO₂, NH₃ and CH₄. In even denser clouds CO-based ices are observed which are rich in CH₃OH and CO₂. The CO₂/H₂O ratio which is different in other galaxies compared to the Milky Way, is suspected to be different due to metallicity difference. H₂ ice has been detected in the absorption band at 2.417 μm (Sandford & Allamandola

Molecular vibrations:
3 – 16 μm

Most abundant:
H₂O and CO

H₂ ice mixed in H₂O

1993; Buch & Devlin 1994; Dissly et al. 1994). The interpretation of this detection is that H₂ is mixed within H₂O-rich grains in conditions that are too warm to allow the bulk of H₂ to condense (Kristensen et al. 2011). However this does not exclude the presence of H₂ ice, even at high abundances, as H₂ ice is even more difficult to detect than H₂ gas (see §3.2.2).

3.6 DARK GAS

No CO emission

Observed in:
 γ -ray
 Far infrared
 CII emission

Far-infrared emission excess in respect to the CO-induced molecular gas gave rise to first speculations that there may be more molecular gas than usually assumed. The results of Reach et al. (1994) suggest the presence of molecular gas even in regions without CO-emission. Using diffuse γ -ray emission from the interstellar medium, Grenier et al. (2005) determined the presence of an additional massive dark gas, undetected by CO emission. The far-infrared map of the Spitzer Survey shows that dark gas also exists in the Small (Leroy et al. 2007) and Large (Bernard et al. 2008) Magellanic clouds. This discovery was followed by CII emission detections without corresponding CO detections, best explained by the presence of warm H₂ dark gas (Langer et al. 2010). Planck Collaboration et al. (2011) deduce the mass of the dark gas as being 118% of the CO emitting molecular gas which was confirmed by Paradis et al. (2012).

*H₂ mass in MW:
 CO emission $\times 2$*

Dark baryons

The detection of dark gas in the Milky Way and the Magellanic clouds more than doubles the CO-predicted mass of H₂ in our Galaxy. Adding the 118% of H₂ mass to Table 2.1, we would find a total mass for H₂ of $1.83 \cdot 10^9 M_{\oplus}$ corresponding to a fraction of 0.31 instead of 0.17, bypassing the HI mass. Warm dark gas is not really “dark”, as it is easily detected by CII emission, whereas cold dark gas is more difficult to detect. The dark gas mass estimated by the Plank collaboration has to be seen as a lower limit, as even more mass in form of H₂ can be expected in the outer galactic disk. The detection of dark gas is important, as there is still a large fraction of missing baryons in our galaxy (see next chapter) and dark molecular gas is one of the most promising candidates for the dark baryons (see §4.4.2).

3.7 STAR FORMATION

The informations on star formation has been vastly improved over the last decade thanks to several space telescopes (i.e., Spitzer, Herschel and Hubble). Kennicutt & Evans (2012) provide an up to date review on the observations in the Milky Way and nearby galaxies and McKee & Ostriker (2007) one on the actual state of star formation theory.

Stars form due to the gravitational collapse of cores of molecular clouds. The collapse of self-gravitating gas has been studied for over a century. The molecular cloud is usually considered being a one-component ideal gas and is governed by the balance between gravity and gas pressure. The gravity of this fluid is directly proportional to its density and the pressure proportional to the adiabatic density derivative of the pressure $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_s$. It has been shown

by Jeans (1902) that if a perturbation with a long enough wavelength is introduced into the system, this perturbation will grow exponentially. With growing perturbation, the pressure of the fluid will not be able to withstand its gravity anymore which will ultimately lead to gravitational collapse. The gravitational stability of multi-component fluids is more complex and has been studied mostly on cosmic scales considering an additional dark matter component (e.g. Grishchuk & Zeldovich 1981; Jog & Solomon 1984b; Volkov & Ortega 2000). Different collapsing geometries are studied in §6 and the gravitational stability of one- and multi-component fluids in §7.

Gravitational Jeans collapse

Figure 3.6.: Stellar initial mass function, normalized so that the integral of each curve is equal to 1. Black: Salpeter (1955), red: Kroupa (2001), blue: Chabrier (2003).

Star counts allow to establish an initial stellar mass function (IMF). The first one was proposed by Salpeter (1955) which follows a simple power law, whereas newer estimates done by Kroupa (2001) and Chabrier (2003) replace the power law for low-mass stars. Figure 3.6 shows the three initial mass functions. The mass fraction of the high-mass and low-mass stars is difficult to estimate because heavy stars are so rare, and light stars are difficult to detect. There is no obvious reason why the initial mass function should be universal. However, in the Milky Way there is solid agreement from region to region.

A big mystery of star formation remains its inefficiency. In the Milky Way, considering a mean density of $n_{\text{H}} \approx 5 \cdot 10^7 \text{ m}^{-3}$ and a free-fall time of $\tau_{\text{ff}} = \sqrt{3\pi/32G\rho}$, the highest star formation rate can be estimated to $200 M_{\odot}\text{yrs}^{-1}$. However, observations show that it lies in the range of $0.9 - 2.2 M_{\odot}\text{yrs}^{-1}$, at least 2 orders of magnitude below estimations (Draine 2011). Many explanations have been proposed, including the quasistatic model of molecular cloud dynamics (see §3.3), transport of angular momentum or feedback-effects. The star formation rate likely depends on density and Schmidt (1959) proposed a law to calculate the rate as a function of density. As the density is difficult to calculate, Kennicutt (1998) proposes a different law, calculating

Star formation: Inefficient

the star formation rate per disk area as a function of the gas surface density. This law is usually called the Schmidt-Kennicutt Law:

$$\Sigma_{\text{SFR}} = (2.5 \pm 0.7) \cdot 10^{-4} \left(\frac{\Sigma_{\text{gas}}}{M_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-2}} \right)^{1.4 \pm 0.15} M_{\odot} \text{kpc}^{-2} \text{yrs}^{-1} \quad (3.2)$$

During the first step of star formation, the collapse is plane-parallel and a H_2 phase transition can be reached, leading to the formation of solid H_2 . The presence of these ice clumps could be an additional reason for the star formation inefficiency.

DARK BARYONS

Ever since dynamical calculations of astronomical objects are made, distinct differences are found between the observed and calculated orbits, revealing missing mass. In the beginning, the missing mass was often found afterwards, as in the case of the discovery of Neptune. Once it even helped to find a more general theory on gravity by Einstein, as was the case with the orbit of Mercury. However, since the discovery of more than a factor 100 of missing mass in galaxy clusters by Zwicky (1933, 1937), the evidence for a large amount of missing invisible matter, usually called dark matter, was accumulating. In the beginning, the general understanding was that dark matter was baryonic, but soon the common assumption was that dark matter is non-baryonic, mainly due to Big Bang nucleosynthesis constraints, and more exotic candidates were investigated. Nevertheless, as there is still a missing factor of at least 2 of baryonic matter, at least a fraction of the dark matter has to be baryonic.

The name “baryonic dark matter” is somewhat unfortunate, as it seems to indicate that there is something special about it. In principle it is normal baryonic matter, which just happens to be undetected. For that reason, the expression dark baryons is preferred.

Dark matter:
Mostly
non-baryonic,
small baryonic
fraction

Dark baryons:
Undetected baryonic
matter

4.1 DYNAMIC EVIDENCE FOR MISSING MATTER

There is a lot of different observational evidence for dark matter, some of which is presented in this section. This is not meant to be a complete inventory of all dark matter evidence, but should reflect that mass is missing everywhere, at galactic, intergalactic and cosmic scales. For an exhaustive overview of all the evidence of dark matter see Roos (2010). The evidence for missing baryonic matter is discussed in the next section.

Missing matter at
every scale

- *Flat galactic rotation curves*
The rotation speed in spiral galaxies, after rising from the centre, remains approximately constant afterwards. Such a rotation curve is expected if the mass is increasing proportionally to the radius, which is in contradiction with the observed visible mass. The missing mass is explained by dark matter. The rotation curve remains flat in HI regions outside the optical galaxy (e.g. Rogstad & Shostak 1972; Roberts & Rots 1973; Rubin et al. 1980). Therefore, the need for dark matter to explain the rotation curves goes well beyond the optical disk.
- *Elliptic galaxy velocity dispersion*
The mass to light ratios of velocity dispersion in elliptic galaxies indicate a high fraction of missing mass (e.g. Faber & Jackson 1976),

but the velocity dispersion does not allow to uniquely determine the density profile. X-ray observations of hot gas on the other hand indicate that the mass is increasing proportionally with radius (e.g. Forman et al. 1985; Sarazin 1986), as in spiral galaxies.

- *Velocity dispersion in Clusters*

The detection of too high galaxy velocities is usually viewed as the first clear evidence of dark matter (Zwicky 1933). The dynamical mass exceeds the visible mass by a factor of up to 100. More recently, X-ray observations of hot gas confirmed this independently (e.g. Vikhlinin et al. 2006).

- *Large-scale structure of Universe*

The formation of the large-scale structure of the universe needs more mass than observed. This can be predicted in theory (e.g. Zel'dovich 1970; Zeldovich 1972) and has been confirmed by simulations (e.g. Springel et al. 2005).

4.2 BARYONS

Baryons are composite subatomic particles consisting of three quarks (Olive & Particle Data Group 2014). They belong, together with mesons (which consist of one quark and one anti-quark) to the hadrons. Quarks have a charge of either $+2/3 e$ or $-1/3 e$, and the baryonic charge depends on the quark composition. The two most abundant and relevant baryons are the proton and the neutron, which consist of up (u) and down (d) quarks which have charges of $+2/3 e$ and $-1/3 e$ respectively. Protons consist of two up and one down quark (uud), which leads to a charge of $+1 e$, whereas neutrons consist of one up and two down quarks (udd) and is without charge. Quarks have a spin of $J = 1/2$, and depending whether two quarks are aligned or not, two spins add up to 1 or 0, leading to baryonic spins of either $J = 1/2$ or $J = 3/2$. Figure 4.1 shows the possible baryons with $J = 1/2$ using up, down, strange and bottom quarks. Both protons and neutrons are part of this list.

Baryon:
3 quarks

Proton: uud
Neutron: udd

4.3 BIG BANG NUCLEOSYNTHESIS

The abundance of the elements created by the Big Bang nucleosynthesis, ^2H , ^3He , ^4He and ^7Li is a function of the baryon to photon ratio, which is directly proportional to the baryon density Ω_b . Measuring the primordial abundance can be done either by observing objects in whom little stellar nucleosynthesis has to be expected (e.g. dwarf galaxies) or which are far away and thus in an early stage of their evolution (e.g. distant quasars). An alternative way is to measure the baryon to photon ratio through observations of the cosmic microwave background radiation and anisotropies. See Iocco et al. (2009) for a review on the Big Bang nucleosynthesis and the determination of the abundance.

Baryon density:
Dependent on
abundance of lightest
elements

**Baryons with Up, Down, Strange
and Bottom Quarks and Spin J=1/2**

Figure 4.1.: Credit: Fermilab.

Figure 4.2.: The relative amounts of the different constituents of the Universe.
Credit: ESA/Planck Collaboration.

The Planck measurements were able to determine the different densities at high precision (see Fig. 4.2): $\Omega_b h^2 = 0.02230 \pm 0.00014$, $\Omega_m h^2 = 0.14170 \pm 0.00097$ (Planck Collaboration et al. 2015). The baryonic mass fraction is thus ~ 0.157 . The observed baryonic mass is in good accordance with Ω_b at redshifts $z \geq 3$, but below, there is a *first missing baryons problem* (e.g. Peric & Salucci 1992; Cen & Fang 2006). The sum of the observed baryonic matter is estimated to be composed of $\sim 6\%$ stars in galaxies, $\sim 1.7\%$ cold gas in galaxies, $\sim 4\%$ gas in galaxy clusters and $\sim 30\%$ neutral cool-warm intergalactic medium (Fukugita & Peebles 2004). According to this estimates, 58.3% of baryons are still missing.

1st problem:
*Missing baryons in
the universe*

The *second missing baryons problem* is in galaxies. The observed baryons in galaxies such as the Milky Way do not sum up to the expected amount according to the Big Bang nucleosynthesis and large-scale structure formation (e.g. Flynn et al. 2006; McGaugh 2008). As will be discussed in the next section, the missing baryons in galaxies cannot be explained by the same candidates as the missing baryons in the universe.

2nd problem:
*Missing baryons in
galaxies*

It is an interesting coincidence that baryons are missing starting at redshifts where the background temperature $T_z = T_{\text{CMB}}(1+z)$ is below the maximum temperature for which a plane-parallel collapse can lead to H_2 condensations. Initial temperatures below $T_{z=3} = 10.8$ K would easily allow H_2 to be in a phase transition during sheet-like contraction.

$z \lesssim 3$:
*possible phase
transition in IGM*

4.4 DARK BARYONS CANDIDATES

In this section, different dark baryon candidates are presented in the order of increasing mass, summarized in Table 4.1. The most promising candidate for the missing baryons in the universe is warm-hot intergalactic medium. However, this medium cannot explain the missing baryons in galaxies, which is why different candidates are needed on the galactic scale. The main focus in the present work is on gaseous H_2 and small up to planetoid-sized H_2 bodies as they are directly related to this thesis. The different non-baryonic dark matter candidates, be they cold, warm, or hot are a different topic altogether

Table 4.1.: Dark baryon candidates.

<i>Type</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Mass</i>
Gas/Plasma	Warm-hot IGM	1 u (= $1.7 \cdot 10^{-27}$ kg)
	Molecular hydrogen	2 u
Substellar bodies	Snowballs	$10^{-6} - 1$ kg
	Comets	$10^{12} - 10^{16}$ kg
	Planetoids	$\leq M_{\oplus}$
Massive compact halo object	Brown dwarfs	$\leq 0.08 M_{\odot}$
	Red dwarfs	$\sim 0.1 M_{\odot}$
	White dwarfs	$\leq M_{\odot}$
	Neutron star	$\sim 2 M_{\odot}$
	Stellar black holes	$\sim 10 M_{\odot}$
	Very massive black holes	$10^2 - 10^5 M_{\odot}$
	Supermassive black holes	$\geq 10^5 M_{\odot}$

and will not be discussed here, see Feng (2010) and Porter et al. (2011) for reviews on non-baryonic dark matter candidates with an emphasis on weakly interacting massive particles (WIMP) and detection methods.

4.4.1 Warm-hot intergalactic medium

Figure 4.3.: Compilation of current observational measurements of the low-redshift baryon census.

Credit: Shull et al. (2012).

The most explored candidate for dark baryons is the warm-hot intergalactic medium (WHIM) (see Bregman (2007) for a review on the topic). This hot

plasma is predicted by simulations to be distributed as filaments between galaxies with an overdensity of $\rho/\langle\rho\rangle - 1 = 7 - 200$ (e.g. Davé et al. 2001). Recent X-ray observations have indeed detected this medium (Fang et al. 2010). However, 30% of the baryons may still be missing (see Fig. 4.3), even though they may be in form of an even hotter intergalactic medium (Shull et al. 2012).

4.4.2 Dark H_2 disk

Figure 4.4.: Hubble sequence mass fraction.

Credit: D. Pfenniger, private communication.

The possibility of dark baryons in form of a cold, H_2 disk has first been proposed by Pfenniger et al. (1994). It is a compelling candidate as it would explain many different observational puzzles, such as:

- *Flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies beyond optical disk*
The flat rotation curves of the HI outer disk of spiral galaxies (see §4.1) could be explained by an accompanying dark gas disk.
- *Constant dark matter to HI ratio in outer spiral galaxies*
Bosma (e.g. 1981) shows that the ratio of dark matter and HI remains constant in the outer disk. This fact may imply that dark matter is not only proportional to HI radially, but also vertically and thus in form of a rotating disk.
- *Excess of H_2 in interacting galaxies*
Braine & Combes (1992, 1993) show that the observed total amount of H_2 in interacting galaxies is higher than the one of isolated galaxies, especially in the centre. This can be explained by the fact that H_2 gas

from the outer disk is falling towards the centre due to strong gravitational torques (Bournaud et al. 2007).

- *Transformation of dark matter into stars*

If we assume that disk galaxies evolve along the Hubble sequence Im-Sm-Sd-...-Sa-S0 (Pfenniger 1996), there is a decrease of dark matter and an increase of star mass along the sequence (see Fig. 4.4 right). Some of the gas needed for the stellar formation might be explained by gas infall, as the total mass of galaxies also evolves along the sequence (see Fig. 4.4 left). However the baryonic to non-baryonic matter ratio was constant, this would not explain why the dark matter fraction is decreasing. A different explanation would be that the dark matter is directly transformed into stars, which would imply that it was baryonic.

The proposed dark gas disk would be in a fractal structure, where the smallest structures, called clumpuscles, would have a size of 30 AU and a mass of $10^{-3} M_{\odot}$ (Pfenniger & Combes 1994). The fractal structure would allow up to a factor 10 more mass compared to a smooth model for the same column densities and be massive enough to amount for a large fraction of the missing baryons. At a temperature similar to the CMB and with a low metallicity, it would be difficult to detect. Recent observations of dark gas (see §3.6) further strengthen the argument for this candidate. Frequent encounters between clumpuscle would prevent the formation of stars or Jupiters, but the formation of smaller bodies would still be possible (see next section). Pfenniger (2004) further discusses that cold solid cores help to stabilize cold gas globules.

Fractal structure

Galactic simulations including dark gas and a (non-baryonic) dark matter halo show that a multiphase model coupling the visible warm gas and the cold dark gas reproduces spiral galaxy properties (Revaz et al. 2009).

Multiphase coupling

4.4.3 *Substellar bodies*

Substellar bodies with masses below brown dwarfs have long been discarded as possible dark baryon candidates due to the fact that they were believed to vaporize at too small timescales (Hegyi & Olive 1986), and because of the lack of absorption observation in the case of small ice grains and direct observation of comet- and planetoid-sized bodies in the solar neighbourhood (Hills 1986). However, observational non-evidence for larger bodies only applies for objects which can survive close to the sun and there were serious flaws in the calculation of the sublimation timescales. White (1996) shows that H_2 bodies with a radius $\geq 10^4 - 10^5$ m can survive during $10^9 - 10^{10}$ years. Walker (2013) demonstrates that H_2 dust grains can survive indefinitely given the right conditions.

*Survival timescale:
Much longer than
commonly assumed*

Substellar H_2 bodies, from dust grains to planetoids, would not survive long enough near to stars, but could well hide a large part of the missing baryons if situated in cold dark clouds. The main challenge is explaining the

formation of these bodies in the first place. This thesis presents a study on precisely this topic, showing that H_2 condensation is very well possible in the interstellar medium during plane-parallel collapses if the initial temperature is ≤ 15 K (see §6).

Missing baryons:
 H_2 gas
 + H_2 bodies

The possibility of substellar bodies as dark baryons is closely linked with dark H_2 gas disks as discussed in the previous section and the missing dark baryons in galaxies could well be a combination of both. Dark gas is an ideal birthplace for substellar H_2 bodies. If H_2 bodies are forming in the densest regions of a dark gas disk, they could be much more massive and amount for most of the missing baryons in disk galaxies.

4.4.4 *Massive compact halo object*

In the 1990s, massive compact halo objects, with the somewhat unfortunate acronym MACHO, were viewed as a probable candidate for the missing baryons, or even for dark matter in general (e.g. Carr 1994). These objects, ranging from brown dwarfs up to supermassive black holes (see Table. 4.1), are hard to detect as they emit little or no radiation.

Microlensing:
 Not enough events

Detection for these objects was looked for using microlensing of the Large Magellanic Cloud. Brown dwarfs as well as black holes were quickly discarded (Alcock et al. 2000b, 2001), but the MACHO collaboration claimed to have found enough events for objects in the range of $0.15 - 0.9 M_\odot$ (Alcock et al. 2000a). However, Hubble space telescope searches do not account for such a high amount of red or white dwarfs which are in this mass range (Graff & Freese 1996). The EROS collaboration, which had a better sensitivity, did not confirm the MACHO collaboration results and neither did Tisserand et al. (2007). The present understanding is that the combined mass fraction of all massive halo objects is too small to account for either dark matter or the missing dark baryons.

Part II

PHYSICS

The following chapters present the relevant physics of the present work. §5 recalls the ideal gas and van der Waals equations of state. §6 discusses different collapse geometries and shows why the plane-parallel collapse is the most favorable. §7 develops the one- and two-component gravitational instability criteria and shows their particularities if a fluid is in a phase transition. §8 recalls the Lennard-Jones intermolecular potential, and develops the virial theorem including both gravity and the Lennard-Jones terms.

The chapters have been published, in slightly different form, in FP2015a for one-component fluids and in FP2015b for binary mixtures and multi-component fluids.

5

EQUATION OF STATE OF A FLUID

5.1 IDEAL GAS FLUID

Simple EOS used far
from condensed
phase

A fluid far from the condensed phase can be approximated with the ideal gas equation of state:

$$P = nk_B T, \quad (5.1)$$

with $n = \rho/m$ the number density, ρ the mass density, m the molecular mass and k_B the Boltzmann constant. Its adiabatic density derivative is:

$$\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}\right)_s = \gamma \frac{k_B T}{m}, \quad (5.2)$$

where the adiabatic index is $\gamma = 5/3$ in the case of a monoatomic gas. The ideal gas equation of state can only represent a fluid in gaseous form. In order to represent a condensed fluid or a fluid in a phase transition, a different, more complete equation of state is needed.

5.2 VAN DER WAALS FLUID

EOS able to describe
a phase transition

Figure 5.1.: van der Waals phase diagram for a fluid with $T_r = 0.9$. Cyan line: gas phase; blue line: phase transition; black line: solid phase; dashed line: Maxwell construct.

The van der Waals equation is a classical equation of state of a pure fluid presenting a first order phase transition. This equation of state describes the macroscopic behaviour of a fluid in which at microscopic level the molecules are strongly repulsive at short distances and beyond that weakly attractive over a limited range.

The van der Waals equation (van der Waals 1910; Johnston 2014) is a modification of the ideal-gas law, taking the finite size of molecules and intermolecular interactions into account. It links pressure, density, and temperature as follows:

$$P = \frac{k_B T n}{1 - bn} - an^2, \quad (5.3)$$

with a [Pa m^6] and b [m^3] being constants characteristic of the fluid. It can also be expressed in a reduced, dimensionless form as,

$$P_r = \frac{8T_r}{\frac{3}{n_r} - 1} - 3n_r^2, \quad (5.4)$$

where $P_r = P/P_c$, $n_r = n/n_c$, and $T_r = T/T_c$. The parameters P_c , T_c and n_c are the values of the thermodynamic critical point (Kondepudi & Prigogine 1998; Carey 1999; de Carvalho & Macedo 1995; Volkov & Ortega 2000).

Figure 5.1 shows the phase diagram for a fluid with $T = 0.9T_c$. One can distinguish the gaseous phase (dotted line) and the solid phase (solid line); in between (dashed line), the fluid presents a phase transition. There are states where $(\partial P/\partial \rho)_s < 0$, which is thermodynamically unstable. The parts of the dashed curve where $(\partial P/\partial \rho)_s > 0$ are metastable because a lower entropy state is reached when the fluid splits into condensed and gaseous components. The fraction of condensed over gaseous phase grows from 0 to 1 from left to right.

When the two phases coexist, the van der Waals EOS is replaced by a constant pressure marked by a horizontal line. This constant pressure level is determined by the Maxwell equal area construct (Clerk-Maxwell 1875), demanding a total zero $P \cdot v$ work for an adiabatic cycle between the fully gaseous to the fully condensed state.

Figure 5.2 shows the phase diagrams for fluids with a temperature from $T = 0.2T_c$ to $T = 1.2T_c$. The dotted line shows the original van der Waals EOS whereas the solid line displays the modified law using the Maxwell construct. There is no Maxwell construct for $T \geq T_c$ as $(\partial P/\partial \rho)_s$ is always ≥ 0 . Lekner (1982) provides a parametric solution to the van der Waals and Maxwell construct, using Δs as variable.

The Maxwell line is very similar to the laboratory condensation line for H_2 in a $T - P$ diagram as can be seen in Fig. 5.3, but is rather off for He, especially at low temperatures. Correctly representing the H_2 phase transition is what is essential for our study as in the astrophysical context, a H_2 phase transition is always at higher temperature and lower pressure than for He.

Maxwell line:
Phase transition

Figure 5.2.: van der Waals phase diagram for a fluid with a temperature of $T_r = 0.2$ (black), $T_r = 0.4$ (yellow), $T_r = 0.6$ (green), $T_r = 0.8$ (blue), $T_r = 1.0$ (red), and $T_r = 1.2$ (magenta). Solid line: van der Waals EOS with Maxwell construct, dotted line: original van der Waals EOS.

Figure 5.3.: H₂ and He laboratory data and van der Waals phase diagrams. Blue: H₂, red: He. Solid line: laboratory data; dotted line: van der Waals vapor curve derived from Maxwell construct.

5.2.1 Density derivative

The isotherm density derivative of a van der Waals fluid is:

$$\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}\right)_T = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{on the Maxwell line} \\ \frac{24T_r}{m(n_r-3)^2} - \frac{6n_r}{m} & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (5.5)$$

Phase transition:
($\partial P / \partial \rho$)_s = 0

One can see that it drops to zero once on the Maxwell line, that is, if in a phase transition. The adiabatic density derivative is:

$$\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}\right)_s = \gamma \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}\right)_T \quad (5.6)$$

where the adiabatic index is $\gamma = c_p / c_v$. Thus, ($\partial P / \partial \rho$)_s = 0 for a fluid in a phase transition.

5.3 FLUID MIXTURE

In a fluid consisting of K different components i , the mean mixture number density is $n = \sum_i n_i$, the mixture mass density is $\rho = \sum_i \rho_i$ with $\rho_i = m_i n_i$, and the mixture pressure is $P = \sum_i P_i$. In the case of an ideal gas, Dalton's law states $P = \sum_i x_i P_i$. Each component has a molecular fraction $x_i = n_i / n$ and a mass fraction $w_i = m_i / m$ with $m = \sum_i x_i m_i$.

Mixture properties:
 T, n, P, x_i, w_i

6

PLANE-PARALLEL COLLAPSE

Fastest collapse

Lin et al. (1965) and Zel'dovich (1970) show that a plane-parallel collapse, leading to a sheet-like geometry, is a faster collapse than filament- or point-like ones. This has been confirmed experimentally by Shandarin et al. (1995).

6.1 ENERGY AND RADIATION TRANSFER DURING CONTRACTION

We consider a non-rotating sphere of radius r initially in unstable equilibrium which contracts at constant mass as an ellipsoid with semi-principal axes a , b and c (see Fig. 6.1). In a sheet-like collapse, two semi-axes remain the same ($a = b = r$) while one is decreasing ($c = \varepsilon r$), leading to an oblate spheroid. In a filament-like collapse, one semi-axis remains the same ($a = r$) while two are decreasing together ($b = c = \varepsilon r$), leading to a prolate spheroid. In a point-like collapse, all the three semi-axes decrease together ($a = b = c = \varepsilon r$), remaining a sphere. During compression, density increases by a factor $Z = n/n_0$. Since the ellipsoid volume is $V_{\text{ell}} = 4/3 \pi abc$, compression changes as: $\varepsilon_{\text{oblate}} = Z^{-1}$, $\varepsilon_{\text{prolate}} = Z^{-1/2}$, and $\varepsilon_{\text{sphere}} = Z^{-1/3}$.

6.1.1 Gravitational energy

The gravitational energy difference between the initial sphere and subsequent ellipsoids must be released as additional thermal energy. The gravitational energy of a revolution ellipsoid reads, with $E_{G,0} = E_{G,\text{sphere}}(r) = -(3/5)GM^2/r$ (Landau & Lifshitz 1975):

$$\frac{E_{\text{oblate}}(Z)}{E_{G,0}} = \frac{\arccos(Z^{-1})}{\sqrt{1-Z^{-2}}} = \frac{\pi}{2} - Z^{-1} + O(Z^{-2}), \quad (6.1)$$

$$\frac{E_{\text{prolate}}(Z)}{E_{G,0}} = \frac{\text{arcosh}(\sqrt{Z})}{\sqrt{1-Z^{-1}}} = \log(2\sqrt{Z}) + O\left(\frac{\log(Z)}{Z}\right), \quad (6.2)$$

$$\frac{E_{\text{sphere}}(Z)}{E_{G,0}} = Z^{1/3}. \quad (6.3)$$

Infinite densities
with finite
temperature increase

Sheet-like contraction leads to infinite densities with *finite* temperature increase, which is much more favourable for reaching condensation conditions than filament-like or point-like contraction.

We show now that the maximum relative temperature increase of an initial perfect gas sphere initially in equilibrium is bounded. State 0 is the initial (unstable) equilibrium sphere case, and state 1 is any later denser case, not necessarily in equilibrium. Since in equilibrium, the initial state respects the virial condition,

$$E_{G,0} + 2E_{\text{kin},0} = 0, \quad (6.4)$$

Figure 6.1.: Collapsing geometries.

where $E_{\text{kin},0}$ is the kinetic energy. At rest, the initial sphere kinetic energy consists only of microscopic motion and is proportional to the initial temperature T_0 .

The initial and later total energies are,

$$E_{\text{tot},0} = E_{G,0} + E_{\text{kin},0}, \quad (6.5)$$

$$E_{\text{tot},1} = E_{G,1} + E_{\text{kin},1}. \quad (6.6)$$

Taking into account possible radiative cooling, we suppose $E_{\text{tot},1} \leq E_{\text{tot},0}$, which leads to, using the initial virial condition,

$$\frac{T_1}{T_0} \leq \frac{E_{\text{kin},1}}{E_{\text{kin},0}} \leq 2 \frac{E_{G,1}}{E_{G,0}} - 1. \quad (6.7)$$

The first inequality takes into account that state 1 is not necessarily in equilibrium, some kinetic energy may be attributed to macroscopic motion.

Thus, using the above potential energy ratios, in the case of an oblate spheroid contraction,

$$\frac{T_1}{T_0} \leq \pi - 1 - 2Z^{-1} + O(Z^{-2}), \quad (6.8)$$

Maximum
temperature increase
of 2.1

that is, the final temperature can not exceed $\pi - 1 \approx 2.1$ times the initial temperature. In the case of a prolate spheroid contraction, temperature is logarithmically bounded as Z increases,

$$\frac{T_1}{T_0} \leq \log(4Z) - 1 + O\left(\frac{\log(Z)}{Z}\right), \quad (6.9)$$

while in a spherical contraction, temperature is bounded by the cubic root of compression,

$$\frac{T_1}{T_0} \leq 2Z^{1/3} - 1. \quad (6.10)$$

6.1.2 Radiative cooling

Energy lost by radiation lowers temperature, but if during contraction opacity increases, at some point the radiative cooling rate drops below the heating rate due to gravitational energy conversion, slowing down the collapse. Here we show with simple arguments how opacity changes when continuously contracting an initial sphere towards denser, smaller spheres, or towards denser revolution ellipsoids of oblate or prolate kinds, keeping the longest axis constant, and assuming at any stage uniform density, and constant absorption cross-section.

Optical depth

The optical depth τ in the cumulated absorption over a photon path ℓ : $\tau \equiv \int_0^\ell \sigma n d\ell$, where σ is the absorption cross-section of individual atoms with number density n . The central optical depth, calculated from the centre to the ellipsoid edge along some direction, is a first order estimator of the average

optical depth. We compare the optical depth $\tau_0 = r\sigma n_0$ for the initial sphere with the later ones. For revolution ellipsoids, where a and c are the semi-long and short axes respectively, the distance from the center to some point on the edge is $\ell(\theta) = ac / \sqrt{a^2 \sin^2 \theta + c^2 \cos^2 \theta}$ for oblate spheroids, and $\ell(\theta) = ac / \sqrt{a^2 \cos^2 \theta + c^2 \sin^2 \theta}$ for prolate spheroids. The angle θ vanishes at the spheroid equator. Since the ellipticity $\varepsilon = c/a$ varies as Z^{-1} , $Z^{-1/2}$, and $Z^{-1/3}$ in the oblate, prolate and spherical cases respectively, the optical depth ratios as functions of compression Z and θ are found to be:

$$\frac{\tau_{\text{oblate}}}{\tau_0} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sin^2 \theta + Z^{-2} \cos^2 \theta}}, \quad (6.11)$$

$$\frac{\tau_{\text{prolate}}}{\tau_0} = \frac{Z^{1/2}}{\sqrt{\cos^2 \theta + Z^{-1} \sin^2 \theta}}, \quad (6.12)$$

$$\frac{\tau_{\text{sphere}}}{\tau_0} = Z^{2/3}. \quad (6.13)$$

Optical depth from center

Thus in the oblate case the central optical depth ratio does not change along the poles, and at high compression remains barely increased over most of directions. In the prolate case it increases the least along the equator, but is proportional to the square root of compression. In the spherical case it increases the most rapidly, as a power 2/3 of compression. Thus sheet-like compression provides the least optical depth increase, spherical compression the most.

Global absorption

One can refine the previous estimate for cooling by calculating for any point inside an ellipsoid the probability for a photon to be absorbed. For a given optical depth τ the absorption probability is $p = 1 - \exp(-\tau)$. The global probability of absorption must be calculated for all solid angles for all points. These 4- or 5-dimensional integrals for bi- or tri-axial ellipsoids seems not to be solvable analytically, and straightforward numerical quadratures would be expensive. Thus we resort to a Monte-Carlo draw to estimate these quantities. We pick randomly uniformly a number of points inside the ellipsoid and a random uniform directional unit vector \mathbf{n} , and find the two distances ℓ_1, ℓ_2 , to the edge of the ellipsoid, allowing to calculate two optical depths τ_1, τ_2 , and corresponding absorption probabilities p_1, p_2 for each point. Knowing the starting position \mathbf{x} inside the ellipsoid (a, b, c) , and the direction vector \mathbf{n} , we find the two signed distances to the ellipsoid edge by solving the quadratic equation $(x + \ell n_x)/a^2 + (y + \ell n_y)^2/b^2 + (z + \ell n_z)^2/c^2 = 1$ for ℓ . Explicitly, noting $\alpha = a^{-2}, \beta = b^{-2}, \gamma = c^{-2}$, for each point $\mathbf{x} = [x, y, z]$ the procedure becomes:

Monte Carlo random point and direction picking

$$A = \alpha n_x^2 + \beta n_y^2 + \gamma n_z^2, \quad (6.14)$$

$$B = \alpha x n_x + \beta y n_y + \gamma z n_z, \quad (6.15)$$

$$C = \alpha x^2 + \beta y^2 + \gamma z^2 - 1, \quad (6.16)$$

$$D = \sqrt{B^2 - AC}, \quad (6.17)$$

$$\ell_1 = -(D + B)/A, \quad \ell_2 = (D - B)/A. \quad (6.18)$$

Figure 6.2.: Absorption probability calculated by Monte Carlo in contracting oblate spheroids (red), prolate spheroids (blue), and spheres (black), as function of compression $Z > 1$. At $Z = 1$ all cases are spherical. The dashed curves show the absorption probability when photons start at the center only. The solid curves show the average probability when starting anywhere inside the ellipsoid in random directions. Different cases are displayed where the initial sphere optical depth τ_0 is the indicated.

For each set of ℓ_i , average absorption probabilities can be found for a range of σ 's. The two absorption probabilities $p_i = 1 - \exp(-\sigma n|\ell_i|)$, $i = 1, 2$, for each point provide two distinct probabilities. Each set of p_i s should converge towards a similar average value. The difference allow to check the error obtained with a finite number of points. Between $2 \cdot 10^4$ (sphere case) and $3 \cdot 10^7$ points (oblate spheroid case) have been drawn such that the $\log_{10} p_i$ between the two sets differ by at most 0.01. The result is shown in Fig. 6.2. The error bars would be comparable or smaller than the curve thickness.

The sphere and prolate spheroid cases become quickly optically thick, increasing as $Z^{2/3}$ and $Z^{1/2}$ respectively in the optically thin regime. In contrast, the absorption of a contracting optically thin oblate spheroid increases logarithmically until it reaches $Z\tau_0 \sim 1$ beyond which it remains approximately constant; in other words if the initial state is optically thin, it remains so even after infinite compression. The emission signature of a collapsing sheet should therefore remain observationally barely noticeable, since both temperature and optical thickness increase by very modest factors in comparison with the other geometries.

*Optically thin
medium remains so*

6.2 INTERSTELLAR CONDITIONS

As shown in the above sections, the adiabatic matter compression of a sheet-like geometry leads to a finite release of energy, leading to a maximum relative temperature increase of only 2.1, while in a filament-like geometry the energy diverges logarithmically, and in a point-like geometry as $Z^{1/3}$ with Z the density compression. Fig. 6.3 shows how an initial sphere at $T = 10$ K, $P = 10^{-12}$ Pa would change its temperature and pressure when contracting adiabatically towards a sheet, filament, or point, changing its gravitational energy into thermal energy. Whereas the temperature is quickly increasing with filament- and point-like geometries, in the sheet-like geometry it rises only to ~ 21 K, well below the 33 K critical temperature of H_2 . Clearly the sheet-like collapse is the most favourable geometry for reaching the H_2 phase transition regime. Including radiative cooling, which is the fastest in sheet-like geometry, the temperature increase by contraction is even less.

*$T \leq 15$ K:
Phase transition
possible*

Figure 6.3.: Adiabatic compression curves of an initial sphere to sheet-, filament- and point-like geometries (black lines) for interstellar conditions ($T = 10$ K, $P = 10^{-12}$ Pa) are shown. Sheet-like collapses allow to reach the phase transition regime even without cooling. Cooling would displace the curves to lower temperature. H₂ (blue) and He (red) laboratory data.

GRAVITATIONAL STABILITY

The conditions of a gravitational collapse due to an instability has first been studied by Jeans (1902). The gravitational stability of self-gravitating binary and multi-component fluids has been studied by Grishchuk & Zeldovich (1981) and shown that there can be only one unstable solution. Jog & Solomon (1984a,b) have first discussed the stability of two-component disks. In a similar fashion de Carvalho & Macedo (1995) have studied oscillations and resonances in a binary fluid mixture. Volkov & Ortega (2000) have discussed the stability of self-gravitating systems with a spectrum of particle masses and consider rotating mediums. In this chapter, the gravitational stability of one- and many-component fluids will be presented with a special emphasis if a component is in a phase transition.

7.1 GRAVITATIONAL STABILITY OF A SINGLE COMPONENT FLUID

The equations for conservation of mass and momentum, and for the gravitational potential of a fluid read:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (7.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v}) + \nabla P + \rho \nabla \Phi = 0, \quad (7.2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \nabla \Phi - 4\pi G \rho = 0. \quad (7.3)$$

Following Jeans (1902), we supersede these equations with perturbation terms in the x -direction $\rho = \rho_0 + \delta\rho$, $P = P_0 + \delta P$, $\Phi = \Phi_0 + \delta\Phi$ and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_0 + \delta\mathbf{v}$ with $\delta\mathbf{v} = (\delta v, 0, 0)^T$, linearising the equations and setting $\delta P = \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}\right)_s \delta\rho$:

$$\frac{\partial \delta\rho}{\partial t} + \rho_0 \nabla \cdot \delta\mathbf{v} = 0, \quad (7.4)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial \delta\mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}\right)_s \nabla \delta\rho + \rho_0 \nabla \delta\Phi = 0, \quad (7.5)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \nabla \delta\Phi - 4\pi G \delta\rho = 0. \quad (7.6)$$

This system of partial differential equations is transformed to an algebraic system of linear equations in the Fourier space: $\delta A = \int dk \hat{A}(k) \exp[i(kx - \omega t)]$, where A represents ρ , v , and Φ . The passage to Fourier space transforms the differential operators $\partial/\partial t$ and $\partial/\partial x$ to multiplications by $-i\omega$ and ik , respectively:

$$-i\omega \hat{\rho} + ik \rho_0 \hat{v} = 0, \quad (7.7)$$

$$-i\omega \rho_0 \hat{v} + ik \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}\right)_s \hat{\rho} + ik \rho_0 \hat{\Phi} = 0, \quad (7.8)$$

$$-k^2 \hat{\Phi} - 4\pi G \hat{\rho} = 0, \quad (7.9)$$

*Transformation to
Fourier space*

which can be written in matrix form $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega & k\rho_0 & 0 \\ k(\partial P/\partial\rho)_s & \omega\rho_0 & k\rho_0 \\ -4\pi G & 0 & -k^2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\rho} \\ \hat{v} \\ \hat{\Phi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7.10)$$

Non-trivial solutions for \mathbf{x} require that the determinant of \mathbf{A} vanishes,

$$\det(\mathbf{A}) = k^2\rho_0 \left[\omega^2 + 4\pi G\rho_0 - k^2 \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial\rho} \right)_s \right], \quad (7.11)$$

which is the case for either $k = 0$, or

$$\omega^2 = k^2 \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial\rho} \right)_s - 4\pi G\rho_0. \quad (7.12)$$

A fluid is unstable if $\omega^2 < 0$, which is the case if:

$$k^2 < k_J^2 \equiv \frac{4\pi G\rho_0}{(\partial P/\partial\rho)_s}. \quad (7.13)$$

The classical Jeans criterion for a wavelength reads,

*Jeans instability
criterion*

$$\lambda > \lambda_J \equiv \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial\rho} \right)_s \frac{\pi}{G\rho}}. \quad (7.14)$$

Therefore the effective gravitational instability is directly dependent on the equation of state of the medium.

7.1.1 Gaseous phase

When a fluid is in gaseous phase, i.e. far away of a phase transition, the ideal gas equation of state (§5.1) can be used. It's density derivative is always positive (see Equ. 5.2), which leads to the classical, ideal monoatomic gas Jeans criterion for instability,

*Ideal gas Jeans
instability criterion*

$$\lambda > \lambda_J = \sqrt{\frac{\pi\gamma k_B T}{G\rho m}}. \quad (7.15)$$

7.1.2 Phase transition

When considering a fluid presenting a phase transition the term $(\partial P/\partial\rho)_s$ may differ from that of an ideal gas. As seen before, in the case of the van der Waals fluid, the Maxwell construct must be used, which may considerably change the combined stability of the fluid (see §5.2). In the presence of a phase transition, the equation of state gradient is strongly modified, in particular $(\partial P/\partial\rho)_s = 0$. Therefore, a self-gravitating fluid in a phase transition is also automatically gravitationally unstable.

*Phase transition:
Fluid unstable at any
scale*

Figure 7.1 shows the 3D representation of the EOS including the Maxwell construct. Clearly the curved triangular region, the phase transition region (on

Figure 7.1.: van der Waals EOS, including the Maxwell construct.

the left) has a very different gradient than the almost ideal-gas region at low density and high temperature, or the condensed phase region at high density. It is remarkable that a temperature drop by one order of magnitude from the critical temperature leads to a drop in the critical pressure by 14 orders of magnitude. For example for H₂ at 3 K the critical pressure is $6.4 \cdot 10^{-9}$ Pa.

7.2 GRAVITATIONAL STABILITY OF A FLUID MIXTURE

Considering a fluid mixture as a one-component fluid using average properties, the Jeans criterion would be as follows:

$$k^2 < k_J^2 \equiv \frac{4\pi G\rho}{(\partial P/\partial\rho)_s} . \tag{7.16}$$

This is, however, an inappropriate approach, especially if each component has a different mean square velocity, which is the case in a isothermal fluid with different molecular masses.

In order to correctly predict the stability of a many-component fluid mixture, each component has to be treated individually. We will show how this can be done for two components as this is relevant for this work, see Grishchuk & Zeldovich (1981) for the solution of a n -component fluid.

7.2.1 Binary fluid

Having two components α and β , the mass and momentum conservation have to be fulfilled for each component:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha \mathbf{v}_\alpha) = 0, \quad (7.17)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho_\beta}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\beta \mathbf{v}_\beta) = 0, \quad (7.18)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho_\alpha \mathbf{v}_\alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\alpha \mathbf{v}_\alpha \mathbf{v}_\alpha) + \nabla P_\alpha + \rho \nabla \Phi = 0, \quad (7.19)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho_\beta \mathbf{v}_\beta}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_\beta \mathbf{v}_\beta \mathbf{v}_\beta) + \nabla P_\beta + \rho \nabla \Phi = 0, \quad (7.20)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \nabla \Phi - 4\pi G (\rho_\alpha + \rho_\beta) = 0. \quad (7.21)$$

Superseding, as in §7.1, these equation with perturbation terms $A_\alpha = A_{\alpha 0} + \delta A_\alpha$ and $A_\beta = A_{\beta 0} + \delta A_\beta$ in the x -direction and linearising them yields:

$$\frac{\partial \delta \rho_\alpha}{\partial t} + \rho_\alpha \nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{v}_\alpha = 0, \quad (7.22)$$

$$\frac{\partial \delta \rho_\beta}{\partial t} + \rho_\beta \nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{v}_\beta = 0, \quad (7.23)$$

$$\rho_\alpha \frac{\partial \delta \mathbf{v}_\alpha}{\partial t} + \left(\frac{\partial P_\alpha}{\partial \rho_\alpha} \right)_s \nabla \delta \rho_\alpha + \rho_\alpha \nabla \delta \Phi = 0, \quad (7.24)$$

$$\rho_\beta \frac{\partial \delta \mathbf{v}_\beta}{\partial t} + \left(\frac{\partial P_\beta}{\partial \rho_\beta} \right)_s \nabla \delta \rho_\beta + \rho_\beta \nabla \delta \Phi = 0, \quad (7.25)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \nabla \delta \Phi - 4\pi G (\delta \rho_\alpha + \delta \rho_\beta) = 0, \quad (7.26)$$

which transform into a linear equation system in Fourier space:

$$-i\omega \hat{\rho}_\alpha + ik \rho_{\alpha 0} \hat{v}_\alpha = 0, \quad (7.27)$$

$$-i\omega \hat{\rho}_\beta + ik \rho_{\beta 0} \hat{v}_\beta = 0, \quad (7.28)$$

$$-i\omega \rho_{\alpha 0} \hat{v}_\alpha + ik \left(\frac{\partial P_\alpha}{\partial \rho_\alpha} \right)_s \hat{\rho}_\alpha + ik \rho_{\alpha 0} \hat{\Phi} = 0, \quad (7.29)$$

$$-i\omega \rho_{\beta 0} \hat{v}_\beta + ik \left(\frac{\partial P_\beta}{\partial \rho_\beta} \right)_s \hat{\rho}_\beta + ik \rho_{\beta 0} \hat{\Phi} = 0, \quad (7.30)$$

$$-k^2 \hat{\Phi} - 4\pi G (\hat{\rho}_\alpha + \hat{\rho}_\beta) = 0. \quad (7.31)$$

This can be written in the matrix form $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$, defining $c_\alpha^2 = (\partial P_\alpha / \partial \rho_\alpha)_s$ and $c_\beta^2 = (\partial P_\beta / \partial \rho_\beta)_s$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega & 0 & k\rho_{\alpha 0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega & 0 & k\rho_{\beta 0} & 0 \\ k c_\alpha^2 & 0 & \omega \rho_{\alpha 0} & 0 & k \rho_{\alpha 0} \\ 0 & k c_\beta^2 & 0 & \omega \rho_{\beta 0} & k \rho_{\beta 0} \\ -4\pi G & -4\pi G & 0 & 0 & -k^2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\rho}_\alpha \\ \hat{\rho}_\beta \\ \hat{v}_\alpha \\ \hat{v}_\beta \\ \hat{\Phi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7.32)$$

In order to simplify, we set $\Gamma_\alpha = 4\pi G\rho_{\alpha 0}$ and $\Gamma_\beta = 4\pi G\rho_{\beta 0}$ and find the following determinant:

$$\det(\mathbf{A}) = k^2\rho_{\alpha 0}\rho_{\beta 0} \left[\omega^4 + (\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2(c_\alpha^2 + c_\beta^2))\omega^2 + k^2(-\Gamma_\beta c_\alpha^2 - \Gamma_\alpha c_\beta^2 + k^2 c_\alpha^2 c_\beta^2) \right]. \quad (7.33)$$

Again, in order to have a non-trivial solution, its determinant must be zero, which, in the case of $k \neq 0$, is

$$\omega^4 + (\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2(c_\alpha^2 + c_\beta^2))\omega^2 - k^2(\Gamma_\beta c_\alpha^2 + \Gamma_\alpha c_\beta^2 - k^2 c_\alpha^2 c_\beta^2) = 0, \quad (7.34)$$

with the following solution for ω^2 :

$$\begin{aligned} (\omega^2)_{1,2} &= -\frac{1}{2}(\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2(c_\alpha^2 + c_\beta^2)) \\ &\pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}(\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2(c_\alpha^2 + c_\beta^2))^2 + k^2(\Gamma_\beta c_\alpha^2 + \Gamma_\alpha c_\beta^2 - k^2 c_\alpha^2 c_\beta^2)}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.35)$$

Setting $\omega^2 = 0$ in Equ. (7.34) yields:

$$k^2(-\Gamma_\beta c_\alpha^2 - \Gamma_\alpha c_\beta^2 + k^2 c_\alpha^2 c_\beta^2) = 0, \quad (7.36)$$

with the following solution:

$$k_{\text{GZ}}^2 \equiv \frac{\Gamma_\alpha}{c_\alpha^2} + \frac{\Gamma_\beta}{c_\beta^2}, \quad (7.37)$$

Jeans-like instability criterion

a fluid is unstable for $\omega^2 < 0$ or $\omega^2 \in \mathfrak{J}$, which is the case for $k^2 < k_{\text{GZ}}^2$.

7.2.2 Multi-component fluid

It is shown by Grishchuk & Zeldovich (1981) that the above approach can be used for a n -component fluid, leading to the following stability criterion for a multi-component fluid:

$$k^2 < k_{\text{GZ}}^2 \equiv \sum_i \frac{4\pi G\rho_i}{\partial P_i / \partial \rho_i}. \quad (7.38)$$

7.2.3 Gaseous phase

A gaseous fluid far from the condensed phase can be approximated with the ideal gas law (5.1). The partial pressures can be calculated using Dalton's law. Equ. (7.38) becomes:

$$k_{\text{GZ,id}}^2 = \frac{4\pi G}{\gamma k_{\text{B}} T} \sum_i n_i m_i^2, \quad (7.39)$$

Ideal gas Jeans-like instability criterion

This equation differs from Equ. (7.16), which in the ideal gas case becomes:

$$k_{\text{J,id}}^2 = \frac{4\pi G}{\gamma k_{\text{B}} T} n m^2. \quad (7.40)$$

In the case where all components have the same temperature $k_{\text{GZ,id}} \geq k_{\text{J,id}}$ independent of the molecular fraction x_α and molecular masses. In the case of a H₂-He mixture, the maximum $k_{\text{GZ,id}}^2/k_{\text{J,id}}^2 = 1.12$ at $x_{\text{H}_2} = 0.67$.

7.2.4 Phase transition

When approaching a phase transition, the ideal gas law does not take into account condensations and does not yield correct values anymore. The van der Waals equation of state (5.4) must be used. In the phase transition regime $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_s = 0$, varying density lets pressure constant. This is a crucial effect for this work, since gravitational contraction is no longer compensated by pressure increase. Setting $c_\alpha = 0$ in Equ. (7.34) we get:

$$\omega^4 + [\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2 c_\beta^2] \omega^2 - \Gamma_\alpha k^2 c_\beta^2 = 0, \quad (7.41)$$

its solutions is:

$$\omega^2 = -\frac{1}{2}(\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2 c_\beta^2) \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{4}(\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2 c_\beta^2)^2 + \Gamma_\alpha k^2 c_\beta^2}. \quad (7.42)$$

If we set $\omega^2 = 0$ in Equ. (7.41), only the trivial $k = 0$ is a solution. Otherwise, the upper sign solution of Equ. (7.42) is always positive and the lower sign solution is always negative for any k as:

$$(\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2 c_\beta^2)^2 < (\Gamma_\alpha + \Gamma_\beta - k^2 c_\beta^2)^2 + 4\Gamma_\alpha k^2 c_\beta^2. \quad (7.43)$$

Phase transition in
one component:
Total fluid unstable

Therefore one ω -solution of Equ. (7.42) is always negative and thus unstable, independent of the strength of either Γ_α or Γ_β .

LENNARD-JONES INTER-MOLECULAR POTENTIAL

Figure 8.1.: Lennard-Jones potential.

The van der Waals model of phase transition fluid is convenient for a continuum fluid description, but fails to represent all the phenomena around the phase transition, which is the reason for correcting it with the above mentioned Maxwell construct. Even with the Maxwell construct, however, a local thermal equilibrium is still supposed to hold. In astrophysical contexts, often even these assumptions cannot be granted. For instance, in supersonic turbulent situations, ubiquitous in the interstellar medium, thermal equilibrium cannot be satisfied since mechanical energy propagates faster than thermal energy through pressure. Thus any method using quantities, like temperature or pressure, implicitly assumes that a local thermal equilibrium is established, which makes their use in the supersonic turbulent regime uncertain.

van der Waals:
Assumes local
thermal equilibrium

A much less demanding model of fluid is provided by molecular dynamics, where the simplest molecule interactions close to the van der Waals model in equilibrium situations is provided by the Lennard-Jones intermolecular potential (Jones 1924). No local or global thermal equilibrium is required. The Lennard-Jones potential is reliable when studying not too dense phases and consists of an attractive long-range term and a repulsive short-range term (Fig. 8.1),

$$\Phi_{\text{LJ}}(r) = 4 \frac{\epsilon}{m} \left(r_{\sigma}^{-12} - r_{\sigma}^{-6} \right), \quad (8.1)$$

Intermolecular
potential

with $r_{\sigma} = r/\sigma$. Its minimum value, located at $r_{\sigma} = 2^{1/6}$, is $-\epsilon/m$.

It reproduces the van der Waals equation of state when in equilibrium conditions using the following relations (Caillol 1998):

$$T_c = 1.326 \frac{\epsilon}{k_B}, \quad (8.2)$$

$$n_c = 0.316 \sigma^{-3}, \quad (8.3)$$

$$P_c = 0.157 \frac{\epsilon}{k_B \sigma^3}. \quad (8.4)$$

8.1 LENNARD-JONES MIXTURES

For a fluid mixture, we use the usual Lorentz-Berthelot combining rule for the Lennard-Jones potential between two molecules:

$$\Phi_{\text{LJ}}(r_{ij}) = 4 \frac{\epsilon_{ij}}{m_i} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right] \quad (8.5)$$

with $\sigma_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_i + \sigma_j)$ and $\epsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\epsilon_i \epsilon_j}$ (Lorentz 1881; Berthelot 1898). The most accurate mixing rules for energy and distance are (Banaszak et al. 1995; Chen et al. 2001):

$$\sigma^3 = \sum_i^K \sum_i^K x_i x_j \sigma_{ij}^3, \quad (8.6)$$

Mixing rules

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sum_i^K \sum_i^K x_i x_j \epsilon \sigma_{ij}^3}{\sigma^3}. \quad (8.7)$$

Since $T \propto \epsilon$ and $n \propto \sigma^{-3}$ we have $n_c/n_{c,\text{ff}} = (\sigma/\sigma_\alpha)^{-3}$ and $T_c/T_{c,\alpha} = \epsilon/\epsilon_\alpha$. Using Equ. (5.4), we find $P_c = (8/3)T_c n_c$, and therefore $P_c/P_{c,\alpha} = (\sigma/\sigma_\alpha)^{-3} \cdot (\epsilon/\epsilon_\alpha)$.

Note that as in the ideal gas case, using these mixing properties to calculate k_J in analogy to Equ. (7.16) instead of using Equ. (7.38) would lead to different results. In the ideal gas case, the biggest difference is $\sim 10\%$, but in the present case of a van der Waals fluid the difference can be much bigger, for example k_J always returns a finite number if the critical temperature of the mixture $T_c > 1$ whereas k_{GZ} can nevertheless be infinite if one of the components is in a phase transition.

8.1.1 Binary mixture

Considering a fluid consisting of two components α and β , we define

$$\theta = \frac{T_{c,\beta}}{T_{c,\alpha}} = \frac{\epsilon_\beta}{\epsilon_\alpha}, \quad (8.8)$$

Binary fluid ratios

$$\nu = \frac{n_{c,\beta}}{n_{c,\text{ff}}} = \left(\frac{\sigma_\beta}{\sigma_\alpha} \right)^{-3}, \quad (8.9)$$

$$\mu = \frac{m_\beta}{m_\alpha}. \quad (8.10)$$

The following Lennard-Jones properties can be derived using Equ. (8.5 – 8.10):

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_\alpha \left(1 + \nu^{-1/3} \right), \quad (8.11)$$

$$\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \epsilon_\alpha \theta^{1/2}, \quad (8.12)$$

as well as the following van der Waals mixture properties:

$$\frac{n_{c,x}}{n_{c,\alpha}} = \left[x_\alpha^2 + \frac{x_\alpha x_\beta}{4} (1 + \nu^{-1/3})^3 + \frac{x_\beta^2}{\nu} \right]^{-1}, \quad (8.13)$$

$$\frac{T_{c,x}}{T_{c,\alpha}} = \frac{n_{c,x}}{n_{c,\alpha}} \left[x_\alpha^2 \nu^{1/3} + \frac{x_\alpha x_\beta \theta^{1/2}}{4} (1 + \nu^{-1/3})^3 + \frac{x_\beta^2 \theta}{\nu} \right], \quad (8.14)$$

$$\frac{P_{c,x}}{P_{c,\alpha}} = \frac{n_{c,x}}{n_{c,\alpha}} \cdot \frac{T_{c,x}}{T_{c,\alpha}}, \quad (8.15)$$

with $x_\beta = 1 - x_\alpha$. Without loss of generality we choose $\theta < 1$.

Three different cases can be distinguished, shown in Fig. 8.2:

(A) $T_{c,\beta} < T_{c,\alpha} < T$

Having the temperature above both critical ones, neither component can be in a phase transition and k_{GZ} is always finite.

(B) $T_{c,\beta} < T < T_{c,\alpha}$

β is still above the critical temperature and cannot be in a phase transition, but α may or may not be in a phase transition depending on n_α .

(C) $T < T_{c,\beta} < T_{c,\alpha}$

Having the temperature below both critical temperatures, both components can be in a phase transition. At equal component number density, α is faster in a phase transition, but theoretically, at low n_β , β could be in a phase transition without α , but this hardly ever happens in reality.

These three cases are studied using computer simulations (see Table 12.1).

Hydrogen-Helium Mixture

The critical temperature of H₂ and He are 32.97 and 5.19K, whereas their usual Lennard-Jones ϵ values are 36.4 and 10.57 k_B K. This is in conflict with the temperature conversion of Equ. (8.8), as $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{-He}} = 6.35$ using critical temperatures whereas $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{-He}} = 3.44$ using the Lennard-Jones ϵ values. The same is the case to a lesser degree for the critical density.

All performed simulations are molecule-independent, but θ , ν and μ need to be defined. These values were set using T_c , n_c and the molecular mass of laboratory He and H₂ data (Air Liquide 1976). The goal of this article is to understand the role of a secondary component in a fluid presenting a phase transition together with gravity. In molecular clouds, the most likely case of a phase transition is $T_{c,\text{H}_2} > T > T_{c,\text{He}}$, thus it is important to have a correct ($T_{\text{He}}/T_{\text{H}_2}$) fraction.

Conflict:
Critical values
vs
Lennard-Jones

Figure 8.2.: van der Waals phase diagram with Maxwell construct for a $\alpha - \beta$ mixture, each species considered as independent. (A) $T = 1.5 T_{c,\alpha}$; (B) $T = 1.5 T_{c,\beta}$; (C) $T = T_{CMB}$.

Blue lines: α species, red lines: β species, black lines: initial partial number density of the α species used in the binary fluid simulations (§12) for $n = n_{\alpha} + n_{\beta} = 10^{-2} [n_{c,\alpha}]$ for $x_{\alpha} = 1, 0.75, 0.25$.

8.2 VIRIAL THEOREM

8.2.1 Lagrange-Jacobi identity

The virial theorem (Clausius 1870) describes the statistical equilibrium of a system of interacting particles or fluid systems, relating the kinetic and potential energies. In the case of a self-gravitating Lennard-Jones fluid, the Lennard-Jones potential and gravity combine as a total potential $\Phi = \Phi_G + \Phi_{LJ}$.

The virial theorem for this new potential can be derived using the Lagrange-Jacobi identity path, by taking the second time derivative of the moment of the polar inertia $I \equiv \sum_i m_i r_i^2$, we find,

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 I}{dt^2} = \sum_i m_i \dot{r}_i^2 + \sum_i m_i \mathbf{r}_i \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_i, \quad (8.16)$$

where the first right-hand term is twice the kinetic energy E_{kin} , and the second one is the virial term. For a system near a statistical equilibrium, both sides of this equation should oscillate around 0, so the respective time averages should vanish.

The Lennard-Jones potential is a sum of two homogeneous functions¹ $\Phi_{LJ} = \Phi_{LJ,a} + \Phi_{LJ,r}$ of degree -6 and -12 respectively, while gravity is of degree -1 . So we can use Euler's theorem of homogeneous functions to express the virial term as a sum of potential energies multiplied by minus the homogeneous degree. The Lagrange-Jacobi identity becomes

$$0 = \underbrace{2E_{\text{kin}} + 12E_r}_{>0} + \underbrace{6E_a + E_G}_{<0}. \quad (8.17)$$

*Kinetic, gravitational
and Lennard-Jones
terms*

There are two negative, attractive terms, and two positive, repulsive terms. If the attractive and repulsive terms equalize each other, the system is in virial equilibrium.

8.2.2 Homogeneous density

In the case of a homogeneous density distribution of mass M , the energy terms are:

$$E_{\text{kin}} = \frac{3k_B T}{2m} M, \quad (8.18)$$

$$E_r = R \frac{\epsilon_\alpha \sigma_\alpha^{12} n^4}{m} M, \quad (8.19)$$

$$E_a = -A \frac{\epsilon_\alpha \sigma_\alpha^6 n^2}{m} M, \quad (8.20)$$

$$E_G = -G f_G(n, m) M^{5/2}, \quad (8.21)$$

with $f_G > 0$ depending on the geometry. In the case of a single-component fluid, the repulsive and attractive constants are $A = c_a$ and $R = c_r$, where

¹ By definition, a homogeneous function f of degree k satisfies $f(\lambda \mathbf{x}) = \lambda^k f(\mathbf{x})$.

the constants c_r and c_a in the Lennard-Jones terms have been calculated by straight summation over the $1.5 \cdot 10^{12}$ nearest molecules, as given in Table 8.1 for both the simple cubic (SC) and hexagonal close packed (HCP) or face-centred cubic (FCC) lattices. The coefficients c_r and c_a depend on the exact geometry, and rigid lattice spacing is only to be expected in crystalline ices, whereas in gaseous and liquid mediums the spacing is much more random. However, the order of magnitude of the coefficients remains the same.

Table 8.1.: Lattice constants.

Lattice	c_r	c_a
SC	24.8085962	33.6076959
HCP/FCC	48.5275208	57.8156842

In the case of a binary fluid mixture, The repulsive and attractive constants are:

$$R = c_r \left[x_\alpha^5 + \theta v^{-4} x_\beta^5 + \frac{\theta^{1/2}}{2^{12}} (1 + v^{-1/3})^{12} (x_\alpha x_\beta^4 + x_\alpha^4 x_\beta) \right], \quad (8.22)$$

$$A = c_a \left[x_\alpha^3 + \theta v^{-2} x_\beta^3 + \frac{\theta^{1/2}}{2^6} (1 + v^{-1/3})^6 (x_\alpha x_\beta^2 + x_\alpha^2 x_\beta) \right]. \quad (8.23)$$

Figure 8.3 shows the two constants for H₂-He mixtures.

Figure 8.3.: R/c_r (black) and A/c_a (red) values for H₂-He mixtures.

The sum of the Lennard-Jones and kinetic terms must be positive as the gravitational term is negative: $E_G < 0 < E_r + E_a + E_{\text{kin}}$. This is the case if:

$$2A\epsilon_\alpha (\sigma_\alpha^3 n)^2 \leq k_B T + 4R\epsilon_\alpha (\sigma_\alpha^3 n)^4. \quad (8.24)$$

There can be no virial equilibrium, for any mass $M > 0$, if the attractive Lennard-Jones term dominates the kinetic and repulsive terms. We define the unvirializable density domain as follows:

Unvirializable
density domain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D} &\equiv \{n : n_- < n < n_+\} \\ n_\pm^2 &= \sigma^{-6} \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{1 - 4 \frac{R}{A^2} \frac{k_B T}{\epsilon}}}{4 \frac{R}{A}}. \end{aligned} \quad (8.25)$$

Figure 8.4.: van der Waals phase transition (grey background, dotted lines) and unvirializable densities (within solid lines) of H_2 -He mixtures with $x_\alpha = 1$ (blue), $x_\alpha = 0.75$ (cyan), $x_\alpha = 0.5$ (black), $x_\alpha = 0.25$ (yellow) and $x_\alpha = 0$ (red). Dots: T_{\max} .

If the term in the square root is negative, there is no real solution and therefore no unvirializable densities. This is the case if:

Maximum
temperature

$$T > T_{\max} \equiv \frac{A^2}{4R} \frac{\epsilon}{k_B}. \quad (8.26)$$

Figure 8.4 shows the n_\pm values and the domain of the van der Waals phase transition for H_2 -He mixtures with different molecular fractions. The n_\pm curves delimit the unvirializable density domain \mathcal{D} . Note that there are unvirializable densities above the critical temperature T_c up to T_{\max} even though no phase transition is possible.

One can see that the domain of phase transition does not change a lot for the different $x_{\text{H}_2} > 0$, as the H_2 phase transition temperature remains the same and the density changes as $n_x = x \cdot n$. It is at much lower temperatures for $x_{\text{H}_2} = 0$, as there is no H_2 anymore and the phase transition domain switches to He.

The evolution of a fluids with unvirializable densities depends whether they are in a phase transition or not. If in a phase transition, there is a gravitational instability independent of M (see §7), which leads to a collapse and the formation of bodies of small mass. If not in a phase transition, there is only a gravitational collapse above the ideal gas Jeans mass M (see Equ. 7.38). Below that mass, clumps still form, which leads to an augmentation of the kinetic and repulsive Lennard-Jones terms until Equ. (8.24) is fulfilled, at which point an equilibrium is reached and the fluid may remain stable.

8.2.3 *Homogeneous sphere*

For homogeneous, finite mass spheres at a given temperature, the individual terms of the Lagrange-Jacobi identity are Eqs. (8.18 – 8.21) with

$$f_G = \left(\frac{36\pi mn}{125} \right)^{1/3}. \quad (8.27)$$

The virial equation, obtained by setting $d^2I/dt^2 = 0$ in the Lagrange-Jacobi identity, contains terms proportional to M except the gravity term, which is proportional to $M^{5/3}$. Dividing the equation by M we can separate $M^{2/3}$, yielding,

$$\text{Virial mass} \quad M^{2/3} = \left(\frac{375}{4\pi\rho} \right)^{1/3} \frac{1}{Gm} \left[k_B T + 4c_r \epsilon \left(\frac{\sigma^3 \rho}{m} \right)^4 - 2c_a \epsilon \left(\frac{\sigma^3 \rho}{m} \right)^2 \right], \quad (8.28)$$

which is indeed positive if the sum of the terms inside the brackets are also positive. However the term proportional to c_a is negative, and when large introduces the possibility that no positive solution for $M^{2/3}$ exists. Solving the bracket terms equal to zero we find again Equ. 8.24 and the unvirializable densities. Thus, M vanishes if $n \in \mathcal{D}$.

The maximum temperature at which M can vanish is thus T_{\max} of Equ. (8.26). Since the critical temperature for a phase transition in the absence of gravity is about ϵ/k_B , we see that T_{\max} can be substantially larger than the critical temperature. With the values given in Table 1 for the constants c_a and c_r , the maximum temperature below which gravity combined with molecular forces enhances fragmentation are $T_{\max} = 414.3$ K and 626.8, K for the SC and HCP/FCC lattices, respectively, which are 11.38 and 17.22 larger than ϵ/k_B .

The corresponding density ρ_f at which fragmentation can occur at *arbitrarily small mass* is

$$\text{Fragmentation density} \quad \rho_f = \frac{m}{\sigma^3} \sqrt{\frac{c_a}{4c_r}}, \quad (8.29)$$

which is of the order of the individual molecule density m/σ^3 .

The Lagrange-Jacobi identity therefore allows us to predict a density ρ_f and a maximum temperature T_{\max} below which a homogeneous sphere made of Lennard-Jones molecules can find a gravitational equilibrium at an arbitrarily small mass: in a way, this provides a simple model, an explanation, for the reason of forming substellar ice clumps out of a cold self-gravitating gas. For H_2 molecules arranged as SC or HCP/FCC lattice, we find $\rho_f = 73.8$ kg m⁻³ and 69.2 kg m⁻³, respectively. These densities are of the order or slightly below the solid or liquid H_2 density (≈ 80 kg m⁻³).

At temperatures $T > T_{\max}$ the isothermal equilibrium curves have a minimum mass when $dM/d\rho|_T = 0$, which is expressed as

$$M_{\min}^2 = K \frac{\epsilon^3 \sigma^3}{G^3 m^4} \frac{c_a^{11/2}}{c_r^{5/2}} \frac{\left[\frac{11}{5} \tau - \left(1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{11}{25} \tau} \right) \right]^3}{\sqrt{1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{11}{25} \tau}}} \quad (8.30)$$

where $\tau = T/T_{\max}$ and

$$K = \frac{81}{2\pi} \left(\frac{5}{11} \right)^{11/2} \approx 0.1686476934. \quad (8.31)$$

Figure 8.5 shows the minimum mass as a function of the temperature for HCP/FCC H_2 homogeneous spheres. It is rising very steeply at $T \gtrsim 627 \text{ K}$, but rising much slower after $\sim 1000 \text{ K}$. Interestingly the mass range includes all the masses below terrestrial planet masses for temperatures below H_2 dissociation.

$T \gtrsim 627 \text{ K}$
 $M \leq M_{\oplus}$

Figure 8.5.: Minimum mass of isothermal equilibrium curves for H_2 homogeneous spheres.

8.2.4 Condensed bodies

Different condensed and uncondensed bodies can be identified using the Lagrange-Jacobi identity, as summarized in Table 8.2.

Table 8.2.: Condensed and uncondensed bodies in a Lennard-Jones fluid using the Lagrange-Jacobi identity.

Dominating Terms	Name
$2E_{\text{kin}} + 6E_{\text{a}}$	molecular gas
$12E_{\text{r}} + 6E_{\text{a}}$	comet
$12E_{\text{r}} + E_{\text{G}}$	rocky planetoid
$2E_{\text{kin}} + E_{\text{G}}$	gaseous planetoid

Figure 8.6 shows some $M(\rho, T)$ equilibrium curves of gravitating homogeneous sphere whose molecules are arranged on a HCP/FCC lattice, which is able to represent the most compact sphere lattice at high density. At low density, on the left of the diagram, the equilibrium is principally fixed by the attractive part of molecules and their temperature, and the exact lattice structure is irrelevant. This is the domain of uncondensed molecular gas.

Figure 8.6.: Virial equilibrium of gravitating Lennard-Jones homogeneous isothermal spheres with H_2 molecules arranged on a HCP/FCC lattice. The sphere mass as a function of density is plotted for temperatures ranging from $\tau \equiv T/T_{\max} = 10^{-2}$ to 10^2 . Below dotted line: comets; right to dashed line: rocky planetoids.

On the right, there is an accumulation curve at approximately $\rho \approx 100 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ representing purely condensed H_2 bodies mainly balancing gravity with the repulsive part of the molecular interaction. The area between the dashed line, connecting the minimum of the isotherms with $T > T_{\max}$, and the accumulation curve is the domain of rocky planetoids.

Low gravity:
Molecular gas
Comets

High gravity:
Rocky and gaseous
planetoids

At temperatures below $T_{\max} = 626.8 \text{ K}$, the equilibrium curves plunge to arbitrarily small masses along two regimes: the left vertical asymptotes represent the limit gaseous bodies, and the right asymptotes the condensed (solid or liquid) bodies called comets. The area of the comets lies between the dotted line, connecting the elbows of the isotherms with $T < T_{\max}$, and the dashed line.

At high temperature and low density, to the left of both the dotted and dashed line and above the isotherm lines, lie the gaseous planetoids. These bodies' equilibrium is fixed principally by gravity and temperature.

Of course real astrophysical bodies are not homogeneous, in practice in the small mass regime one can expect bodies made of a mixture of condensed state in the core surrounded by a less dense gaseous atmosphere, which could be calculated by solving the hydrostatic equilibrium, see Pfenninger (2004), where some models of isothermal bodies made of H_2 containing a solid core and a gaseous atmosphere have been discussed.

8.3 DYNAMICAL FRICTION

When discussing gravitational collapses, the concept of dynamical friction (Chandrasekhar 1943) is important, since heavy objects may condensate from the gas and start to precipitate, i.e., move with respect to the gas in the local gravity field. Considering a uniform density and Maxwellian velocity distribution, the dynamical friction of an heavy object of mass m_h reads:

Gas precipitation

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}_h}{dt} = -\frac{4\pi G^2 m_h \rho \log(\Lambda)}{v_h^3} \left[\operatorname{erf}(X) - \frac{2X}{\sqrt{\pi}} \exp(-X^2) \right] \mathbf{v}_h. \quad (8.32)$$

$\log(\Lambda)$ is the Coulomb logarithm and $X = v_h / \sqrt{2\sigma_v}$. For the qualitative analysis needed in this work it is enough to state:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}_h}{dt} \propto -m_h. \quad (8.33)$$

This can be used in different cases. First, He is twice as heavy as H₂ and can therefore be considered a heavy object and lead in some conditions to sediment faster than H₂. Secondly, when H₂ is in a phase transition, H₂ ice grains may sediment faster than He.

Grain sedimentation

Part III

SIMULATIONS

The following chapters present the numerical code and the simulations performed. §9 introduces the molecular dynamics code LAMMPS, its use in the current work and the super-molecule concept used in order to combine the inter-molecular Lennard-Jones and the gravitational potential. §10 describes several test simulations performed to ensure the correct use of LAMMPS. §11 explains the one-component simulations done and shows the simulation results. §12 describes the two-component simulations and their results.

§9 has been published in FP2015a and in a shortened version in FP2015b. §10.2 onwards and §11 has been published in FP2015a. §12 has been published in FP2015b.

METHOD

For all simulations, the Large-Scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) is used (Plimpton 1995). The LAMMPS software is a state of the art and widely used single and multi-processor code in chemistry, material sciences, and related fields. Its abilities to quickly compute short and long-range forces and the possibility to use a multi-timescale integrator make it a suitable tool to perform our simulations.

9.1 MOLECULAR DYNAMICS

9.1.1 *Potential solver*

The LAMMPS code has a wide range of force fields. For the simulations in this article we use only the LJ and self-gravitational potentials.

Neighbour list

Since the straight calculation cost for exact pairwise interactions is $O(N^2)$, approximate but still accurate methods are implemented that make the calculations possible at a much lower cost. A cut-off radius r_c is used for the short-range forces. As the attractive part of the LJ potential drops with r^{-6} , it is calculated only for neighbour particles within r_c . The neighbours for each particle are found using a Verlet neighbour list. This list is created with a radius of $r_n = r_c + r_s$, r_s being an extra skin distance to avoid the recalculation of the Verlet list at every time-step. This cut-off method is $O(N)$ and therefore linearly scales with the number of particles.

As LAMMPS is designed for the simulation of chemical substances not far from terrestrial conditions, and self-gravity is too weak to be of any influence, no specific self-gravity module is provided. For that reason, a tweak is used by using the Coulomb's potential module for an electric field,

$$\Phi_C = \frac{Cq_iq_j}{\epsilon r}, \quad (9.1)$$

where C is the interaction constant, ϵ the dielectric constant, and $q_{i,j}$ the charges of the molecules. As C is fixed in LAMMPS, to correctly calculate the gravitational potential we set the constants as follows:

Coulomb to gravity

$$\epsilon = -1, \quad (9.2)$$

$$q_i = \sqrt{\frac{G}{C}} m_i. \quad (9.3)$$

The gravitational potential drops with r^{-1} so the long range interactions cannot be ignored. It is calculated using the Particle³-Mesh (P³M) method

(Hockney & Eastwood 1981). The gravitational potential is split in short-range and long-range parts in Fourier space (Ewald 1921):

$$\hat{\Phi} = \hat{\Phi}_{\text{SR}} (1 - \exp(-k^2 r_s^2)) + \hat{\Phi}_{\text{LR}} \exp(-k^2 r_s^2), \quad (9.4)$$

P³M method

where r_s is the splitting distance. The potential Φ_{SR} is calculated at the same time as the LJ potential, using the same Verlet list. The potential Φ_{LR} is calculated in Fourier space using a fast Fourier transform (FFT).

Isolated system

The gravitational solver in Fourier space naturally assumes periodic boundary conditions in all three dimensions. Thus in order to use Fourier space for isolated systems, either the gravitational potential has to be adapted (James 1977) or the zero-padding trick has to be used (Hockney & Eastwood 1981). There is no standard option for an isolated system in all three dimensions in LAMMPS in Fourier space, but the zero-padding trick can be easily implemented by placing all particles within one eighth of the simulation domain and prevent them to leave this area, for example by mirror walls or a reflecting sphere available in LAMMPS). This means, however, that the mesh of an isolated system is eight times larger than for a periodic system for the same spacial resolution.

Zero padding

Multilevel Summation

There is an alternative method available in LAMMPS to calculate the long-range forces, called the multilevel summation method (MSM) and explained by Hardy (2006); Hardy et al. (2009). An advantage of the multilevel summation method is that it can be used for periodic and isolated boundary conditions. The basic idea can be seen in Figs. 9.1 and 9.2: The potential is split in a short-range part which is calculated directly and several long-range parts which are interpolated over a grid. The spacing of the grid becomes larger for longer distances. The method scales as $O(N)$ but is slower than the FFT calculations if the number of cores is smaller than ~ 500 , which is why it was only used in some test simulations.

Slower for few cores

9.1.2 *Time integration*

The time integration is done using the symplectic leapfrog scheme. The drift and kick operators,

$$D(\Delta t) \equiv x(t + \Delta t) = x(t) + \Delta t \dot{x}(t), \quad (9.5)$$

$$K(\Delta t) \equiv \dot{x}(t + \Delta t) = \dot{x}(t) + \Delta t \ddot{x}(t), \quad (9.6)$$

are applied according to the sequence $K\left(\frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) D(\Delta t) K\left(\frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)$ at each elementary time-step. For short-range force, the time-step is constant throughout the simulation and set as $10^{-2} - 10^{-3}$, which is the typical interaction timescale during nearest-neighbour molecular interactions. This is reasonable since the

Figure 9.1.: MSM essential ideas: splitting the Coulomb interaction potential and interpolating the longer range parts from nested grids.
Credit: NIH Resource for Macromolecular Modeling and Bioinformatics (<http://www.ks.uiuc.edu>)

Figure 9.2.: Algorithmic steps for MSM.
Credit: NIH Resource for Macromolecular Modeling and Bioinformatics (<http://www.ks.uiuc.edu>)

repulsive interaction and the finite kinetic energy prevent strongly varying accelerations between particles.

Small changes of individual particle positions can significantly change the short-range forces, which is why a very small time-step is required. But these small changes have almost no influence on long-range forces. For this reason, there is no need to calculate the long-range forces at every time-step.

Large time-step for long-range forces

In regard to short-range calculations, long-range calculations are an order of magnitude more costly per step but always need the same amount of calculation time: creation of the density-map with a fifth order interpolation procedure, a FFT solution of the potential, and the same interpolation procedure for finding the accelerations.

With the reversible reference system propagator algorithm (rRESPA), a multiple timescale integrator is available for LAMMPS that enables us to reduce the number of long-range force calculation (Tuckerman et al. 1992). It enables time integration in up to four hierarchical levels, but only two are needed for the simulations we present. The rRESPA time-integration-scheme looks as follows:

$$K_{\text{LR}}\left(\frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\left[K_{\text{SR}}\left(\frac{\Delta t}{2n_{\text{SR}}}\right)D\left(\frac{\Delta t}{n_{\text{SR}}}\right)K_{\text{SR}}\left(\frac{\Delta t}{2n_{\text{SR}}}\right)\right]^{n_{\text{SR}}}K_{\text{LR}}\left(\frac{\Delta t}{2}\right), \quad (9.7)$$

rRESPA scheme

where n_{SR} is the number of short-range iterations and set as 10 – 100, K_{LR} is the kick operator using the long-range (FFT) accelerations, and K_{SR} the kick operator using the short-range accelerations.

9.1.3 Super-molecules

The maximum number of particles that can be simulated on today's super-computers is of the order of $10^9 - 10^{10}$ particles. Even using such a huge number of molecules would only result in a fluid with a total mass of a few femtograms. It is obvious that gravity has no effect on this kind of fluid. For that reason, the concept of super-molecules is introduced. This concept is well established in galactic dynamics simulation, where super-stars weigh typically $10^4 - 10^6 M_{\odot}$, and in cosmology where super-WIMPS may weigh as much as $\sim 10^{67} \text{ GeV}c^{-2}$ particles. Two-body relaxation or diffusion due to the low number of super-particles is negligible, provided the simulation time is not too large, depending on the specific problem. Practice has shown that this kind of an approximation is valid in galactic dynamics for instance if the simulation length is of order 100 dynamical times (Binney & Tremaine 2008).

Need for high total mass

The basic principle of the concept is that each super-molecule consists of η molecules, and its mass is therefore,

$$m_{\text{SM}} = \eta m_{\text{M}}. \quad (9.8)$$

Super-molecule mass

To have the same properties of a super-molecule fluid as for a normal fluid, every term of the virial Equ. (8.17) has to be transformed such that the ratios of the terms are invariant. The kinetic energy term reads

$$2E_{\text{kin}} = N_{\text{M}}m_{\text{M}}\langle v_{\text{M}}^2 \rangle = N_{\text{SM}}m_{\text{SM}}\langle v_{\text{SM}}^2 \rangle. \quad (9.9)$$

Since the total mass is constant, $N_M m_M = N_{SM} m_{SM}$, the velocity dispersion of molecules and super-molecules is also the same,

*Super-molecule
velocity*

$$\langle v_{SM}^2 \rangle = \langle v_M^2 \rangle . \quad (9.10)$$

From the two LJ terms, Equ. (8.19–8.20) remain the same if

$$\frac{\epsilon_M \sigma_M^{12}}{m_M^5} = \frac{\epsilon_{SM} \sigma_{SM}^{12}}{m_{SM}^5} , \quad (9.11)$$

$$\frac{\epsilon_M \sigma_M^6}{m_M^3} = \frac{\epsilon_{SM} \sigma_{SM}^6}{m_{SM}^3} . \quad (9.12)$$

Solving these two equations and using Equ. (9.8), we derive

*Super-molecule
Lennard-Jones
constants*

$$\epsilon_{SM} = \eta \epsilon_M , \quad (9.13)$$

$$\sigma_{SM} = \sqrt[3]{\eta} \sigma_M . \quad (9.14)$$

The gravitational energy Equ. (8.21) does not change since it does not depend on super-molecule properties. The gravitational constant, described in molecular dynamics units ($\sigma = \epsilon = m = 1$) is

$$G_{SM} = \frac{G m^2}{\sigma \epsilon} \eta^{2/3} . \quad (9.15)$$

It is important to ensure that the gravitational force between two super-molecules remains small compared to the corresponding LJ force within the short-range force cut-off radius. This is assured by setting $F_G(r_c) \ll F_{LJ}(r_c)$ with r_c being the cut-off radius. This leads to the following constraint:

*Super-molecule
constraint*

$$\eta^{2/3} \ll \frac{24 \epsilon_M \sigma_M}{G m_M^2} (r_{c,SM}^{-5} - 2 r_{c,SM}^{-11}) , \quad (9.16)$$

where $r_{c,SM} = (r_c / \sigma_{SM})$. Using a cut-off radius of $r_c = 4 \sigma$ and hydrogen super-molecules, we find a maximum super-molecule mass equal to $5.7 \cdot 10^{-6} M_\oplus$, meaning at least $1.7 \cdot 10^5$ particles are required for simulating an Earth-mass, virialized, H₂-condensed body.

9.1.4 Ice clump detection

The LJ potential has its minimum at $r_m = 2^{1/6} \sigma$. If an ice clump is at absolute zero temperature, all bound molecules would have this distance from at least one other molecule. But, as the molecules in a clump are vibrating, the maximum binding distance between two molecules is generally larger than r_m .

The simplest clump consists of two molecules. Their mean kinetic energy as a function of the maximum displacement can be calculated numerically (Fig. 9.3).

The mean kinetic energy rises up to the maximum value of $r_{\sigma, \max} = 1.3625$, after which it drops again. It can be assumed that all stable clumps have a

Figure 9.3.: Mean kinetic energy as a function of the maximum displacement in an ice clump.

binding distance below this value. The distance constraint for two molecules to be bound is therefore:

$$r_{\sigma} \leq r_{\sigma, \text{max}} . \quad (9.17)$$

Ice clump distance constraint

Using $r_{\sigma, \text{max}}$ as the threshold distance, LAMMPS provides a list of clumps at fixed time intervals.

9.2 UNITS

A fluid is defined by the number of super-molecules N_{SM} , the initial velocity distribution (temperature), the number density, and the strength of the gravitational potential. All simulation properties are molecule-independent, the initial temperature and density are measured as a factor of the critical values T_{cr} and n_{cr} . The gravitational potential is measured either as a factor of the ideal-gas Jeans gravity G_{J} in the case of a single component fluid or as a factor of the ideal-gas Jeans-like gravity G_{GZ} in the case of a fluid mixture:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{\text{J}} &= \frac{G}{G_{\text{J}}} , \\ G_{\text{J}} &= \frac{\pi \gamma k_{\text{B}} T}{L^2 \sum_i n_i m_i^2} , \end{aligned} \quad (9.18)$$

Gravity strength

with the box side $L = (N_{\text{SM}}/n)^{1/3}$. The above formulation is correct for both single-component fluids and binary fluid mixtures. It is interesting to note that G_{J} is proportional to temperature and inversely proportional to density.

In simulations of binary fluids, the Lennard-Jones constant differences between the two components θ and ν the mass difference μ , the molecular fraction x_{α} and the strength of the gravitational potential are set in accordance to laboratory H_2 and He values:

$$\theta = \frac{T_{\text{c,He}}}{T_{\text{c,H}_2}} = 0.157 , \quad (9.19)$$

$$\nu = \frac{n_{\text{c,He}}}{n_{\text{c,H}_2}} = 1.12 , \quad (9.20)$$

$$\mu = \frac{m_{\text{He}}}{m_{\text{H}_2}} = 2 . \quad (9.21)$$

The time unit is defined as the average time of a particle crossing the box:

$$\text{Crossing time} \quad \tau = \frac{L}{V} \quad (9.22)$$

with $V^2 = \sum_i v_{xi}^2 / N$ and L the box length. Since $m_M V^2 = 3 k_B T$, τ becomes larger when m_M increases at constant T .

9.3 PLANE PERTURBATION

*Sinusoidal velocity
perturbation*

To illustrate the behaviour of a homogeneous fluid perturbed by a plane sinusoidal wave, a velocity perturbation in the x direction is introduced with wavelength λ equal to the box side L . Starting with a Maxwellian distribution v_i of velocities for the homogeneous unperturbed case, the x -component of the velocities is perturbed in such a way as to conserve energy. The perturbed x -velocity component for each particle i reads,

$$v'_{xi} = \alpha [v_{xi} + \beta V \sin(\omega x_i)] , \quad (9.23)$$

with $\omega = 2\pi/L$. The correction factor $\alpha \leq 1$ is used to keep the same kinetic energy in the x direction, with

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{\sum_i v_{xi}^2}{\sum_i [v_{xi} + \beta V \sin(\omega x_i)]^2} . \quad (9.24)$$

β determines the strength of the perturbation, but is supposed to be small enough to be in the linear regime of perturbations. In the present simulations, $\beta = 0.01$.

9.4 VISUALIZATION

Slice view

In order to visualize the snapshots, two dimensional number density maps will be used. When showing all N super-molecules, smaller aggregates will be washed-out and barely visible, which is why only a slice of the whole simulation box will be shown. Figure 9.4 shows how this slice is selected: The highest number density is sought in the x -direction, from there $N_{\text{slice}} = f_{\text{slice}} N$ super-molecules are selected. In that way, Δx differs for every snapshot, but N_{slice} is always the same number.

*Logarithmic color
map*

The number density n and number fraction x_α are represented by brightness and color. As at low density, the brightness is maximum and the color is simply white, the color map is best visualized in polar coordinates with n being the radius and x_α the angle. Figure 9.5 shows the color map used, for better contrasts, the brightness is displayed in a logarithmic scale.

Figure 9.4.: 2D density map of 3D space.

Figure 9.5.: Color mapping of density map.

10

TEST SIMULATIONS

10.1 GRAVITATIONAL SOLVER

Some initial test simulations were run in order to ensure the gravitational solver using the coulomb-solver of LAMMPS is functioning as wanted.

10.1.1 *Kepler orbit*

Figure 10.1.: Kepler orbits of Fourier space solver. Black line: direct calculation, blue line: 32^3 mesh, red line: 64^3 mesh, yellow line: 128^3 mesh.

*Direct summation,
FFT and MSM*

The first test simulations is a Kepler orbit of two bodies, one massive and one with negligible mass. The gravitational constant, total mass, and distance between the two bodies is set to 1. Ten orbits are simulated with 100 timesteps per full orbit. The simulation is performed using direct calculation, Fourier space potential solver and multilevel summation solver with different mesh sizes.

Figure 10.1 shows the orbits for the Fourier space potentials, one can identify that the orbits become more precise with increase mesh size. The opposite is the case for the multilevel summation solver as can be seen in Fig. 10.2, the orbits are excellent for all mesh sizes except 128^3 , which slowly spirals inwards. This disturbing fact can be partially explained that by increasing

Figure 10.2.: Kepler orbits of multilevel summation solver. Black line: direct calculation, blue line: 32^3 mesh, red line: 64^3 mesh, yellow line: 128^3 mesh.

the mesh-size, the number of summation needed increases also, introducing small errors. Nevertheless, the fact that the orbits get worse by increasing the mesh size is just another reason (together with being way slower than the Fourier space solver) why the multilevel summation solver was not trusted nor used for any simulations to be published.

MSM: Decreasing quality with increasing mesh size

10.1.2 Direct, Fourier space and multilevel summation comparison

Systems with a number of super-molecules small enough to be able to be simulated using direct calculations are compared between direct summation, Fourier space and multilevel summation in this section. Even though the simulations cannot be used to understand physical systems as Equ. (9.16) is not fulfilled, the error by overemphasising the gravitational force should be the same independent of the method. Both periodic systems and isolated systems were compared.

Periodic system

A fluid with an initial temperature, density and mass equal to 1 and a gravitational constant of 0.16 in Lennard-Jones units is simulated with $N = 4096$ super-molecules with periodic boundary conditions. The same simulation is run three times with the same random seed for direct summation, in Fourier space and using multilevel summation. The two mesh simulations use 16^3 mesh cells.

Figure 10.3.: Temperature (a) and number of bound molecules (b) time evolution of the periodic boundary conditions gravity solver test. Black: direct summation, blue: Fourier space, red: multilevel summation

Figure 10.3 shows the temperature and number of bound molecule evolution of the three simulations. The temperatures evolution is in good agreement. The number of bound molecules is very similar for the two mesh simulations, but is clearly higher for the direct summation. One has to remember that the mesh-size is very small with only 16^3 cells, and that mesh methods have an automatically smoothing, reducing the inter-molecular gravitational forces.

Bound molecules:
Direct > mesh

The Fourier space simulation is the fastest, followed by the multilevel summation which is already 7 times slower, whereas the direct summation was 920 times slower. The long simulation time of the direct calculation is to be expected, but the much slower multilevel summation time does not encourage its use considering the fact that it is not more precise.

Isolated system

A fluid with an initial temperature, density and mass equal to 1 and a gravitational constant of $1/64$ in Lennard-Jones units is simulated with $N = 17074$ super-molecules with periodic boundary conditions. The same simulation is run three times with the same random seed for direct summation, in Fourier space and using multilevel summation. The two mesh simulations use 32^3 mesh cells.

Figure 10.4 shows the temperature and number of bound molecule evolution of the three simulations. There is good agreements between all three

Figure 10.4.: Temperature (a) and number of bound molecules (b) time evolution of the periodic boundary conditions gravity solver test. Black: direct summation, blue: Fourier space, red: multilevel summation

simulations, showing that the super-molecule concept yields good results if the gravitational forces are low compared to the Lennard-Jones ones in intermolecular interactions. It also shows that the zero-padding trick is working for simulating isolated systems using Fourier space with LAMMPS. Figure 10.5 shows snapshots and comet-size distribution of the direct calculation simulation.

The Fourier space and the multilevel summation simulations have almost the same time, whereas the direct calculation takes almost 700 times longer. It is interesting that the two mesh-simulations have the same speed, given that the Fourier space simulation has 8 times more mesh-cells to calculate due to the zero-padding trick. When simulating isolated systems, the use of the multilevel summation is thus a serious alternative.

Bound molecules:
Direct = mesh

10.2 SUPER-MOLECULE CONCEPT TESTS

10.2.1 Potential energy

A fluid in a cubic box with periodic boundary conditions and initial constant density of $n = 0.006 n_{cr}$ is simulated with LAMMPS. Three different initial Maxwellian velocity distributions with temperature $T = 1.5, 3.0$ and $6.0 T_{cr}$, and a number of particles from $N_{SM} = 30^3 - 200^3$ are used. Table 10.1 shows the parameters of the different simulations.

Figure 10.5.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of the isolated system gravity solver test with direct summation. The slice shows in depth 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function.
 $\tau = \sigma \sqrt{\epsilon/m}$.

Table 10.1.: Parameters of the super-molecule test simulations.

Name	n/n_{cr}	T/T_{cr}	N_{SM}
SM15	0.006	1.5	$4^3 - 200^3$
SM30	0.006	3.0	$4^3 - 200^3$
SM60	0.006	6.0	$4^3 - 200^3$
SM04	0.1	0.4	$25^3 - 200^3$
SM06	0.1	0.4	$25^3 - 200^3$
SF ^a	0.1	0.1	$50^3 - 160^3$

Notes: All simulations are without gravity and use the basic KDK time integration scheme.

^a External gravity $a = 0.1 (L/\tau^2)$

Figure 10.6.: LJ potential energy as a function of the number of super-molecules at $t = 1\tau$ of simulations SM15 (black), SM30 (red) and SM60 (blue).

Figure 10.6 shows the LJ potential energy of those three fluids with respect to the number of super-molecules. One can see fluctuations in the simulations with low N_{SM} , but the result becomes reasonable when $N_{\text{SM}} > 10^4$ and a satisfactory convergence is obtained if $N_{\text{SM}} > 10^5$. Therefore all the subsequent simulations are performed with $N_{\text{SM}} > 10^5$.

Good convergence for $N_{\text{SM}} > 10^5$

10.2.2 Cluster percentage

High density, low temperature fluids are simulated during 5τ at various number of super-molecules. These fluids will form comets and allow us to compare the final percentage of bound molecules. Table 10.1 shows the parameters of the different simulations.

Independent of super-molecule size

Figure 10.7 shows the fraction of bound molecules with respect to the number of super-molecules. All simulations reach the same percentage, independent of the number of super-molecules.

Figure 10.7.: Fraction of bound molecules as a function of the number of super-molecules at $t = 5\tau$ of simulations SM04 (black) and SM06 (red).

Figure 10.8.: z -Coordinate of the centre of mass of comets as a function of time of the SF simulation. $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$ (black), 64^3 (yellow), 80^3 (green), 100^3 (blue), 128^3 (red) and 160^3 (magenta).

10.2.3 Precipitation in an external field

An external acceleration is applied in the $-z$ direction to a fluid within a box with reflecting boundary conditions. The fluid is very cold and rather dense (see Table 10.1) and is therefore forming ice grains, or comets. Because of acceleration and Archimedes's principle, the comets fall to the bottom and stay there, similar to snowfall on Earth.

The purpose of this simulation is to test the timescaling of the precipitation as function of the number of particles. Figure 10.8 shows the z -coordinate of the centre of mass of comets as a function of time. The curves are very similar, with a slight over-estimation of the collapse time for the smallest simulation. Therefore the precipitation phenomenon timescale is not strongly dependent on the mass resolution.

No mass resolution
dependence

SINGLE COMPONENT SIMULATIONS

11.1 ONE-PHASE FLUID

To study the reaction of a pure one-phase ideal-gas fluid far from the phase transition but with the above plane-wave perturbation, the initial temperature is taken above the critical value ($T_0 = 1.25 T_{\text{cr}}$) and the initial density well below the critical value ($n_0 = 10^{-2} n_{\text{cr}}$). Three different cases are studied: without gravity, weakly self-gravitating below the classical ideal-gas Jeans criterion with $\gamma_J = 0.5$, and sufficiently self-gravitating above the ideal-gas Jeans criterion with $\gamma_J = 1.25$. The simulations are performed with N_{SM} ranging from 50^3 to 160^3 . Table 11.1 shows the parameters of the different simulations.

Table 11.1.: Parameters of the one-phase fluid simulations.

Name	n/n_{cr}	T/T_{cr}	N_{SM}	γ_J
OP0	10^{-2}	1.25	100^3	0
OPGw	10^{-2}	1.25	100^3	0.5
OPGs	10^{-2}	1.25	$50^3 - 160^3$	1.25

Notes: OP0 without gravity and using the KDK time integration scheme. All gravitational simulations use the P³M gravitational solver and the rRESPA time scheme.

11.1.1 Time evolution

As the simulations conserve total energy, the formation of comets, implying a decrease of potential energy, can be measured by the mean temperature (i.e., kinetic energy) of the system. This is equivalent to the release of latent heat when a gaseous fluid condenses.

Figures 11.1 (a) and (b) display the temperature and the comet percentage evolutions of the one-phase fluid simulations: OP0 without gravity and $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$ super-molecules and the sufficiently self-gravitating fluid OPGs with N_{SM} ranging from 50^3 to 160^3 . The weakly self-gravitating fluid of simulation OPGw is not shown since it is identical to the no gravity case OP0.

For the fluid without gravity OP0 and the weakly self-gravitating fluid OPGw, no particular effect is observed. The percentage of comets rises to $\lesssim 2\%$, which can be attributed to the initial fluctuations in the distribution. The small perturbation introduced in the x -direction does not change the nature of the fluid; its temperature and comet percentage remains the same.

Below Jeans:
Identical to no
gravity

Figure 11.1.: Temperature (a, b) and fraction of bound molecules (c) in comets of the one-phase fluid simulations OP0 (dotted line) and OPGs as a function of time. (a, c): $N_{SM} = 50^3$ (black), 64^3 (yellow), 80^3 (green), 100^3 (blue), 128^3 (red) and 160^3 (magenta). (b): $N_{SM} = 100^3$ with four different random seeds.

Above Jeans:
Exponential growth

The sufficiently self-gravitating OPGs fluids, on the other hand, do change. Their temperatures and cluster percentages are rising steeply showing a substantial latent heat release. All simulations reach the same asymptotic temperature $\sim 6T_{cr}$, but different initial conditions (i.e., random seeds) yield slightly different behaviours during the collapse. This can also be observed in Fig. 11.1 (c) where four identical parameter simulations but different random seeds are run with $N_{SM} = 100^3$, leading to a time difference of $\sim 0.5\tau$ for reaching the asymptotic upper value.

Figure 11.2 (a) shows the density increase around the centre of the perturbation in the range $x = (0.5 \pm 0.05)L$ and compares them to the analytic solution for an ideal gas. The simulations follow the ideal-gas solution with a slight dispersion up to $t \approx 2.5\tau$, where a density rise is not possible anymore because of the repulsive LJ force; the density declines for a short while because of the collapse rebound down to a minimum at $t \approx 2.7\tau$. This density local minimum corresponds with the break in the temperature increase visible in Fig. 11.1. Subsequently, the temperature growth is much slower.

Growth corresponds
to theoretical model

Figure 11.2 (b) shows the evolution of density in the simulations, and the predicted growth rate line for an ideal gas subject to Jeans' instability (§7.1). All curve slopes correspond initially to the predicted Jeans' growth rate. The initial steep growth and the small time delay are caused by the initial noise in the particle distribution. Thus, a certain time is needed for the perturbation to overcome the noise.

Figure 11.2.: Density at $x = (0.5 \pm 0.05)L$ (a) and evolution of perturbation density (b) of the one-phase fluids OP0 (dotted line) and OPGs as a function of time. $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$ (black), 64^3 (yellow), 80^3 (green), 100^3 (blue), 128^3 (red) and 160^3 (magenta). Bold line (a): analytic solution for ideal gas. Dashed line (b): analytic solution for ideal gas.

11.1.2 Comet size distribution

Figure 11.3 shows snapshots and the comet size distribution at different times where N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets and $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. During the temperature rise, the comets are distributed according to a power law,

$$\frac{d \log (f(N_{\text{comet}}))}{d \log (N_{\text{comet}})} = \xi_c \text{ for } M_{\text{comet}} \ll M_{\text{tot}}, \quad (11.1)$$

and no planetoid is formed. The power-law index is very steep at the beginning with $\xi_c \approx -10$, but quickly decreases as it reaches a value of $\xi_c \approx -2.5$ at the end.

After the temperature increase break at $t \approx 2.7\tau$, the power-law distribution remains for small comets, but one bigger gaseous planetoid with over 1% of the total mass forms. It is shown in Fig. 11.4. The spherical body seen at $t \leq 3\tau$ in the snapshots is uncondensed gas, which is why it does not figure in the comet mass distribution (see §9.1.4 for a discussion how condensed matter is identified).

A second power law:

$$\frac{d \log (f(N_{\text{comet}}))}{d \log (N_{\text{comet}})} = \xi_p \text{ for } M_{\text{comet}} \gg M_{\text{SM}} \quad (11.2)$$

*Power law for
small bodies*

*Power law for
large bodies*

Figure 11.3.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of the simulation OPGs with $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$. The slice shows 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function.

Figure 11.4.: 3D-view of simulation OPGs with $N_{SM} = 100^3$ at $t = 4\tau$.

on the right side of the diagram describes the comets and planetoids. Each body occurs typically only once with our limited N_{SM} , and $\xi_p = 1$. Equation (11.1) describes the mass distribution of small bodies where gravity is negligible whereas Equ. (11.2) describes large bodies where gravity is weak, but cannot be neglected.

The first high-density plane is created thanks to the plane perturbation parallel to the yz -plane at $x = 0.5$. One can observe in Fig. 11.3 at $t = 2\tau$ that two filaments form, along the y - and z - axes, connecting the planetoid with itself thanks to the periodic boundary conditions. They are aligned with the mesh, but not primarily due to grid effects, but because these lines are the shortest distance between the planetoid and its periodic images. As can be seen in Fig. 11.18, diagonal filaments are also possible using the second shortest distance.

Filaments

The position of the planetoid is, thanks to the plane-wave perturbation, situated in the $x = 0.5L$ plane, the y and z positions are random and depend on the initial condition and vary with every simulation as shown in Fig. 11.5.

Figure 11.6 shows the temperature distribution in the comets as function of mass. As the number of large comets with the same number of super-molecules is small or even one, no error bars can be seen for the larger comets and the gaseous planetoid.

The broad Maxwellian velocity distribution is seen for the unbound molecules ($M_{comet} = 10^{-6}$). The small comets (2 or more particles) clearly have a lower temperature and dispersion than the average temperature of the system. This is due to the fact that in order for two super-molecules to cluster

Figure 11.5.: Distribution of the y - and z -coordinates of planetoid centre of mass on a 10×10 grid; all OPGs simulations at $t = 2.5\tau$.

Figure 11.6.: Temperature distribution of unbound molecules and comets as a function of comet mass of OPGs with $N_{SM} = 100^3$ at $t = 4\tau$.

together, a third one is needed, and this takes away some of their kinetic energy. The larger a comet is, the closer its temperature is to the system average temperature. On longer formation time the planetoids temperature tends towards the system average temperature, as expected.

11.1.3 *Scaling*

Figure 11.7.: Mean temperature over four one-phase fluid simulations OPGs with different random seeds as a function of time. $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$ (black), 64^3 (yellow), 80^3 (green), 100^3 (blue), 128^3 (red) and 160^3 (magenta).

Figure 11.7 shows the mean temperature value over four simulations with different random seeds. One can see that the two smallest simulations with $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$ and 64^3 are starting to collapse earlier than the other simulations, which are very similar. This can be explained by the fact that these simulations have very low x_{GLJ} values (Equ. 9.16), 3.65 and $4.03 r_\sigma$. The first value is in fact lower than the cut-off radius of $4 r_\sigma$ and fails to satisfy Equ. (9.16), the other one just slightly above it. In these simulations, the gravitational forces are strong even in short-range intermolecular interactions, the simulations are therefore overemphasizing the gravitational effect.

Massive
super-molecules:
*Overemphasizing
gravity*

Figure 11.8 shows the comet mass distribution of all OPGs simulations. For small comets, the percentage for a same number of super-molecules is the same for all N_{SM} . For example, at $t = 5\tau$, all simulations have a fraction of $\sim 10^{-1}$ for comets consisting of two super-molecules. These small clumps should be called multimers as mentioned below. But, with increasing N_{SM} , the mass of a comet consisting of two super-molecules diminishes since $M_{2\text{SM}} = 2/N_{\text{SM}}$.

On the other hand, for large comets and the planetoid, the mass is invariant to N_{SM} . For example, the planetoid at $t = 5\tau$ has the same mass of $M_{\text{planetoid}} \approx 5 \cdot 10^{-2} M_{\text{tot}}$ for all N_{SM} .

The fact that the mass distributions are shifted to the left for larger N_{SM} is misleading, as shown in Fig. 11.9. Only the two largest simulations are shown, the simulation with $N_{\text{SM}} = 128^3$ is shown normally, but for the simulation with $N_{\text{SM}} = 160^3$ is downscaled to $160^3/2 \approx 128^3$, always two comet sizes are added together. As can be seen, when comparing the two simulation using the same scaling, the two mass distributions are in fact very similar.

*Planetoids
independent of
simulation size*

It is interesting to look at the turning point, defined as the point where the mass sum of the biggest comets is larger than the mass sum of smaller comets. This point is interesting as it is the first indicator of the creation of an aggregate of molecules that start to be influenced by gravity. Figure 11.10 shows the time and the mass of the turning point. One can see than the time

Figure 11.8.: Snapshot comet-size distribution sequence of all OPGs simulations with $N_{SM} = 50^3$ (black), 64^3 (yellow), 80^3 (green), 100^3 (blue), 128^3 (red), 160^3 (magenta). N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{comet})$ is the comet size distribution function.

Figure 11.9.: Snapshot comet-size distribution summation sequence of OPGs simulations. Reference with $N_{SM} = 128^3$ (black); sum of 4 comet sizes per star: 100^3 (red).

Figure 11.10.: Time (top) and size (bottom) of the largest comet at the appearance of the turning point.

of appearance is independent of N_{SM} . The comet mass, on the other hand, clearly follows a power law with:

$$\frac{M_{\text{comet}}}{M_{\text{tot}}} \approx 10N_{SM}^{\xi_N}, \quad (11.3)$$

with $\xi_N \approx -1$. Since $N_{SM} = M_{\text{tot}}/M_{SM}$, at turning point the number of super-molecules is always of order of 10. In other words, in critical conditions where the attractive molecular force adds up to gravity, the tendency to make a larger condensed body mass fraction already starts at about ten molecules.

Turning point

11.1.4 Extrapolation to physical scale

Figure 11.11.: Extrapolation of the comet mass distribution for a real H_2 molecular fluid at $t = 5\tau$. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function.

Having studied the scaling behaviour of the simulations, we can attempt to extrapolate some properties for a fluid consisting of real molecules instead of super-molecules. Considering H_2 molecules, the total mass of the OPGs simulations is $1.4 M_{\oplus}$, the box length equal to $2.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ AU and $\tau = 1.5 \cdot 10^2$ years.

*40 orders of
magnitude*

Thus, in realistic conditions there would be a total amount of $2.5 \cdot 10^{51}$ H_2 molecules, the number of molecules per super-molecule N_{comet} varying from $2.0 \cdot 10^{46}$ for $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$ to $3.2 \cdot 10^{44}$ for $N_{\text{SM}} = 160^3$. So, even for the largest simulations, there is a difference in number of particles of more than 40 orders of magnitude with real situations. For that reason, the extrapolated data has to be treated with caution. As long as no other physics enters in the interval of scales, this is however not extraordinary in regards to common practices in simulation works, such as simulating stars with SPH particles. While a single SPH particle can at best represent a mass fraction of $10^{-6} - 10^{-10}$ of the total, an SPH particle is supposed to behave as the smallest mass element in local thermal equilibrium, say a few 1000 protons over the stellar mass: $\sim 10^{-55}$, which lies therefore well over 10^{40} times the SPH simulation resolving capacity.

As can be observed in Fig. 11.1 (c), the fraction of bound molecules does not change when increasing the number of particles and will remain unchanged for a fluid consisting of molecules. The same is true for the size of the resulting planetoid, as can be seen in Fig. 11.8. Therefore, we can assume that after 5τ , the system will consist of $\sim 80\%$ unbound molecules and a planetoid with a mass of $\sim 0.07 M_{\oplus}$.

*Dimers and
multimers*

At $t = 5\tau$, there is a fraction of 10^{-1} of two molecules aggregates i.e. dimers with a mass of $6.6 \cdot 10^{-27}$ kg. These multi-molecules clumps should be called multimers instead of comets. As mentioned above the turning point occurs at $\sim 2.4\tau$ consistently for approximately 10 molecules, so its mass is about $20 m_{\text{H}} = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-26}$ kg.

Using the above values and the two power laws of Equ. (11.1 – 11.2), Fig. 11.11 shows a schematic diagram showing the mass distribution at $t = 5\tau$. While the mass fraction of the turning point multimers is tiny, the power-law distribution rapidly increases the mass in larger grain- and comet-sized bodies until they become a planetoid mass.

11.2 PHASE TRANSITION

Table 11.2.: Parameters of the phase transition simulations.

Name	n/n_{cr}	T/T_{cr}	N_{SM}	γ_{J}
<i>OPGs</i>	10^{-2}	1.25	$50^3 - 160^3$	0, 0.5, 1.25
PT1-1	10^{-1}	0.1	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT2-1	10^{-1}	0.2	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT3-1	10^{-1}	0.3	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT1-2	10^{-2}	0.1	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT2-2	10^{-2}	0.2	$50^3 - 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT3-2	10^{-2}	0.3	$50^3 - 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT5-2	10^{-2}	0.5	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT7-2	10^{-2}	0.7	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT9-2	10^{-2}	0.9	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT1-3	10^{-3}	0.1	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT2-3	10^{-3}	0.2	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$
PT3-3	10^{-3}	0.3	$50^3, 100^3$	0, 0.5, $G = G_{\text{OPGs}}$

Notes: All simulations in two different runs: without gravity and perturbation, using basic KDK time integration scheme, and with gravity and perturbation, using the P³M gravitational solver and the rRESPA time scheme.

We study several physical conditions close to a phase transition. Table 11.2 summarizes their properties. Three different densities, 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} and $10^{-3} n_{\text{cr}}$, and three different temperatures, 0.1, 0.2 and $0.3 T_{\text{cr}}$, are chosen. As the one-phase fluid studied in §11.1 also has a density of $10^{-2} n_{\text{cr}}$, three additional temperatures, 0.5, 0.7 and $0.9 T_{\text{cr}}$, were used for this density to make a link between the one-phase fluid and the fluids studied in this section.

Looking at the phase transition diagram (Fig. 11.12), all fluids with $T \leq 0.3 T_{\text{c}}$ are on the Maxwell line. Those with $\rho \leq 10^{-2} \rho_{\text{c}}$ are on the $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_{\text{s}} > 0$ part of the van der Waals phase diagram, which corresponds to metastable states on the verge of a deep phase transition. The fluids with $\rho = 10^{-1} \rho_{\text{c}}$ are on the $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_{\text{s}} \leq 0$ part of the van der Waals phase diagram, which corresponds to unstable states in a phase transition. The fluids with $T \geq 0.5 T_{\text{c}}$ are still in the stable regime.

Three different cases are studied: without gravity, strongly self-gravitating above the Jeans criterion, and weakly self-gravitating below the Jeans criterion.

Fluids on Maxwell line

Figure 11.12.: Position of the LJ simulations in a corresponding van der Waals phase diagram. Solid line: Maxwell construct for the van der Waals EOS; dotted line: van der Waals EOS. ★: fluid presenting a phase transition; ●: one-phase fluid.

11.2.1 Fluid without gravity

Figure 11.13.: Temperature as a function of time of non-gravitating fluids PT1-1 (black), PT1-2 (yellow), PT2-2 (green), PT2-3 (blue), PT3-2 (red) and PT5-2 (magenta). All simulations with $N_{SM} = 50^3$.

To study the evolution of fluids presenting a phase transition without gravity, the x_{GLJ} value does not have to be considered and the number of super-molecules is set to $N_{SM} = 50^3$. Figure 11.13 shows the temperature evolution of some of these fluids. In the beginning, the molecules merge into small comets, which leads to a decrease of the potential energy and therefore a rise of the temperature. Once the temperature is high enough, the kinetic and potential energy reach an equilibrium and the fluid remains stable.

The number of comets formed is dependent on the density and inversely dependent on the temperature. The higher the number of formed comets, the longer it takes for the fluid to reach a stable regime. For example, the very cold fluids PT1-2 and PT2-2 only reach an asymptotic value around $t \approx 100\tau$.

The comets remain at moderate size as can be seen in the snapshots and in their mass distribution (Fig. 11.14): The number of super-molecules per comets is $< 10^{-2} N_{SM}$. The mass distribution follows the power law of Equ. (11.1), but at $\sim 10^{-4}$, the mass distribution rises again, presenting a big number of comets between 10^{-4} to 10^{-2} super-molecules. Fig. 11.15 shows a close-up 3D view of a medium-sized comet and smaller aggregates.

Figure 11.16 shows the temperature distribution as a function of the comet mass. As in simulation OPGs, the temperature for small bodies lies below average, but reaches average value for more massive bodies.

Formation of
multimers and
comets

11.2.2 Self-gravitating fluid above Jeans criterion

All sufficiently self-gravitating simulations use the same gravitational potential, $G = 1.25 G_J$ ($T = 1.25 T_{cr}$, $n = 0.01 n_{cr}$). As the temperatures and densities differ, G_J and therefore γ_J is different for each simulation, but this parameter is always > 1 .

As $\gamma_J > 1$ for all simulated fluids, they are unstable if perturbed. The lower the initial temperature of a fluid, the bigger is γ_J , which translates to a faster exponential growth. This can be seen in Fig. 11.17 where the fluids with a

Figure 11.14.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of simulation PT2-2 with $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$, and without gravity. The slice shows 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function.

Figure 11.15.: Close-up 3D-view of a medium sized comet and smaller aggregates.

Figure 11.16.: Temperature distribution of unbound molecules and comets as a function of comet size of PT2-2^a without gravity and $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$ at $t = 100\tau$.

Figure 11.17.: Temperature as a function of time of sufficiently self-gravitating fluids OPGs (black); PT1-1 (yellow), PT1-3 (green), PT3-2 (blue), PT5-2 (red), PT7-2 (magenta) and PT9-2 (cyan). All simulations with $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$.

density of $10^{-2} n_{\text{cr}}$ are starting to collapse one after another, from the lowest to the highest temperature.

Formation of gaseous planetoids

The evolution of the fluids is identical to the fluid OPGs: an exponential rise of the temperature until it reaches a temperature break, after which the temperature rises only slowly and a single gaseous planetoid is formed. Figure 11.18 shows snapshots and comet mass distribution, again very similar to the fluid OPGs. First, there is a formation of small comets following the power law of Equ. (11.1), and then the comets are massive enough to attract each other and merge into one big spherical planetoid ($t > 1\tau$), following the power law of Equ. (11.2). The power-law index ξ_c also evolves in a similar fashion as in simulation OPGs, starting out very steep and reaching a final value of $\gtrsim -2$.

Figure 11.18.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of sufficiently self-gravitating simulation PT1-3 with $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$. The slice shows 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function.

Figure 11.19.: Temperature as a function of time of weakly self-gravitating fluids PT2-2 (black), PT3-2 (blue) and PT5-2 (red). Dotted line: $N_{\text{SM}} = 50^3$ and without gravity; dashed line: $\gamma_J = 0.5$ and $N_{\text{SM}} = 80^3$; solid line: $\gamma_J = 0.5$ and $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$.

11.2.3 Self-gravitating fluid below Jeans criterion

To compare weakly self-gravitating fluids in a phase transition (on the Maxwell line) with out-of-phase-transition fluids (below the Maxwell line), γ_J is set to 0.5 for all fluids. This means that the individual G value is different for each simulation.

As shown in §11.2.1, the perturbation of the weakly self-gravitating one-phase fluid OPGw does not create any effect if $\gamma_J < 1$. Figure 11.19 shows the temperature as a function of time of the self-gravitating fluids PT5-2, PT3-2, and PT2-2, and compares them to the non-gravitating fluids. The out-of-phase-transition fluid PT5-2 remains unchanged and does not differ from the non-gravitating fluid, identical to OPGw.

The temperatures of the fluids in a phase transition PT3-2 and PT2-2 are exponentially growing and differ clearly from the non-gravitating ones. In the beginning, the LJ forces dominate the gravitational forces and the fluids behave like non-gravitating fluids. PT2-2 reacts much faster than PT3-2, thanks to its low initial temperature and fluctuations due to the Maxwellian velocity distribution, and forms many small- and medium-sized comets (see §11.2.1). Once these comets are formed, their mass is high enough to attract each other with gravity, forming a single rocky planetoid.

This can be seen in the snapshots and comet mass distribution (Fig. 11.20). During the first 15τ , the fluid is identical to the low-temperature, non-gravitating fluid (compare to Fig. 11.14). Only then does gravity start to play a role, one can see the formation of a planetoid and how it swallows the small- and medium-sized comets during its growth.

With its higher temperature, PT3-2 forms almost no small- or medium-sized comets, which can be seen in the snapshots and comet mass distribution (Fig. 11.21) for the first $\approx 50\tau$. Only after 50τ does gravity show its effect with the appearance of a medium-sized comet, which is too massive to fit into the power law ξ_1 (see at $t = 50\tau$). From then on, this comet attracts super-molecules and thus grows in size until at $t \approx 125\tau$, a single big rocky planetoid is formed.

Formation of rocky planetoids

Time-scale $\geq 100\tau$

Figure 11.20.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of weakly self-gravitating simulation PT2-2 with $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$. The slice shows 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function.

Figure 11.21.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of weakly self-gravitating simulation PT3-2 with $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$. The slice shows 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function.

Figure 11.22.: Temperature distribution of unbound molecules and comets as a function of comet size of PT3-2 with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ and $N_{\text{SM}} = 100^3$ at $t = 200\tau$.

Figure 11.22 shows the temperature distribution as a function of the comet mass of PT3-2. The temperature of the comets containing few super-molecules lies below the average, but the planetoids temperature is the same as the average.

PT2-2, PT3-2 and PT5-2 all scale very well. The two fluids in a phase transition, PT2-2 and PT3-2, have an almost identical timescale for the exponential growth for $N_{\text{SM}} = 80^3$ and 100^3 . The slight difference is due to the initial random seed. As x_{GLJ} depends on γ_J and the temperature, both much lower than for OPGs, its value is clearly above the cut-off radius, which is 7.63 and 8.34 for PT2-2 and 7.03 and 7.69 for PT3-2.

PT5-2 shows no difference for any number of super-molecules, with N_{SM} ranging from 50^3 to 100^3 .

*Independent of
super-molecule size*

11.3 PLANETOID DENSITIES

Figure 11.23.: Density of planetoid as a function of the radius. Simulations OPGs (blue) with $N_{SM} = 100^3$ at $t = 4\tau$, the gaseous planetoid consists of 41559 super-molecules ($0.042 M_{tot}$). Simulation PT3-2 (red), with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ and $N_{SM} = 100^3$ at $t = 200\tau$; the rocky planetoid consists of 74208 super-molecules ($0.074 M_{tot}$). Solid lines: hydrogen, higher value: solid; lower value: liquid. Dotted line: ρ_f of Lagrange-Jacobi identity, higher value: SC; lower value: HCP/FCC.

Figure 11.23 shows the densities of the planetoids as a function the radius of the simulations OPGs and PT3-2 with $\gamma = 0.5\gamma_J$, and compares them to hydrogen laboratory data and values found in the Lagrange-Jacobi identity (§8.2).

The density of the OPGs gaseous planetoid is below that of a conventional solid or liquid. As their temperature is above the critical value ($T > 6 T_{cr}$), super-molecules are not able to condense without the aid of gravity, and because of their high kinetic energy, are vibrating at much higher amplitudes. This leads to more space between the super-molecules and therefore a lower density compared to super-molecules below the critical temperature.

Gaseous planetoids:
Continuous density
drop

The density of the gaseous planetoid drops with increasing radius and hence does not qualify as a homogeneous sphere, but its average density is below the ρ_f value of the Lagrange-Jacobi identity (Equ. 8.29), in accordance with Table 8.2 and Fig. 8.6 for gaseous planetoids.

Rocky planetoids:
Constant density

The density of the PT3-2 rocky planetoid lies between the liquid and solid phase. There is no continuous density drop as for the OPGs simulation, the density remains stable up to almost the outer radius and the body can be approximated as a homogeneous sphere. Its density lies above ρ_f in accordance with Table 8.2 and Fig. 8.6 for rocky planetoids.

We compare fluids with different number fractions by keeping the physical properties alike (constant $T/T_{c,\alpha}$ and $n/n_{c,\alpha}$). By decreasing x_α the mean mass per molecule m increases, since $m_\alpha < m_\beta$. It is therefore not possible to have the same number of molecules per super-molecule η , the same super-molecule mass $M_{SM} = m\eta$, and the same gravity $G_J \propto m^2\eta^{2/3}$ at the same time.

Different number fractions

Since we want to study the reaction of fluids with different x_α above and below the ideal gas Jeans criterion, we need to ensure that γ_J is > 1 or < 1 in the compared simulations. For that reason, neither the total mass nor the number of molecules remains the same when comparing fluids with different x_α while γ_J remains the same. Since $G \propto m^{-2}$ (Equ. 9.18) and $\eta^{2/3} \propto m^{-2}G$ (Equ. 9.15), then $\eta \propto m^{-6}$, and thus $M = m\eta \propto m^{-5}$. Therefore, changing m by a factor 2 leads to a total mass decrease of 32.

Different cases are studied, $T = 1.5T_{c,\alpha}$, $T = 1.5T_{c,\beta}$ and $T = (T_{CMB}/T_{H_2})T_{c,\alpha}$ with $n = 10^{-2}n_{c,\alpha}$ and $x_\alpha = 1, 0.75, 0.5, 0.25$ and 0. These initial parameters are shown in Fig. 8.2. In addition, different densities are used for simulations B75 and C75 in order to compare cases with $n > n_-$ with $n < n_-$ (see §8.2). We also study solar system abundances for different total masses and number densities. The simulations are summarized in Table 12.1.

12.1 ABOVE CRITICAL TEMPERATURES

In this section, we consider fluids where both T_α and T_β are above the critical temperature. The number densities corresponding to the different abundance number fractions can be seen in Fig. 8.2.

Time evolution

Figure 12.1a shows the temperature evolution of the A-simulations (see Table 12.1). In all simulations, the weakly self-gravitating fluids with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ and the fluids without gravity are very similar and do not react significantly to the velocity perturbation. On the other hand, as expected for the sufficiently self-gravitating fluids with $\gamma_J = 1.5$ the introduced perturbation rises exponentially.

Exponential growth

The reaction time is similar for all number fractions, but the mixtures reach slightly higher temperatures. Keeping in mind that all simulations have the same γ_J value, but the total mass differs with $M_1/M_2 = (m_1/m_2)^{-5}$.

To get a deeper understanding of the internal processes, we need to distinguish between the α - and β -component. Figure 12.1b shows the fraction of bound molecules in the simulations as a function of time. The β -molecules, being twice as heavy than the α -molecules are falling faster into the forming

More bound β -molecules than α

Table 12.1.: Parameters of the binary mixture simulations.

Name	x_α	n [$n_{c,\alpha}$] [m^{-3}] ^a	T [$T_{c,\alpha}$] [K] ^a	γ_i	N_{tot}	$M_{\text{tot}}/M_{\oplus}^{ab}$ g	L/R_{\oplus}^a f g	τ/kyrs^d f g
A10	1.0					0.34	27 47	0.86 1.5
A75	0.75					0.094 0.49	16 28	0.58 1.0
A50	0.5	10^{-2}	1.5	0, 0.5, 1.5	100^3	0.039 0.2	11 20	0.45 0.78
A25	0.25					0.019 0.1	8.6 15	0.36 0.64
A00	0.0					0.011 0.056	6.8 12	0.31 0.53
A75s		10^{-2}	1.5	1.5	$50^3 - 160^3$	0.49	18	1.0
A75 ₀₁	0.75	10^{-1}	9.3 · 10 ²⁶	0, 1.5	100^3	0.16	9	0.29
B10	1.0					0.021 0.11	11 18	0.86 1.5
B75	0.75					0.0059 0.031	6.5 11	0.58 1.0
B50	0.5	10^{-2}	0.24	0, 0.5, 1.5	80^3	0.0024 0.013	4.5 7.9	0.45 0.78
B25	0.25					0.0011 0.0063	3.4 5.9	0.36 0.63
B00	0.0					0.00068 0.0035	2.7 4.7	0.31 0.53
B75 _{γ}		10^{-2}	9.3 · 10 ²⁵	0.5 – 1.5	80^3	0.0059 – 0.031	6.5 – 11	0.58 – 1.0
B75 ₀₁	0.75	10^{-1}	9.3 · 10 ²⁶	0, 1.5		0.0097	3.6	0.32
C10	1.0					0.0043 0.022	6.3 11	1.5 0.86
C75	0.75					0.0012 0.0063	3.8 6.6	1.0 0.58
C50	0.5	10^{-2}	0.082	0, 0.5, 1.5	80^3	0.00049 0.0026	2.7 4.6	0.78 0.45
C25	0.25					0.00025 0.0013	2.0 3.5	0.63 0.36
C00	0.0					0.00014 0.00072	1.6 2.8	0.53 0.31
SSM ₀₁		10^{-1}	9.3 · 10 ²⁶	1.05		0.012 ^e	3.9	0.3
SSM ₀₂	0.84	10^{-2}	9.3 · 10 ²⁵	0.48	80^3	0.012 ^e	8.5	0.65
SSE ₀₄		10^{-4}	9.3 · 10 ²³	1.98		1.0	171	13

Notes: All simulations are initially perturbed by a small plane sinusoidal wave in the x -direction.

^(a) Considering $\alpha = \text{H}_2$ and $\beta = \text{He}$. ^(b) Mass independent for $\gamma_i = 0$. ^(c) $T = 1.5T_{c,\text{He}}$. ^(d) $T = T_{\text{GM}}^b$. ^(e) $M = M_{\text{Moon}}$. ^(f) $\gamma_i = 0.5$. ^(g) $\gamma_i = 1.5$.

Figure 12.1.: Temperature (a) and fraction of bound molecules (b) as a function of time of the simulations A10 (blue), A75 (cyan), A50 (black), A25 (yellow) and A00 (red).

(a): Solid line: $\gamma_J = 1.5$; dotted line: $\gamma_J = 0.5$ or 0.

(b): Solid line: both types, dashed line: α -component, dotted line: β -component.

planetoid. Indeed, even in A75, with only $x_\beta = 0.25$, the fraction of bound β -molecules surpasses the fraction of bound α -molecules for $\tau > 2$.

Planetoid formation

Figure 12.2 shows a time-sequence of snapshots and super-molecule comet-size distributions condensed as grains or comets. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets, $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. In the beginning with $t < 3\tau$, small comets of either α or β molecules form. At $t = 3\tau$, a planetoid with $N_{\text{comet}} \approx 0.1N_{\text{tot}}$ forms consisting of both components. One can already see a dominance of β -molecules, especially in the centre.

Beginning at $t = 3\tau$, and even more clearly at $t = 4\tau$, one can observe the formation of a big core consisting only of β -molecules (isolated β dot). In the snapshots this corresponds to the planetoid shown as a β -core surrounded by α -molecules.

Figure 12.3 (top) shows the planetoid density of simulation A75 as a function of radius. Even though the fluid consists of only 25% β -molecules, the planetoid consists mostly of β -molecules with $f_\beta = 0.86$. The α -molecules are only a small fraction and mostly present in the outer part. The gaseous nature of this body is visible as the density regularly decreases in radii.

Gaseous β -planetoid

Figure 12.2.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of the simulation A75 with $\gamma = 1.5$. The slice shows in depth 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. α : blue, β : red, both: black.

Figure 12.3.: Density of planetoid as a function of the radius of the simulations A75 and B75 with $\gamma_J = 1.5$ at $t = 5\tau$ and B75 with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ at $t = 30\tau$. α : blue, β : red, both: black.

Scaling

The scaling of simulations using super-molecules has already been discussed in the previous chapter. In order to obtain correct behaviour, the gravitational forces need to be small compared to the Lennard-Jones forces on intermolecular scales, i.e. $a_G(r_c) < a_{LJ}(r_c)$ with r_c being the cut-off radius (see Equ. 9.16). A turning point can be identified up to which $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ follows the power law $f(N_{\text{comet}}) \propto N_{\text{comet}}^{\xi_c}$ with negative index $\xi_c < -1$, whereas after the turning point $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ follows a second power law with index $\xi_p = 1$ (see Fig. 12.2). The appearance time of this turning point is independent of N_{tot} , whereas the size of the comet at the turning point scales as $N_{\text{comet}}/N_{\text{tot}} \approx 10 N_{\text{tot}}^{-1}$, thus $N_{\text{comet}} \approx 10$. This corresponds roughly to the smallest number of nearest neighbours in the condensed phase for which surface effects start to be dominated by volume effects.

Figure 12.4 shows the fraction of bound molecules as a function of time for all A75_S simulations with $N_{\text{tot}} = 50^3$ to 160^3 . As shown in the previous chapter, the slight time delay between the simulations can be attributed to the random seed. Anyway the asymptotic final value is physically more important, and is the same for all N_{tot} when considering both components. The final value of the β -molecules on the other hand is slightly declining with increasing N_{tot} as can be seen in Fig. 12.5. It follows the power law $N_B/N_{\text{tot}} \approx 0.213 N_{\text{tot}}^{-0.017}$ over the range $N_{\text{tot}} = 10^5 - 10^{6.5}$.

Turning point size:
Number of nearest
neighbours

Fraction of
 β -molecules:
Power law

Figure 12.4.: Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulation A75_S with $\gamma_J = 1.5$. $N_{\text{tot}} = 50^3$ (black), 64^3 (green), 80^3 (blue), 100^3 (yellow), 128^3 (red) and 160^3 (cyan). Solid line: both types, dashed line: α -component, dotted line: β -component.

Figure 12.5.: Fraction of bound β -molecules as a function of N_{tot} of simulation A75_S.

Extrapolation to physical scale

Segregation
overestimation

The simulations represent actually a H₂-He fluid mixture with $\sim 10^{50}$ molecules. Extrapolating the previous power law, we would find that $\sim 3\%$ of β -molecules settle inside the planetoid, instead of $\sim 15\%$. Thus the simulations overestimate species segregation, which was to be expected. Segregation effects should be treated with caution, as we are extrapolating values in a range less than two orders or magnitude 45 orders of magnitude away. Larger simulations should allow to better constraint the effective species segregation in realistic conditions.

12.2 BETWEEN CRITICAL TEMPERATURES

In this section, we consider fluids with $T_\alpha < T_{c,\alpha}$ and $T_\beta > T_{c,\beta}$ with different component fraction x_α . The number density n has been chosen in such a way that for the molecular fractions $x_\alpha > 0$, the α -component with number density $n_\alpha = x_\alpha \cdot n$ is in a phase transition.

Figure 12.6.: Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulations B10 (blue), B75 (cyan), B50 (black), B25 (yellow) and B00 (red) with $\gamma_J = 1.5$. Solid line: both types, dashed line: α -component, dotted line: β -component.

As the temperature of the B-simulations is an order of magnitude smaller than in the A-simulations, the same is the case for the gravitational potential (see Equ. 9.18). For that reason, it is sufficient to use $N_{\text{tot}} = 80^3$ for these simulations.

Above ideal gas Jeans criterion

Figure 12.6 shows the time evolution of the fraction of bound molecules of the B-simulations with $\gamma_J = 1.5$. One can see the similarity to Fig. 12.1b, but the fluids with a high x_α value are rising to higher values even before the perturbation is becoming dominant. This is because the α -part of the fluid is in a phase transition and small ice grains are forming even without the help of gravity.

The density at the core of the planetoid of simulation B75 is lower than the one of A75 as can be seen in Fig. 12.3 (middle), and shows a gaseous profile. This is explained by the fact that by keeping $\gamma_J = 1.5$, the value for G_J is lower for the B-simulations than for the A- ones as $G_J \propto T$ (see Equ. 9.18). Having a lower gravitational potential, the density at which the repulsive Lennard-Jones term and the attractive gravitational term are equal is lower.

The planetoid is still dominated by β -molecules, but there are more α -molecules than in the A75 simulation with $f_\alpha = 0.26$ and $f_\beta = 0.74$. As in the A-simulations, the core consists of gaseous He as is clearly visible in Fig. 12.7.

Below ideal gas Jeans criterion

As can be seen in Fig. 8.2, the α -component of the simulations B10, B75, B50 and B25 all lie on the Maxwell line and are thus in a phase transition,

Figure 12.7.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of the simulation B75 with $\gamma = 1.5$. The slice shows in depth 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. α : blue, β : red, both: black.

Figure 12.8.: Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulations B10 (blue), B75 (cyan), B50 (black), B25 (yellow) and B00 (red) with $\gamma_J = 0.5$. Solid line: both types, dashed line: α -component, dotted line: β -component.

which implies, according to Equ. (7.38), that they are gravitationally unstable even with $\gamma_J < 1$.

Figure 12.8 shows the evolution of fraction of bound molecules of the B-simulations with $\gamma_J = 0.5$. The time-scale is much larger (30τ instead of 5τ in the case of $\gamma_J = 1.5$), having a smaller gravitational potential, the long-range gravitational term is lower and therefore the creation of any potential comet or planetoid takes more time.

The one-component fluids, consisting of either uniquely α -molecules (B10) or β -molecules (B00) have already been studied in details in the previous chapter. The α -fluid B10 is unstable as it is in a phase transition, whereas the β -fluid B00 is stable as its temperature is above the critical one and no phase transition is possible.

The simulations of fluid mixtures B25, B50, B75 with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ are all unstable, even gravitationally. We can distinguish a clear difference to the simulations with $\gamma_J = 1.5$ in that only the α -molecules are forming clumps, the β -molecules remain in gaseous form. Even in the the simulation B25 with only 25% α -molecules, the comets and planetoid consist almost exclusively of α -molecules. This difference between $\gamma_J = 1.5$ and 0.5 can also be seen when comparing Fig. 12.9 with Fig. 12.7.

Figure 12.3 (bottom) shows the radius of the planetoid at $t = 30\tau$ of B75 with $\gamma = 0.5$. Comparing this with the planetoid of B75 with $\gamma = 1.5$ we see that the high-gravity one consists mostly of β -molecules in gas phase whereas the low-gravity one consists of mostly α -molecules in solid phase, surrounded by an atmosphere. Very few β -molecules have been trapped during the planetoid formation, providing an interesting example of a body forming with a distinct composition from the original medium, due to the initial phase transition state.

Only α -clumps

Rocky α -planetoid

Different γ_J values

The last sections show that a B-fluid above the ideal gas Jeans criterion, i.e. with $\gamma_J = 1.5$, is forming a gaseous planetoid consisting mostly of β -molecules. On the other hand, a B-fluid with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ forms a rocky planet-

Figure 12.9.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of the simulation B75 with $\gamma = 0.5$. The slice shows in depth 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. α : blue, β : red, both: black.

Figure 12.10.: Fraction of bound β -molecules as a function of time of the simulations $B75_\gamma$. Blue, from left to right: $\gamma_J = 1.5, 1.4, \dots, 1.1$; red: $\gamma_J = 1$; black, from left to right: $\gamma_J = 0.9, 0.8, \dots, 0.5$. The simulations are stopped once they reach asymptotic values.

oid, consisting almost exclusively of α -molecules. In this section, we vary γ_J from 0.5 to 1.5.

Figure 12.10 shows the fraction of bound β -molecules. It is rising steeply for fluids with $\gamma_J > 1$, in accordance to the ideal gas Jeans criterion and the formed planetoid is gaseous and consists mostly of β -molecules. The fluid with $\gamma_J = 1$ also produces a gaseous planetoid, but the percentage of β -molecules is already dropping a little. Interestingly, in the fluids with $0.7 \leq \gamma_J < 1$, the β -fraction is also rising. The instability criterion of Equ. (7.38) is for all components, not only one of them.

α -Instability affects both components

Figure 12.11 shows snapshots and comet-size distributions of simulation $B75_\gamma$ with $\gamma_J = 0.8$. One sees that at first ($t \leq 8\tau$), only the α -molecules are collapsing and forming a rocky planetoid. Then, thanks to the great attractive force of the α -planetoid, many β -molecules gather around it, forming an atmosphere ($t = 12\tau$). Note that a β -atmosphere can also be observed, in a less striking way, for the simulation with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ in Fig. 12.9. What happens afterwards is very interesting: at $t = 16\tau$, one sees that the rocky planetoid swaps the α and β molecules, the heavier β -molecules replace the α -molecules near the centre.

α -Planetoid with β -atmosphere

12.3 BELOW CRITICAL TEMPERATURES

In this section, to complete the study of binary fluid mixtures, we consider fluids where both T_α and T_β are below the critical temperature. The number density n has been chosen in such a way that for the molecular fractions $x_\alpha > 0$, the α -component with number density $n_\alpha = x_\alpha \cdot n$ is in a phase transition.

Figure 12.11.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of the simulation B75_γ with $\gamma = 0.8$. The slice shows in depth 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. α : blue, β : red, both: black.

Figure 12.12.: Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the simulations C10 (blue), C75 (cyan), C50 (black), C25 (yellow) and C00 (red) with $\gamma_J = 1.5$. Solid line: both types, dashed line: α -component, dotted line: β -component.

Above ideal gas Jeans criterion

Figure 12.12 shows the time evolution of bound molecules of the C-simulations with $\gamma_J = 1.5$. There is a distinct difference compared to the A- and B-simulations: Only the α -molecules are forming clumps, which is also shown in Fig. 12.13. This is slightly counter-intuitive at first, as one could expect the β -molecules to be even more eager to fall into the planetoid than in the A- and B-simulations, since the temperature is lower.

But, thanks to the very low temperature of the C-simulation, the α -molecules quickly form clumps from the very beginning. These clumps are heavier than the β -molecules, and decelerate faster into the planetoid.

Below ideal Gas Jeans criterion

The evolution of the simulations below the ideal gas Jeans criterion are analogous to the B-simulations. The fraction of bound α -molecules in the pure α -fluid and the mixture rise, and the fraction of bound molecules of the pure β -fluid remains very low. This is in accordance with Fig. 8.2 where the α -molecules are unstable but the β -molecules stable. The simulations C10, C75, C50 and C25 form a rocky α -planetoid, as already seen in the B-simulations (see Fig. 12.9).

12.4 VIRIAL THEOREM

When comparing the simulations above the ideal gas Jeans instability, there is a clear difference between the A- and B-simulations on one side, and the C-simulations on the other. In the first two, a gaseous β -planetoid forms, whereas in the latter, a rocky α -planetoid forms. Looking at the virial terms of the fluids (see §8.2), Equ. (8.24) is fulfilled in the A- and B-simulations, whereas for the C-simulation, the density is in the unvirializable domain \mathcal{D} .

Rocky α -planetoid

C-Simulations:
Unvirializable

Figure 12.13.: Snapshot time-sequence (left) and comet-size distribution (right) of the simulation C75 with $\gamma = 1.5$. The slice shows in depth 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. α : blue, β : red, both: black.

Figure 12.14.: Fraction of bound molecules with $m_{\text{cl}} > m_{\text{He}}$ as a function of time of the simulations A75 (blue), A75₀₁ (cyan), B75 (red) and B75₀₁ (yellow), with $\gamma_J = 1.5$. Solid line: α , dotted line: β . Dashed line $\gamma_J = 0.5$.

In this section, we vary the densities of the A and B simulations in order to be in and out of the unvirializable domain.

Figure 12.14 shows the time evolution of clusters having a higher mass than one β -molecule ($N_{\text{cl,ff}} > 2$) for the simulations in the unvirializable domain (A75₀₁ and B75₀₁) and below it (A75 and B75). A very quick rise of α clumps for the unvirializable fluid happens, both with and without gravity, which is in accordance with Equ. (8.24), as neither the repulsive Lennard-Jones term nor the kinetic energy can withhold the attractive Lennard-Jones term thus leading to the formation of clumps. Note that even in simulation A75₀₁, with a temperature above the critical temperature, this clump formation is taking place, even though a phase transition is officially not possible. Only a slow clump formation takes place for the virializable fluids.

Once the exponential growth of the perturbation becomes important ($t \geq 2\tau$), the unvirializable fluids have created an important number of clumps heavier than the β -molecules, which fall, thanks to dynamical friction, faster in the forming planetoid. This can be seen in Fig. 12.15, the planetoids of the simulations A75 and B75 consist mostly of β -molecules, whereas the planetoid of B75₀₁ consists mostly of α -molecules. A somewhat special case is A75₀₁, where the planetoids composition is almost perfectly fifty-fifty. This can be explained by the fact that being above the critical temperature, the clumps are not really solid but dense gas which is able to mix easily with β -molecules. Thus, once a α -planetoid has formed using all the heavy α -clumps, the β -clumps fall into the planetoid and mix with it.

Fast α -clump formation

*Unvirializable:
Formation of rocky
 α -planetoids*

Figure 12.15.: Density of planetoid at $t = 5\tau$ as a function of the radius of the simulations A75 (blue), A75₀₁ (cyan), B75 (red) and B75₀₁ (yellow), with $\gamma_J = 1.5$. Solid line: all molecules, dashed: α -molecules, dotted: β -molecules.

12.5 INFLUENCE OF β -MOLECULES ON α -MOLECULES BELOW IDEAL GAS JEANS CRITERION

As can be seen in Fig. 12.8, almost no β -molecules form clumps if $\gamma_J = 0.5$ and the percentage of β -molecules in the planetoid is negligible. Granted, the concentration of He around the planetoid rises slightly as can be barely seen in Fig. 12.9. Thus the question can be raised whether a small fraction of a secondary molecule (such as He in the case of molecular clouds) needs to be included in low-gravity simulations. To answer that question, simulation B75 with $\gamma_J = 0.5$ was run again, but all β -molecules were removed and their mass equally distributed to the α -molecules (in order to keep the same gravitational potential).

Removal of β in B75

Figure 12.16.: Fraction of bound molecules as a function of time of the normal simulation B75 (cyan), the simulation B75 where the β -molecules were removed (black) and the simulation B10 (blue) with $\gamma_J = 0.5$. Solid line: both types, dashed line: α -component, dotted line: β -component.

Figures 12.16 shows the time evolution of the fraction of bound molecules of the simulations B75, B75 without β -molecules and B10 for comparison.

Figure 12.17.: γ_J of different total fluid masses with $T = 10$ K as a function of number density. Green: Moon, blue: Earth, red: Jupiter, yellow: Sun. Cyan: H_2 phase transition, cyan dots: unvirializable domain \mathcal{D} . Solid line: ideal gas Jeans instability, dotted line: gravitational instability thanks to phase transition.

Even though the two B75 simulations are similar, there are differences to be observed. The fraction of bound α -molecules of the simulation B75 should correspond to the total fraction of bound molecules of the simulation without β -molecules, but the latter is higher, the β -molecules in B75 have a damping effect on the clump formation. In addition, the simulation without β -molecules is rising to a higher value at the end of the simulation.

The inclusion of a small fraction of a secondary molecule does change the look of the simulation by damping the clump-formation of α -molecules. For that reason, the inclusion of secondary molecules in more realistic simulations is useful.

Damping effect on clump formation

12.6 PHYSICAL SYSTEMS

Up to now, we have looked at theoretical models, varying x_α from 0 to 1, and stating the temperature and density as a fraction of the α critical values. The critical values for H_2 are $T_c = 32.97$ K and $n_c = 9.34 \cdot 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-3}$. In astrophysical conditions, the He mass fraction is between $w_{\text{He,SS}} = 0.2741$ for the solar system (Lodders 2003) and $w_{\text{He,MW}} = 0.2486$ for the initial Big Bang mixture (Cyburt et al. 2008), which translates to number fractions $x_{\text{He,SS}} = 0.1598$ and $x_{\text{He,MW}} = 0.1428$.

Figure 12.17 shows γ_J as a function of the number density for solar system abundances ($x = 0.16$) and $T = 10$ K with total masses equal to the Moon, Earth, Jupiter and Sun. H_2 is then in a phase transition for $n > 4 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$,

only a Moon mass or below can be in a phase transition and below the Jeans criterion. The fluid is unvirializable for $n > 6 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$.

If we go to a lower temperature, say the CMB 2.7 K, a H₂ phase transition takes place for $n > 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-3}$. In that case, fluids with Earth mass would be chemically unstable below the ideal gas Jeans criterion for $n \leq 3 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and with Jupiter mass for $n \leq 3 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ m}^{-3}$. Fluid with Sun mass on the other hand cross $\gamma_J = 1$ only in the gaseous phase of H₂. The lowest unvirializable density $n_- = 6 \cdot 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ does not change a lot with temperature.

*Simulation-size
constraints*

The number of FFT mesh cells $N_{\text{FFT}} \propto L^3$ and the simulation time-scale $\tau \propto L$ are both directly dependent on $L \propto n^{-1/3}$, and the total calculation duration scales as $t_{\text{sim}} \propto \tau \cdot N_{\text{FFT}} \propto n^{-4/3}$. For that reason, simulating a fluid at CMB temperature with densities below 10^{20} m^{-3} would translate to extremely long simulation run times with today's computers. In addition, the upper limit for the mass of super-molecules is $m_{\text{SM,max}} \approx 5 \cdot 10^{-6} M_{\oplus}$ (see Equ. 9.16). Thus, the minimum number of super-molecules $N_{\text{tot,min}} = M/m_{\text{SM,max}}$ is $\sim 2 \cdot 10^5, 6.5 \cdot 10^7, 6.5 \cdot 10^{10}$ for a Earth, Jupiter, and Sun mass, respectively. For that reason, for the time being we content ourselves to study Moon and Earth mass systems.

Planetoid formation

*Moon and Earth
mass*

Three simulations were run at a temperature of $T = 10 \text{ K}$, which is above the critical temperature of He and below the one of H₂, and thus in a similar regime as the B-simulations. Two simulations have a total mass equal to the Moon, with $n \approx 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-3}$ which is above the ideal gas Jeans criterion and in the unvirializable domain, and $n \approx 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ which is below the Jeans criterion, and one has a total mass equal to the Earth and with $n \approx 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$ which is above the criterion. The simulation parameters are given in Table 12.1.

*Planetoid type
depends on mass and
density*

Figure 12.18 shows the snapshot and comet-size distribution of the three simulations after the formation of a planetoid. The fluid of SSE04 is above the ideal gas Jeans criterion and we observe the formation a a He-planetoid, surrounded by H₂, similar to §12.2. The evolution of simulation SSM02, being below the ideal gas Jeans criterion, leads to the formation of a rocky H₂ planetoid, similar to §12.2.

In the case of SSM01, the density lies in the unvirializable domain, resulting in a formation of many H₂-grains from the very beginning, which are heavier than the He-atoms. This leads to the formation of a H₂-planetoid similar to §12.3.

Figure 12.18.: Snapshots and comet-size distributions of the simulations SSM01, SSM02 and SSE04. The slice selects in depth 20% of the super-molecules. N_{comet} is the number of super-molecules in one comets. $f(N_{\text{comet}})$ is the comet size distribution function. The squares in the two lower left frames have the same size as the next upper frame. α : blue, β : red, both: black.

Part IV

CONCLUSIONS

The following sections wrap up this work. §13 presents a flow chart for the formation of H₂ bodies usable in larger numerical codes. §14 gives the general conclusions. §15 gives a perspective for future investigations and shows the main challenges.

§14 appeared in slightly different form in FP2015a and FP2015b. §13 and §15 have not yet been published.

13

FLOW CHART

Maximum
simulation mass:
Sun

Simulating the formation of cold rocky H₂ bodies is only possible at very small scales. Even if it is possible in the future to simulate much lower densities and using today's high-performance computer-clusters, the number of super-molecules would still be limited to $N_{\text{tot}} \approx 10^{10-11}$ and the maximum mass per super-molecule to $M_{\text{SM}} \approx 10^{-11} M_{\odot}$, so at maximum a total mass of $\sim 1 M_{\odot}$ could be simulated. Therefore, in the near future, there is no way to directly simulate the effects of a H₂ phase transition using super-molecules in a molecular cloud, and even less in galactic or cosmic simulations.

Resolution increase
of 9 orders of
magnitude

Looking at ISM simulations, the mass resolution is not the only issue, the spacial resolution may be an even greater challenge, as today's resolutions are $\sim 0.05 \text{ pc} \approx 10^{12} \text{ km}$ (Renaud et al. 2013). The size of the H₂ bodies on the other hand would be in the range of a few cm for snow balls to Earth radius for the biggest planetoids, so a spacial resolution increase of at least 10^9 is needed to resolve such bodies in ISM simulations.

Figure 13.1 shows a flow chart for plane-parallel perturbations which gives a qualitative description of the evolution of a perturbation and which could be used in larger simulations to implement the formation of H₂ bodies. Input are the basic fluids properties (T, n, x) and the wavenumber k of the perturbation, the output is whether the perturbation will (a) grow exponentially and lead to a gravitational collapse, (b) lead to the segregation of rocky H₂ bodies due to phase transition and gravity, or (c) will remain stable.

Input:
 T, n, x, k

Output:
(Non-)Formation of
H₂ or He-bodies

It is difficult to quantify the formation of the bodies, which will need more simulations with higher total mass and mass resolution, but a few assumptions can be made. The exponential growth of an ideal gas Jeans collapse is linked to ω and τ where

$$\tau(T, k) = \frac{2\pi}{k} (3k_{\text{B}}T)^{-1/2}, \quad (13.1)$$

and the final density is similar to the critical one, so the ration of the initial and critical densities gives an order of magnitude of the growth needed. The simulation results show that the final mass is of order $\sim 0.01 M$ where

$$M(n, k) \approx \left(\frac{2\pi}{k}\right)^3 \frac{4}{3} \pi m n. \quad (13.2)$$

In the case of a phase transition below the ideal gas Jeans criterion, the number of bound molecules does not change after the formation of the smallest clumps which happens within a few $10 - 100\tau$, the formation of larger bodies only happens due to segregation of smaller clumps, but no new molecules are bound. The initial number of bound molecules is at the moment only a "educated guess" as simulations of a H₂ phase transition with a density as low as molecular clouds is not possible as of now (see §15.2.2 for a discussion of possible solutions).

Figure 13.1.: Flow chart for plane-parallel perturbation.

The parameter $y \equiv \Delta s/2$ where Δs is the entropy difference, the helper functions $f(y)$ and $g(y)$, and the coexistence temperature T_χ and density n_χ are taken from Johnston (2014), and k_{id} is derived from Equ. (7.38):

$$f(y) = \frac{y \cosh y - \sinh y}{\sinh y \cosh y - y}, \quad (13.3)$$

$$g(y) = 1 + 2f(y) \cosh y + f^2(y), \quad (13.4)$$

$$T_\chi(y) = \frac{27f(y) [f(y) + \cosh y]}{4g^2(y)}, \quad (13.5)$$

$$n_\chi(y) = \frac{3f(y)}{\exp(y) + f(y)}, \quad (13.6)$$

$$k_{\text{id}}(T, n, x) = \sqrt{\frac{12\pi G m_{\text{H}_2}^2}{5k_{\text{B}}T} [x(1 + \mu) + \mu]n}, \quad (13.7)$$

$$\omega_{\text{id}}(T, n, x, k) = \text{Equ. (7.35)}. \quad (13.8)$$

The inverse function $T_\chi^{-1}(T)$ can be found analytically, but would use more than one page to display it and is therefore not useful. It could be solved numerically, for example using the Newton method, but in a large numerical code this would be too time consuming. The fastest solution probably is to interpolate mapped values.

CONCLUSIONS

Analytic methods (part ii) and computer simulations (part iii) were used to study the gravitational instability of single component fluids and binary fluid mixtures in a phase transition. We extrapolated the single-component simulations results to the ubiquitous H₂ and showed that the formation of cold, mostly undetectable comet- and even planet-sized rocky H₂ clumps is very possible. The use of only one component gives a good first impression, but in cosmic gases, there is a mass fraction of $w \approx 25 \pm 2\%$ He atoms which is why binary fluids were simulated as well. The binary fluid results show that dependent of the circumstances, there can be either the formation of He or H₂ planetoids.

*He mass fraction of
~25%*

14.1 ANALYTIC RESULTS

A van der Waals fluid can be in three different states: gaseous, solid/liquid, or in a phase transition where the two phases coexist. The latter is defined as lying on the line of the Maxwell construct, where $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_s = 0$. A fluid is gravitationally unstable if an introduced perturbation has a wavelength above a certain value, which depends on $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_s$. Since this quantity vanishes for a fluid presenting a phase transition, such a fluid is also gravitationally unstable.

*Phase Transition:
 $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_s = 0$*

The stability of multi-component fluid mixture has already been studied in the literature, mostly in order to study fluid binaries consisting of baryonic and dark matter. The wave-number below which a fluid mixture is unstable is the sum of the Jeans wave-numbers of each component. Since the Jeans wave-number is inversely proportional to $(\partial P / \partial \rho)_s^{-1}$, which is equal to zero in the case of a phase transition, a fluid mixture is unstable as soon as one of its components is in a phase transition. Physically what happens is that when one species is in a phase transition an overdensity only increases the condensed phase fraction at constant pressure, producing no global force to counter gravity. On the contrary, in pure gas phase an overdensity produces an overpressure, the gradient of which counters gravity.

*Fluid mixture with
phase transition is
gravitationally
unstable at any scale*

In order to study the evolution of unstable fluid mixtures, we used the widely used Lennard-Jones inter-molecular potential, which reproduces quite well the H₂ phase transition (but less well the He transition, which is not essential in this work). The study of the virial theorem, using the gravitational and the Lennard-Jones potential energies, has shown that there is a maximum temperature below which a fluid can fragment at arbitrary small masses. This temperature is an order of magnitude above the critical temperature. This shows, granted the right circumstances, that comets can form at a temperatures an order of magnitude larger than the critical temperature. In the case of

*Fragment at arbitrary
small mass*

Unvirializable density H_2 , this maximum temperature lies in the range of 400 – 600 K, depending on the solid crystalline structure. There is a unvirializable density-domain \mathcal{D} , within which the attractive forces dominate the repulsive ones for any total mass M and no virial equilibrium is possible. These states can be reached in strongly dynamical situations (e.g. during collapses) and are able to produce condensed clumps particularly quickly. Dynamical friction is important to separate species and condensed clumps. For instance, if H_2 is in a phase transition, the formed H_2 clumps are heavier than the He-molecules, and precipitate in a gravitational field, producing almost pure H_2 bodies.

There are three reasons to concentrate on plane-parallel initial collapses:

- Plane-parallel: Fastest collapse*
Temperature increase: x2
Low opacity
1. In typical cosmic conditions, the fastest collapsing geometry is sheet-like, not filament- or point-like.
 2. The adiabatic matter compression during collapse leads to the least heating in sheet-like geometry: in sheet-like adiabatic collapse the gravitational energy released to the fluid is *finite* and amounts to a maximum increase of temperature by only a factor of about two, while in filament-like collapses the temperature diverges logarithmically as function of filament radius, and in point-like collapses the temperature diverges as the inverse sphere radius.
 3. Radiative cooling is the easiest in sheet-like collapse. Indeed the absorption probability in sheet-like geometry remains almost unchanged for any compression, an initially transparent medium remains transparent, whereas the probability converges to one in filament-like and point-like geometries. Therefore, radiative cooling is barely slowed down in sheet-like collapses, and unlike in spherical or filament collapses opacity is unable to prevent density to reach high values. This is a crucial point for this work, as the ISM conditions are commonly thought to be far away from the H_2 phase transition conditions.

14.2 SIMULATIONS

Combine LJ and gravity We performed simulations using the state-of-the-art molecular dynamics simulator LAMMPS. We used super-molecules in order to combine the Lennard-Jones inter-molecular potential together with the gravitational potential in numerical simulations.

14.2.1 *Single component fluid simulations*

Super-molecules

We tested the super-molecule concept thoroughly. We achieved good scaling for non-gravitational effects if the number of super-molecules is large enough ($\gtrsim 10^5$). The sticking point is to ensure that the molecular Lennard-Jones forces are dominating the gravitational forces in close-range interactions. This is achieved by setting the number of super-molecules to be large

enough so that the distance at which the two forces are equal is above the cut-off radius $4\sigma_{\text{SM}}$. For an H_2 fluid this sets a maximum super-molecule mass equal to $5.7 \cdot 10^{-6} M_{\oplus}$, limiting the total mass that can be simulated by the available computing power.

In principle, the super-molecule concept should not perfectly reproduce the time dependence of diffusive properties, as bigger particles introduce faster relaxation. But our experiments using different resolutions spanning several orders of magnitude did not reveal important modifications in the timings of major collapse and asymptotic evolution state. This enables us to study the fragmentation of large bodies, which we call comets and planetoids.

Super-molecule size independence

One-phase fluid

We applied a plane sinusoidal perturbation into a one-phase fluid with a temperature above the critical value. The results reproduce the ideal-gas Jeans instability: no collapse is seen for conditions below the Jeans criterion, while an exponential growth of the perturbation is observed for conditions above it.

As a result, the temperature rises, and small- and medium-sized comets form, some of which later merge into one big planetoid. An interesting observation is the mass distribution of these comets, which follows a power law for the small- and medium-sized "comets", while the planetoid and the largest comets follow a different power law.

Different power laws for small and large bodies

Phase transition fluid

We simulated fluids with temperatures below the critical value and close to the effective phase transition for three different cases: without gravity, sufficiently, and weakly self-gravitating (above and below the ideal-gas Jeans criterion).

Because of the Maxwellian velocity distribution fluctuations, the non-gravitating fluids form small- and medium-sized comets until the potential and kinetic energy reach an equilibrium; thereafter they remain statistically stable. In the absence of any long-range force, no planetoid forms.

The self-gravitating fluids with a gravitational potential above the ideal-gas Jeans criterion do not react differently to a plane sinusoidal perturbation from a one-phase fluid: the perturbation grows exponentially and its temperature rises, and small- and medium-sized comets form, which ultimately merge into one planetoid.

No gravity:
Multimers and small comets

The analysis predicts that fluids presenting a phase transition are unstable even if the gravitational potential alone is below the ideal-gas Jeans threshold. The performed simulations of weakly self-gravitating fluids in the phase transition regime did reproduce the prediction. Because of the weak nature of the gravitational potential, the timescale to see this reaction is two orders of magnitude longer than for sufficiently self-gravitating fluids, but, in the end, a big central planetoid forms anyway. While the out-of-phase transition fluids do not amplify perturbations, those in a phase transition indeed amplify them.

Above Jeans:
Gaseous planetoids

Below Jeans:
Rocky planetoids

14.2.2 Binary fluid simulations

Several binary fluid mixtures were studied using two components: α and β . Their respective properties (the most important being $m_\alpha/m_\beta < 1$ and $T_{c,\alpha}/T_{c,\beta} > 1$) were chosen to mirror a H₂-He fluid, but the fluids general properties were made molecule-independent.

3 temperature cases

Three temperature domains can be defined, (A) above both critical temperatures, (B) between the critical temperatures and (C) below both critical temperatures. In all three cases, the molecular fraction was varied, and the fluids were simulated above and below the Jeans criterion. In order to test the scaling of the simulations, different numbers of molecules were used. For dynamical processes the precise number of super-molecules is not important, but for segregation effects, a weak dependance has been found in the sense that coarser simulations exaggerate them.

In case (A), both components are gaseous, and an introduced perturbation does not grow when the gravitational potential is below the Jeans criterion. When above the Jeans criterion, the fluid collapses and forms a gaseous planetoid. The β -molecules are twice as massive as the α -molecules, and fall faster into the planetoid. For that reason, the planetoid consists mostly of β -molecules, surrounded by an α -atmosphere. This is independent of the molecular fraction x_α , even at very high x_α -values, the planetoids consists mostly of β -molecules.

Above Jeans:
Gaseous β -planetoid
 α -atmosphere

Below Jeans with
phase transition:
Rocky α -planetoid
 β -atmosphere

In case (B) and (C), the number density of the fluids was chosen so that the α -component is in a phase transition for all $x_\alpha > 0$. In fact, both cases are very similar since in both cases the β -component is not in a phase transition. When the fluids are below the Jeans criterion, an instability happens thanks to the phase transition of the α -component, which leads to the formation of H₂ clumps and ultimately a rocky α -planetoid. This planetoid is surrounded by a β -atmosphere, which is getting more important with increasing gravitational potential. As in case (A), the molecular fraction x_α does not matter, even at very low x_α -values, the planetoid still consists almost exclusively of α -molecules.

Unvirializable:
Rocky α -planetoids
even above Jeans

A surprising observation occurs for cases (B) or (C) above the Jeans criterion. In that case, there is a race between the formation of small α -grains thanks to the phase transition and the exponential growth of the perturbation. The heaviest bodies are decelerated faster and fall first into the forming planetoid. When the α -component is either gaseous or only forming very few and small clumps, a β -planetoid forms. On the other hand, if the α -component forms many grains, which are heavier than the β -molecules, an α -planetoid forms. We showed in the simulations that this race between α and β is linked with the unvirializable density domain \mathcal{D} . If a fluid reaches this domain, the α -component wins, otherwise the β -component wins.

Solar system abundances

In addition to the above mentioned simulations, fluids with solar system abundances and Moon or Earth mass were simulated. As shown in Fig. 12.17,

a fluid with Earth mass cannot be below the Jeans criterion and still in a phase transition, but with Moon mass, this is possible. In that case, a rocky H₂ planetoid results. With a mass as low as the Moon, the fluid needs to be very dense in order to be above the Jeans criterion. In fact, it would lie in the unvirializable density-domain \mathcal{D} and a H₂-planetoid forms. For a fluid with Earth mass on the other hand, even a relatively low-density fluid is still above the Jeans criterion. The result is a gaseous He planetoid with a H₂ atmosphere.

14.3 INSTABILITY IN H₂-HE FLUID

Figure 14.1 shows different possible planetoid and comet formations due to a gravitational instability. A fluid is gaseous if below the phase transition domain and solid/liquid if above. When in the phase transition, the density can rise without an increase of pressure.

There can be no formation below the Jeans criterion if the fluid is not in a phase transition. Most of the planetoids due to an ideal gas Jeans collapse consist of gaseous He, but if the fluid is in the unvirializable domain \mathcal{D} , then a H₂ planetoid forms. Note that this H₂ planetoid can be solid/liquid or gaseous dependent of its temperature. If gaseous, He is able to percolate down, slowly transforming it into a He planetoid.

If the fluid is in a phase transition, we have to distinguish between a collapse above the ideal Jeans criterion, which leads to a gaseous He planetoid except in the unvirializable domain where it becomes a rocky H₂ one, and a collapse below the ideal Jeans criterion, which leads to a rocky H₂ planetoid.

The usual average density domain of molecular clouds lies between 10^8 and 10^{12} H₂/m³, and with such a density a H₂ phase transition is only possible at temperatures below ~ 5 K. But molecular clouds are observed to follow a fractal mass distribution over a minimum of 4–6 orders of magnitude in column densities, so the average density is not a quantity proper to characterize molecular clouds. Since we know that stars form with densities $\sim 10^{29}$ H₂/m³, by continuity argument, intermediate states covering all this density interval have to exist.

Fluids with a high total mass, especially with stellar mass or above, reach very quickly the ideal gas Jeans criterion leading to gaseous He-planetoids. But fluids with lower total mass, as for example the cold globules observed in the Helix nebula, especially with Earth mass and below, have the ideal gas Jeans criterion at much higher densities and are in the phase transition domain before being above the ideal gas Jeans criterion.

14.4 WRAPPING UP

This work is general enough to be relevant for many astrophysical situations. In the case of H₂ as main component, it concerns situations where temperature may drop well below 10 K, such as in cold molecular gas in the outer galactic disks, in expanding winds of planetary nebulae or supernovae, where cold substellar mass condensations are known to form, or in protoplanetary

Above Jeans:
*Formation of
gaseous
He-planetoid*

Below Jeans with
phase transition:
*Formation of rocky
H₂-planetoid*

High mass:
Jeans collapse

Low mass:
*Phase transition
segregation*

Context:
*Molecular clouds
Planetary nebulae
Proto-planetary disks*

Figure 14.1.: Gravitational instabilities at different temperatures and densities. Dots: planetoid formation thanks to ideal gas Jeans criterion; red: gaseous He-planetoid, blue: rocky H₂-planetoid, green: gaseous H₂-planetoid with He-accumulation. Cyan background: planetoid formation thanks to phase transition, leading to rocky H₂ comets and planetoids. Blue line: unvirializable density domain \mathcal{D} with $T < T_{c,H_2}$. Green line: unvirializable density domain \mathcal{D} with $T > T_{c,H_2}$. Above dashed lines: ideal gas Jeans criterion for Sun, Jupiter, Earth, and Moon mass.

disks. Other molecules besides H_2 , such as CO, can condense even sooner, but as their mass fraction is low they should not significantly perturb the gravitational balance, while He should not condense at all and should keep a minimal amount of gaseous phase. The precipitation of formed comets and planetoids in a gravitational field, separating the gaseous and condensed phases, is a fascinating aspect that is as yet impossible to capture with traditional hydrodynamical codes, but possible with the molecular dynamics approach.

This study shows that the cold ISM physics is much richer than previously imagined. The formation of substellar gaseous or rocky condensed bodies by the H_2 phase transition combined to gravity, appears natural once we recognize that collapses proceed most of the time along the sequence pancake, filament and point, and in the first sheet-like phase high densities allowing a H_2 phase transition can be reached if the initial medium temperature is below ~ 15 K. This temperature limit would be even higher if radiative cooling had been considered. Most of the ISM cold gas must therefore pass over molecular cloud lifetimes ($\sim 10^6 - 10^8$ yr) through such, brief ($\sim 10^2 - 10^4$ yr) singular sheet-like collapses where density diverges but not temperature. Observationally such events are difficult to detect due to the limited increase of temperature, opacity, and column density all along the collapse, while allowing to reach high volume densities. When seen on edge such sheet-like collapses would look like filaments.

The simulations we were able to perform are still very limited in total mass. Including He is necessary but provides a number of complications with respect to the pure H_2 case, and widens the general picture. Combining the accumulated experience of large scale gas phase simulations by other authors (e.g. Renaud et al. 2013; Butler et al. 2015), we can easily extrapolate what larger simulations should produce with micro-AU resolution: instead of one planetoid per simulation box, pc-sized sheet-like collapses should show filaments with longer lifetimes which would funnel H_2 condensed bodies and produce a spectrum of planetoids and comets, and occasionally stars. The left-over condensed cold substellar bodies should then start to evaporate according to the ambient radiation flux and the depth of their gravitational potential. The lifetime of such bodies should be short near the centre of galaxies, but much longer at the periphery of galaxies, or even in intergalactic space, especially in cosmic filaments. One can postulate that especially at the periphery of disk galaxies where the radiation heating is low, some fraction of the dark baryons can be trapped in the form of such condensed bodies.

Formation of rocky
 H_2 bodies:

$$T \leq 15 \text{ K}$$

+
*Plane-parallel
contraction*

Mass spectrum of
solid H_2 :
*Multimers -
planetoids*

15

PERSPECTIVES

A thesis has to reach an end. However this does not mean that the topic covered by it is exhaustively dealt with. Science can be compared to the Greek mythology of the Lernaean Hydra. This creature possesses many heads, and whenever one is cut off, it grows two new ones instead. Science is similar insofar as whenever you answer one question, new ones appear.

15.1 PHYSICAL MODELS

*Simple physical
model*

The physics in this work were – on purpose – very simple: An initially homogeneous density distribution of one or two components perturbed in one direction with a plane sinusoidal wave. These conditions can easily be simulated using periodic boundary conditions, which were used throughout the simulations. In subsequent research, more demanding physical models could be applied, including the following properties:

- *Angular momentum*

Disk formation

In the absence of any structured movement, the angular momentum is equal to zero. In reality, systems are often in rotation. In rotating systems, the conservation of angular momentum becomes important. As it is very difficult to dissipate angular momentum (energy at least can be radiated), it remains constant over a very long period of time. This changes the dynamics of a system, as any kind of energy exchange must fulfil the conservation law, and disks are formed frequently.

- *Trace elements*

*Ice formation
catalyst*

Molecular clouds consist of ~98% H₂ and He, the remaining mass consists of heavier molecules and dust grains. At first sight, neglecting the remaining 2% seems like an acceptable simplification. But these heavier trace elements may play important roles. Being much heavier and having a much larger surface, ice can form on dust grains. Large molecules and dust grains may also function as a catalyst for the formation of big H₂ ice grains, in the way dust grains on Earth help the formation of rain drops. As neither H₂ nor He can radiate energy below ~500 K, only the heavier elements can cool down a fluid through radiation.

- *Radiative transfer*

Cooling

Thus far, all simulations have been done without any cooling mechanisms, the fluid being basically dark. When introducing cooling (or heating), the dynamics of a fluid become much richer. As shown in §6, a sheet-like collapse increases the temperature by a factor of 2. Whether or not this temperature increase is radiated can decide if a fluid is in a

phase transition and influence the form of resulting condensation bodies.

- *Different intermolecular potential*

This work used the Lennard-Jones intermolecular potential. It is simple enough for doing extensive virial analyses and can be implemented very efficiently in numerical codes, and it is nevertheless complete enough to correctly reproduce a van der Waals fluid in equilibrium. Furthermore, it reproduces the phase transition of H₂ quite well. Nevertheless, this potential has its limitations. The twelfth-term repulsive term is chosen for ease of calculation and is not physically motivated, thus the physics (not the formation) of condensed bodies has to be treated with care. At very low temperature, He and H₂ have quantum effects, which are not taken into account at all. There are other, more complex intermolecular potentials, such as the Buckingham potential, which lend themselves for further investigation.

Condensations

Quantum effects

15.2 TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

There are many technical challenges in order to have lower initial densities, higher resolution, higher total mass and more complex physical models. The most important ones are listed below.

15.2.1 Increase number of super-molecules

One of the main challenge is to increase the number of super-molecules. On one side, this is an easy challenge, as it simply translates into creating initial conditions with more particles, on the other side, it needs much more computing power, which is always challenging. The total simulation time can be estimated as $T_{\text{sim}} = N_{\Delta t} T_{\Delta t}$, where $T_{\Delta t}$ is the calculation time per time-step and $N_{\Delta t}$ is the number of time-steps. Neglecting FFT calculations, which are of $O(N \log(N))$ but happen only every 10 – 100 timesteps, the time per timestep is proportional to N : $T_{\Delta t} = O(N)$, whereas the number of timesteps is proportional to the simulation box-length $L \propto N^{1/3}$: $N_{\Delta t} = O(N^{1/3})$. We find thus that the time of a simulation can be estimated as $T_{\text{sim}} = O(N^{4/3})$.

Simulation time:
 $O(N^{4/3})$

Higher mass resolution

The first reason why an increase of super-molecules has important effects is the mass resolution. The mass per super-molecules was 10^{15} kg (similar to Mars' smaller moon Deimos) for the lightest simulation C00 and 10^{19} kg (similar to the asteroid 3 Juno) for the heaviest simulation A10. Thus, even one super-molecule exceeds already the mass of an average comet. In the present work, the emphasis was on the formation of planetoids – rocky or gaseous – which can be numerically resolved. However, in order to study the formation of smaller bodies, a much higher mass resolution would be needed.

$M_{\text{min}} = 10^{15}$ kg

Higher total mass

$$M_{\text{SM}} = 5 \cdot 10^{-6} M_{\oplus}$$

The highest possible super-molecule mass is $5 \cdot 10^{-6} M_{\oplus}$. If this mass is exceeded, the gravitational forces become too important at intermolecular level, perturbing the dynamics and leading to false results, as shown in §10. This constraint heavily limits the total mass which can be simulated using a pure super-molecule approach. To study a Jupiter-mass fluid a minimum of $65 \cdot 10^6$ super-molecules is needed, for a sun-mass system even $65 \cdot 10^9$. Comparing this to the number of super-molecules generally used in this work (i.e. $N \leq 10^6$), much more computing power will be needed in the future. A Jupiter-mass simulation is possible on a medium-sized computing cluster, whereas a Sun-mass one would need one of the world's top clusters.

Other approaches might be possible. Starting at very low density (see next section), in a first run the fluid could be simulated in a collisionless gravitational n-body simulation using heavy particles in order to identify the high-density regions. Then, the particles ending up in these regions might be replaced by super-molecules and the simulation rerun. Similarly, the high-density regions might be simulated in isolation.

15.2.2 *Low density*

10 orders of
magnitude

All simulations performed in this work had high initial densities, from 10^{24} to 10^{27} m^{-3} . In order to simulate dense molecular clouds, densities of 10^{12} to 10^{15} need to be reached, so at least ten orders of magnitude lower. This presents mainly two challenges: the neighbour list for the short-range intermolecular potential and the long-range gravitational solver.

Neighbour list

Associated
containers

Trees

In the simulations of this work, the neighbour list is calculated using a Verlet list, i.e. the calculation domain is split in a grid where the cell-size is equal or smaller than the cut-off radius r_c . For each particle a linked list is created using the grid, containing all its neighbour particles. In order not to recalculate the list at every timestep, an additional skin radius r_s is added. That way it is enough to update the neighbour list every 10 – 1000 timesteps. This method is not applicable anymore if the density is too low, as the ratio of the simulation box over cut-off radius will be very high, and the grid would become too large. There are several possibility to overcome the excess of memory, for example using associative containers or trees.

Gravitational solver

LAMMPS uses the P³M method to solve the gravitational potential: the long-range forces are calculated by FFT using a mesh, and the short-range forces by direct calculation. As in the case of the neighbour list, this will not be possible at low densities. The direct calculation cost in one mesh cell is of $O(N_{p,c})$ where $N_{p,c}$ is the number of particles in the cell. A high-density region might very well be confined within one mesh cell and contain a big

fraction of the super-molecules, which would turn the calculation into $O(N^2)$, which is not feasible.

Fortunately, there exist already many efficient methods to solve the gravitational potential, such as adaptive mesh refinement (Couchman 1991), the Barnes-Hut tree (Barnes & Hut 1986), the TreePM method (Bagla 2002) or the fast multipole method (Greengard & Rokhlin 1987). Which one to use is mostly a matter of availability and ease of implementation, as each method has its advantages and disadvantages.

AMR
Tree(PM)
FMM

Implementation

There are basically four different ways to obtain a numerical code being able to combine inter-molecular dynamics with gravity at low density:

1. Combine LAMMPS with a gravitational code
2. Expand LAMMPS
3. Expand a gravitational code
4. Write a new code

Option (1) would definitely be the most efficient way, but as every program has its own particle format, it may be difficult to transfer particle lists from one code to another. Options (2) and (3) are similar, the question being which way around is more efficient. Having a very good gravitational solver is useless if the intermolecular solver is inefficient and vice versa. Up to now, the bottle-neck for the simulations has been the intermolecular potential solver, but this may change when the density is much lower, because the neighbour list of many particles would then be empty. Option (4) would of course be a drastic step, but if the first three points lead nowhere, this may be the only way to go. Thanks to new programming languages directly implementing parallelism, the creation of a new code from scratch may be possible in short period of time.

Bottle-neck:
LJ potential

15.2.3 *Isolated system*

In addition to systems with periodic boundary conditions, the simulation of isolated systems should be pursued, especially when the angular momentum is non-zero as in disks. There are no technical problems for the short-range intermolecular potential solver, but solving the gravitational long-range systems in isolated systems is slightly different when using FFT solver. This can, of course, be avoided by using a tree or the fast multi-pole method for gravity, but when retaining an FFT-based solver, some points have to be considered. First, as the FFT solver automatically solves periodic boundaries, either the potential has to be changed for an isolated system (James 1977), or the zero-padding trick has to be used (Hockney & Eastwood 1981). Second, as a FFT-solver uses always a finite simulation box, a boundary needs to be

Zero-padding trick

defined. The easiest solution is to use a reflecting sphere around the simulation domain which conserves the angular momentum. Some test simulations have been made in isolated systems using the zero-padding-trick and a reflecting sphere (§10.1.2).

Density distribution:

Homogeneous
Isothermal

The initial density distribution of an isolated system can have many forms. An isothermal uniform density distribution cannot be stable without rotation, as such a distribution would develop either a temperature or density gradient. A more suitable initial density distribution would be a (pseudo-) isothermal disk. An initial angular momentum can be introduced by setting the supermolecules in rotation around the centre. In the case of a homogeneous density distribution the tangential velocity would be $v_{\perp} \propto R$ whereas in the case of an isothermal distribution the velocity would be constant.

15.2.4 Radiative transfer

Berendsen
thermostat

Trace elements

Cooling (and heating), is among the physical challenges to solve. It is of course philosophically difficult to imagine where the radiation energy would go to or come from in the case of periodical boundary conditions. However one could imagine that such a system is not really infinite, but only many order of magnitude larger than the simulation box. Radiation energy loss in isolated systems on the other hand is straight forward. There are many ways to implement radiative transfer, a simple one being a thermostat, in which case all particles change their temperature following the same law. A simple yet useful thermostat is the Berendsen one, where $dT/dt = (T_0 - T)/\tau$ where T_0 is the wanted temperature and τ the timescale. This is however rather unphysical, since H_2 and He molecules are not directly radiating. A more appropriate implementation would be to use trace elements, such as CO or dust grains, which are radiating using a Berendsen thermostat, while the H_2 and He molecules exchange heat with them via dynamic interaction. This would, of course, still be an oversimplification, as it does not take into account the opacity of the medium, but should yield good preliminary results.

Part V

APPENDIX

§A explains the basic usage of the LAMMPS code and §B shows a typical LAMMPS run-script used for the simulations.

A

LAMMPS USAGE

Python scripts

All simulations in this work have been run with the parallel molecular dynamics code LAMMPS. Its functionality is described in §9, in this Appendix its usage is described. LAMMPS can be run directly using input-files, but this severely limits its possibilities, it is more convenient to use the scripting language Python¹. For visualisation, the excellent Matplotlib Python library (Hunter 2007) is used. §B shows a typical run-script.

A.1 PRE-PROCESSING

A uniform super-molecule distribution on a grid in periodic boundary conditions is used to ensure no pair of super-molecules is closer than σ , which would lead to a large acceleration due to the r^{-12} potential. A different solution is to distribute the molecules randomly and run the simulations for a few time-steps with a limited maximum velocity. As the two methods lead to the same results, the easier grid distribution was chosen. The units used in LAMMPS are so-called Lennard-Jones units, that is, $\sigma = \epsilon = m = 1$. The number of super-molecules and the spacing of the super-molecule distribution can be selected directly in LAMMPS, as seen in lines 104 - 110 in Listing B. The velocity distribution is Maxwellian and set in line 119, using the initial temperature and a random number seed.

Several simulation parameters, including the mass of the super-molecules, the strength of the gravitational potential, the time-steps of the Lennard-Jones and the gravitational solvers and the size of the FFT mesh are defined in lines 116 – 143. Two different types of snapshot files are used, a basic one saving only the position, type and velocity of the super-molecules is written 100 – 200 times per τ (called *snap*), and a more complex one including the list of all clumps is written 10 times per τ (called *cl*). This is defined in lines 148 – 161. The plane sinusoidal velocity perturbation cannot be set using LAMMPS commands and is programmed directly in Python in lines 169 – 203. The simulation runs are defined in lines 206 – 208, 5 times per τ the calculation domain gets rebalanced for better scaling performance.

A.2 SIMULATION RUN

LAMMPS runs in parallel using MPI². The simulation were run on the regor³ computer-cluster of the Observatory of Geneva. The python run-scripts (see

1 <http://www.python.org>

2 <http://www.mpi-forum.org/>

3 <http://obswww.unige.ch/doc/rst/Regor2.html>

Listing B) were launched using the queue software slurm⁴. As there were problems using LAMMPS together with the InfiniBand⁵ the number of cores per simulations was limited by the number of cores per processor, which on regor is 12 for the largest processor. This was however a good upper limit anyway, that way many simulations were able to be run in parallel.

A.3 POST-PROCESSING

Once a simulation is finished, the raw data has to be processed. This is done using a number of python scripts and the HDF5 file format(The HDF Group 1997 - 2015):

- *Snapshot-file to HDF5*
The snapshot-files of LAMMPS can be written in either text- or binary format. Of course, for larger simulations, text-format is not useful as the resulting files are much larger and slower to write and read. Throughout the simulations, the binary format was thus used. Unfortunately, every numerical code has its own binary format, and reading them needs some care. To render the lecture of the snapshot-files easier, the *snap* and *cl* binary LAMMPS files are transformed into HDF5-snap- and HDF5-cl-files.
- *Mean temperature, density and angular momentum*
Scripts read all the HDF5-snap-files of a simulation and calculate the mean temperature and temperature standard deviation, the density at a given position in $x = x_0 \pm \Delta x$ and the angular momentum of the major axes e_x , e_y and e_z , and writes them to corresponding HDF5-files for further use (for example Figs. 11.2, 11.6).
- *Comet-size distribution*
A script reads HDF5-cl-files containing the list of clumps, calculates the number of bound super-molecules and creates an array comet size vs number of comets which are written to an HDF5-file for further use (for example Fig. 12.6).
- *Planetoid density*
Using a single HDF5-cl-file, a script selects the most massive clump (usually a planetoid), calculates its center of mass and using an onion (spherical) grid to calculate the density as a function of radius (used for example in Fig. 11.23).
- *Comet temperature distribution*
Using a single HDF5-cl-file, a script calculates the temperature per comet-size (used for example in Fig. 11.6).
- *Spherical and cylindrical density and temperature map*
Designed mostly for future use, scripts calculate the spacial density and

⁴ <http://slurm.schedmd.com/>

⁵ <http://www.infinibandta.org/>

temperature distribution of simulation domains in onion (spherical) or leek (cylindrical) coordinates and writes them to HDF5-files which will be used for isolated spheres and disks.

- *Snapshot visualization*

A script takes a number (2 – 8) of HDF5-snap- and HDF5-cl-files, calculates a density map for each snap-file and creates a snapshot visualization and comet-size distribution figure such as Fig. 11.3.

- *Create movie*

A script takes all HDF5-snap- and HDF5-cl-files and the temperature-HDF5-file of a simulation and creates a movie.

B

LAMMPS RUN-SCRIPT

Listing B.1: Run-script of the simulation A75 with $\gamma_J = 0.5$.

```
1 from lammps import lammps
2 from numpy import *
3 from scipy import *
4 from mpi4py import MPI
5
6 #init mpi
7 comm = MPI.COMM_WORLD
8 rank = comm.Get_rank()
9
10
11 #constants
12 ncr = 0.316
13 Tcr = 1.326
14 pcr = (3./8)*Tcr*ncr
15
16 gamma = 5./3
17
18 TH2 = 32.97
19 THe = 5.19
20
21 TCMB = 2.7
22 TSS = 10.
23
24 rhH2 = 31.263
25 rhHe = 69.641
26
27 mH2 = 2.0159
28 mHe = 4.0026
29
30 nH2 = rhH2/mH2
31 nHe = rhHe/mHe
32
33 theta = THe/TH2
34 mu = mHe/mH2
35 thetaC = TCMB/TH2
36 thetaSS = TSS/TH2
37 nu = nHe/nH2
38 sigB = nu**(-1./3)
39
```

```

40 def dPdri(T, m, n):
41     return T/m
42
43 def Gi(T, m, n, L):
44     return gamma*dPdri(T, m, n)*pi/n/m/L**2
45
46 def GM(T, n, x, L):
47     m1 = 1.
48     m2 = mu
49     n1 = n*x
50     n2 = n*(1-x)
51     return pi*gamma*T/(L**2*(n1*m1**2 + n2*m2**2))
52
53 def tau(L, T, m):
54     return L/sqrt(3*T/m)
55
56
57 #USER INPUT
58 n_d = 80
59 n0 = 1e-2*ncr
60 T0 = 1.5*theta*Tcr
61 gam = 0.5
62 x = 0.75
63
64 m0 = x + (1-x)*mu
65
66 N = n_d**3
67 L0 = n0**(-1./3)*n_d
68
69 G0 = gam*GM(T0, n0, x, L0)
70 tau0= tau(L0, T0, m0)
71
72 if rank == 0:
73     print "Tcr", Tcr
74     print "ncr", ncr
75     print "pcr", pcr
76     print
77     print "theta", theta
78     print "nu", nu
79     print
80     print "T", T0
81     print "n", n0
82     print "m", m0
83     print "x", x
84     print
85     print "Gid", Gi(T0, m0, n0, L0)

```

```
86     print "GM", GM(T0, n0, x, L0)
87     print "tau", tau0
88     print
89     print "gamma", gam
90     print "G", G0
91
92
93
94 fP = 0.01
95
96
97 #####
98 # INIT
99 #####
100 lmp = lammmps()
101
102 lmp.command("log logfile")
103
104 lmp.command("units lj")
105 lmp.command("atom_style charge")
106 lmp.command("boundary p p p")
107 lmp.command("lattice sc %g"%n0)
108 lmp.command("region box block 0 %i 0 %i 0 %i"%(n_d,
    ↪ n_d, n_d))
109 lmp.command("create_box 2 box")
110 lmp.command("create_atoms 1 box")
111
112 lmp.command("set type 1 type/fraction 2 %g %i"%(1-x
    ↪ , rand()*2**16))
113 lmp.command("group alpha type 1")
114 lmp.command("group beta type 2")
115
116 lmp.command("mass 1 1.0")
117 lmp.command("mass 2 %g"%mu)
118
119 lmp.command("velocity all create %g %i dist
    ↪ gaussian loop all"%(T0, rand()*2**16))
120
121
122 lmp.command("set type 1 charge %g"%sqrt(G0))
123 lmp.command("set type 2 charge %g"%(sqrt(G0)*mu))
124
125 lmp.command("pair_style lj/cut/coul/long 4")
126 lmp.command("pair_coeff 1 1 1.0 1.0 4")
127 lmp.command("pair_coeff 2 2 %g %g 4"%(theta, sigB))
```

```

128 lmp.command("pair_coeff 1 2 %g %g 4"%(sqrt(theta),
    ↪ 0.5*(1 + sigB)))
129
130 lmp.command("kspace_style pppm 1.0e-3")
131 lmp.command("kspace_modify mesh %i %i %i"%(n_d, n_d
    ↪ , n_d))
132 lmp.command("kspace_modify order 5")
133
134 lmp.command("dielectric -1")
135
136 lmp.command("neighbor 1 bin")
137 lmp.command("neigh_modify delay 0 every 1 check no"
    ↪ )
138 lmp.command("neigh_modify one 10000")
139
140 lmp.command("fix 1 all nve/limit 1")
141
142 lmp.command("timestep 0.2")
143 lmp.command("run_style respa 2 20 pair 1 kspace 2")
144
145 lmp.command("compute alphaT alpha temp")
146 lmp.command("compute betaT beta temp")
147
148 lmp.command("thermo_style custom cpu time temp
    ↪ c_alphaT c_betaT pe etotal")
149 lmp.command("thermo_modify lost warn")
150 lmp.command("thermo_modify flush yes")
151 lmp.command("thermo 50")
152
153 lmp.command("dump 1 all custom %i snap/snap*.bin id
    ↪ type xs ys zs vx vy vz "%(int(round(tau0
    ↪ /100.*5))))
154
155 lmp.command("dump_modify 1 pad 8")
156
157 lmp.command("compute cla all cluster/atom 1.3625")
158 lmp.command("compute cl1 alpha cluster/atom 1.3625"
    ↪ )
159 lmp.command("compute cl2 beta cluster/atom %g"
    ↪ %(1.3625*nu**(-1./3)))
160 lmp.command("dump 2 all custom %i cl/cl*.bin id
    ↪ c_cla c_cl1 c_cl2 type x y z vx vy vz"%(int(
    ↪ round(tau0/10.*5))))
161 lmp.command("dump_modify 2 pad 8")
162
163 lmp.command("restart 5000 restart")

```

```
164
165 #####
166 # RUNS
167 #####
168
169 #Change Velocities
170
171 lx = lmp.extract_global("boxxhi", 1)
172 om = 2*pi/lx
173 if rank == 0:
174     print "Creating Shock"
175     print "lx", lx, "omega", om
176     print
177
178 n = lmp.extract_global("nlocal", 0)
179
180 xs = lmp.extract_atom("x", 3)
181 vs = lmp.extract_atom("v", 3)
182
183 #Old mean squared x0-velocity
184 v2l = 0.
185 for i in r_[0:n]:
186     v2l += vs[i][0]**2
187 v2 = comm.allreduce(v2l)
188 V = sqrt(v2/N)
189
190 #Sinus velocity distribution
191 for i in r_[0:n]:
192     vs[i][0] += fP*V*sin(om*xs[i][0])
193
194 #New mean squared x0-velocity
195 v2l = 0.
196 for i in r_[0:n]:
197     v2l += vs[i][0]**2
198 v2n = comm.allreduce(v2l)
199
200 #Set to old mean squared x0-velocity
201 f = sqrt(v2/v2n)
202 for i in r_[0:n]:
203     vs[i][0] *= f
204
205
206 for i in range(int(round(tau0/5.*50))):
207     lmp.command("balance dynamic xyz 20 1.1")
208     lmp.command("run 50 post no")
```


PUBLICATIONS

Some ideas and figures have appeared previously in the following publications:

PUBLICATIONS IN REFEREED JOURNALS

- *Substellar fragmentation in self-gravitating fluids with a major phase transition*
A. Füglistaler and D. Pfenniger, 2015
Astronomy & Astrophysics, Volume 578, id.A18
arXiv:1503.04788
- *Formation of H₂-He Substellar Bodies in Cold Conditions: Gravitational Stability of Binary Mixtures in a Phase Transition*
A. Füglistaler and D. Pfenniger, 2015
Astronomy & Astrophysics, submitted
arXiv:1507.04604

CONFERENCES PROCEEDINGS

- *Sub-stellar fragmentation in very cold molecular clouds*
A. Füglistaler and D. Pfenniger, 2015
From Interstellar Clouds to Star-Forming Galaxies:
Universal Processes?, IAU Symposium 315
IAU General Assembly 2015, Honolulu
- *Gas-solid phase transition combined with gravity*
A. Füglistaler and D. Pfenniger, 2015
Scale-Free Processes in the Universe, IAU Focus Meeting 18
IAU General Assembly 2015, Honolulu

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- Aux avancées scientifiques et technologiques.
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- Aux problèmes informatiques.
- Aux coupures d'électricité.
- À mon appendice qui a décidé de faire une inflammation un mois avant le rendu de cette thèse.

D'UNE FAÇON GÉNÉRALE, CETTE THÈSE EST DÉDICACÉE AUX ASTRONOMES ET ASTROPHYSICIENS AVEC QUI MES RELATIONS FURENT AUSSI DIVERSES QU'ENRICHISSANTES.

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